

Learning-based reinforced control strategies for autonomous vehicles

*Stratégies de contrôle renforcé par apprentissage pour les
véhicules autonomes*

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To my loving parents and wife,

supportive brothers and sisters,

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Abstract

In a world where everyone is constantly on the move and has more preferences for personal mobility, the number of cars on the road is constantly increasing. This has induced higher risks for road accidents, degraded traffic conditions, and further aggravated air pollution. Consequently, the research community has been working toward a shift to autonomous driving for decades. The latter can reshape mobility and transportation by reducing road accidents, traffic jams, and air pollution, yielding energy efficiency, convenience, and more productivity as significant driving time will be used for other activities instead.

Autonomous vehicles are complex systems consisting of several modules that perform perception, decision-making, planning, and control. The control module, consisting of longitudinal control for speed tracking and lateral control for path tracking, is essential for achieving automatic driving. Due to the highly dynamic and constantly changing nature of road environments, the control module in autonomous driving systems needs to learn and adapt to these dynamic environments by exploiting available data and using different learning techniques. This thesis contributes to the state-of-the-art enhanced control strategies applied to autonomous driving. The contributions address the longitudinal and the lateral control tasks separately and then the combined coordinated and coupled lateral and longitudinal control.

For the longitudinal control, we propose the adaptive PID approach using two techniques: Offline optimization and adaptation using genetic algorithms (GA-PID) and online learning and adaptation with neural networks (NN-PID). We introduce an adaptive MPC technique enhanced with a new, improved PSO algorithm for steering control. Then we achieve MPC online parameter adaption by using neural networks (NN-MPC) and adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference systems (ANFIS-MPC), which learn to adapt the controller to the changing working conditions and external disturbances.

For the combined coordinated lateral and longitudinal control, we propose a PSO-PID to handle the task of speed tracking and an enhanced linear parameter varying model predictive controller (LPV-MPC) to control lateral dynamics. The LPV-MPC is enhanced with an improved cost function to provide better performance and sta-

bility and formulated with an adaptive LPV model, in which a recursive estimator estimates the tire cornering stiffness coefficients. Then, we address the coupled speed and steering control by developing a more elaborate LPV-MPC capable of simultaneously handling both lateral and longitudinal vehicle dynamics. Furthermore, a neural network adapts the controller's prediction model online, and an improved genetic algorithm further optimizes its cost function.

Finally, we tackle a more challenging autonomous driving problem where the vehicle drives at its handling limits, namely autonomous racing. We introduce a real-time nonlinear model predictive controller (NMPC) coupled with a moving horizon estimator (MHE). We solve the optimal racing problem with an NMPC-based off-line trajectory planner that computes the best trajectory while considering the physical limits of the vehicle and circuit constraints. Then, we further enhance the control strategy by adding a learning extension based on Gaussian process regression. The latter improves the NMPC predictions by learning and correcting the mismatch between the actual vehicle dynamics and the NMPC prediction model.

Acronyms

ANFIS Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference System

CG Center of Gravity

CNN Convolutional Neural Network

DoF Degrees of Freedom

FMT Fast Machine Tree

GA Genetic Algorithm

GPS Global Positioning System

IMU Inertial Measurement Unit

LIDAR Light Detection And Ranging

LMI Linear Matrix Inequality

LPV Linear Parameter Varying

LQR Linear Quadratic Regulator

LTV Linear Time Varying

MDP Markov Decision Process

MHE Moving Horizon Estimator

MIMO Multi-Input Multi-Output

MLP Multi-Layer Perceptron

MPC Model Predictive Control

MSE Mean Squared Error

NLP Nonlinear Optimization Problem

NMPC Nonlinear Model Predictive Control

NN Neural Network

PID Proportional Integral Derivative

PRM Probabilistic Road Maps

PSO Particle Swarm Optimization

QP Quadratic Programming

RADAR Radio Detection And Ranging

RBFNN Radial Basis Function Neural Network

RLS Recursive Least Squares

RMSE Root Mean Squared Error

RNN Recurrent Neural Network

RRT Rapidly-exploring Random Tree

SMC Sliding Mode Control

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Chapter 1

General Introduction

1.1 Context and Motivation

The ever-increasing populations in most countries have led to a constantly increasing need for more transportation systems. The number of road cars has exploded lately, inducing degraded traffic conditions and increased air pollution. Population growth also limits access to housing in big cities, which means most people live far from work and spend countless hours commuting between home and work, using transportation systems or driving personal vehicles. Prolonged driving induces strain and raises the possibility of road accidents, which has been a major public safety concern for decades. In fact, road accidents are now causing around 1.35 million deaths and more than 50 million injuries worldwide on a yearly basis, which makes them the 8th leading cause of mortality [1]. In France, around 3300 people die yearly from road accidents with car users representing the major fatalities [2]. These facts have urged the United Nations and World Health Organization to embark on global plans to halve road deaths and injuries before 2030. The increasing need for safer and more reliable transportation, improved traffic conditions, and reduced air pollution has motivated the research to accelerate the development of self-driving technology. The latter has been a research trend during the last decades, being among the technologies that are expected to completely change people's lifestyles. The shift towards autonomous driving has been further encouraged by the recent developments in artificial intelligence, big data, and information processing techniques. Autonomous driving will considerably reduce road accidents, traffic congestion, and air pollution by excluding human error, increasing route sharing, and improving mobility intelligence. More-

over, energy consumption will be optimized and time spent on driving will be used for other productive activities. Consequently, researchers are working toward full autonomy to reduce human error and mitigate the risks and dangers of manual driving which accounts for almost 96% of all car accidents in the US [3]. The development of self-driving technologies has had a long history. The idea of autonomous vehicles first appeared in the 1920s, but it was perceived as a mere fantasy until the 1980s when they turned into a real possibility after the work of Ernst Dickmanns [4]. Significant research was conducted as part of the PROMETHEUS project, to develop a real autonomous vehicle. The project demonstrated in 1994 an autonomous car known as VaMP, which realized a 1,600 km drive with a total of 95% autonomously driven. Later in 1995, CMU NAVLAB achieved a 5,000 km drive of which 98% was autonomously driven across the US [4]. One of the major milestones in autonomous driving technology is the DARPA grand challenge [5], which has further inspired researchers in the field. The aim of this challenge was for driverless cars to carry an off-road race without any human intervention, this was the first event to completely exclude the human from the loop. The DARPA urban challenge [6] took place in 2007, it aimed for autonomous vehicles to navigate urban settings in a simulated environment. Ever since, numerous autonomous driving challenges took place including the Hyundai autonomous challenge [7], the VisLab intercontinental autonomous challenge [8] and China's intelligent vehicle future challenge [9]. Research in the field started accelerating afterward in academia and industry. For instance, the Autopilot system of Tesla has received significant advances, and Waymo, Google's autonomous driving system [10], has achieved great advancements in the field, with over 10 million miles of road testing and 7 billion miles of virtual testing. Other similar challenges include the recent F1/10 racing challenge [11], and the Formula Student Driverless (FSD) competition [12]. Fig. 1.1 shows the Stanley car that won the 2005 DARPA grand challenge, Waymo's autonomous vehicle, the Gotthard driverless racing platform used in FSD competition, and the F1/10 autonomous driving platform. The automatic driving systems in the vehicles shown in the figure comprise many modules that work in a coordinated way. The perception module consists of multiple sensors such as cameras, Global Positioning System (GPS), Light Detection And Ranging (LIDAR), Radio Detection And Ranging (RADAR), and Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU). A

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Figure 1.1: (a) Stanley car, (b) Waymo autonomous vehicle, (c) Gotthard driverless race car, (d) F1/10 Platform.

variety of algorithms are used by the perception module to sense the environment and obtain relevant information. The planning and decision-making module uses sensor data to make decisions and plan the speed and trajectory profiles. These decisions are executed by the control module. Control is one of the most important tasks to achieve autonomous driving. Generally, the control module is divided into longitudinal and lateral control, longitudinal control handles speed tracking, and lateral control ensures accurate steering. This is achieved by commanding the different actuators such as the accelerator, the brakes, and the steering wheel. Fig. 1.2 shows a general overview of automatic driving systems. In addition, the environments where autonomous vehicles operate are highly dynamic and constantly changing. Thus, the control systems need to be capable of learning these changes and adapting to them by exploiting available data and making use of different learning techniques. The SAE standard J3016 [13] divides vehicle autonomy into 5 automation levels. Level 0 with

no automation represents the conventional cars. In level 1, simple automatic driving systems like adaptive cruise control and electronic stability control are deployed into the vehicle. Advanced systems like speed and steering control or emergency braking are introduced in level 2. In level 3, the vehicle is capable of sensing the environment through multiple sensors, and it is able to drive autonomously while requiring driver supervision and intervention in infeasible situations. The vehicle is autonomous in level 4, with only occasional driver intervention for certain driving modes only. Level 5 vehicles are completely autonomous, they handle all driving modes without any supervision [4].

Figure 1.2: Overview of an automated driving system.

1.2 Objectives

Based on the different challenges raised in the context and motivation section, the main objectives of this thesis are summarized as follows:

- Study and investigate the current vehicle modeling techniques for control design, and determine their suitability based on the driving scenario.
- Investigate the possibility of optimizing existing control techniques using learning approaches and meta-heuristic algorithms.
- Exploit data-based approaches to improve the existing classical control strategies, both in terms of modeling and control algorithm.

- Develop adaptive control strategies to learn to cope with dynamic environments and adapt to constantly changing working conditions.
- Apply the developed strategies to the different control tasks of autonomous driving.

1.3 Thesis Outline

The content of this manuscript is divided into 7 chapters, where the main contributions are on the longitudinal control, the lateral control, and the combined lateral and longitudinal control for autonomous vehicles. Therefore, the content of each chapter is briefly described.

- **Chapter 2:** provides a recent literature review on the most widely used control strategies and motion planning algorithms in autonomous driving. The chapter covers both model-based and data-based control strategies and provides a general discussion on the strengths and weaknesses of each method based on the latest corresponding research. Furthermore, planning algorithms like graph-based, sampling-based, and optimization-based approaches are also compared and evaluated.
- **Chapter 3:** presents a variety of models that are often used to describe the vehicle's behavior for control design. The main modeling techniques include geometric, kinematic, and dynamic modeling approaches, in addition to combined modeling approaches. Tire modeling is also discussed in detail, and several tire models are exposed and compared. Finally, a brief discussion on Linear Parameter Varying (LPV) modeling is provided at the end.
- **Chapter 4:** addresses the problem of longitudinal control in autonomous driving, it introduces the self-adaptive Proportional Integral Derivative (PID) control strategy. First, a Genetic Algorithm (GA) is proposed to fine-tune the PID gains in different driving scenarios, then a lookup table technique is introduced to adapt the PID controller online (denoted GA-PID). Second, an approach using a shallow online-learning Neural Network (NN) is proposed to

simultaneously optimize and adapt the PID controller (denoted NN-PID). This technique uses the PID equations to learn to optimize its gains and requires only the tracking error and the control signals.

- **Chapter 5:** studies the lateral control task for autonomous driving, commonly known as path tracking. This chapter proposes the optimal adaptive Model Predictive Control (MPC) control using three distinct methods. An improved Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) algorithm is introduced to optimize the different MPC parameters that are required to design the controller. The optimization is carried out for a variety of driving scenarios, and the data of optimal parameters generated by the PSO algorithm is stored to be used by a lookup table for the online MPC adaptation. The MPC is developed using Quadratic Programming (QP) where the control signal is approximated with Laguerre functions to allow the use of long prediction and control horizons without affecting the computation time. In the second and third methods, two systems using feed-forward neural networks and Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference System (ANFIS) are proposed to learn the data of optimal MPC parameters and perform online control adaptation (denoted NN-MPC and ANFIS-MPC, respectively).
- **Chapter 6:** consists of 2 parts and deals with the combined lateral and longitudinal control of autonomous vehicles. In the first part, the coordinated control strategy is introduced where the speed tracking is ensured with a PSO-optimized PID controller which is coordinated with an LPV-MPC controller for vehicle steering. The prediction model of the formulated LPV-MPC is adaptive in the sense that the cornering stiffness coefficients are estimated online by a Recursive Least Squares (RLS) algorithm and adapted. In the second approach, the coupled control strategy is addressed by developing a more elaborate LPV-MPC controller capable of handling both speed and steering control. Furthermore, the controller is optimized with an improved GA algorithm, and its prediction model is adaptive, where the cornering stiffness coefficients are predicted by a deep neural network that requires measurable parameters only.

- **Chapter 7:** tackles a more challenging problem, it addresses the control and state estimation for autonomous racing which is a sub-field of autonomous driving. The chapter provides a comprehensive set-up for autonomous racing, the control strategy is based on Nonlinear Model Predictive Control (NMPC). Gaussian process regression is used to learn and correct the mismatch between the true vehicle dynamics and the prediction model of the NMPC. The controller is further complemented with a Moving Horizon Estimator (MHE). Furthermore, the racing path is planned offline to ensure optimal racing performance.
- **Chapter 8:** is a general conclusion of the work presented in this manuscript, it summarizes the main contributions and the obtained results. Future perspectives and constructive remarks are also provided in this chapter, which aims to further improve and complete the presented contributions.

1.4 List of Publications

This section lists the academic publications realized during the course of this PhD thesis, including both accepted and under revision articles.

Published articles

1. Y. Kebbati, N. Ait-Oufroukh, D. Ichalal, and V. Vigneron, “Lateral control for autonomous wheeled vehicles: A technical review,” *Asian Journal of Control*, 2022.
2. Y. Kebbati, N. Ait-Oufroukh, P. Vicenc, V. Vigneron, and D. Ichalal, “Autonomous driving using GA-optimized neural network based adaptive LPV-MPC controller,” in *2022 IEEE International Conference on Networking, Sensing and Control (ICNSC)*, IEEE, vol. 1, 2022, pp. 1–6.
3. Y. Kebbati, N. Ait-Oufroukh, V. Vigneron, and D. Ichalal, “Coordinated PSO-PID based longitudinal control with LPV-MPC based lateral control for autonomous vehicles,” in *2022 European Control Conference (ECC)*, IEEE, 2022, pp. 518–523.

4. Y. Kebbati, N. Ait-Oufroukh, V. Vigneron, and D. Ichalal, “Neural network and ANFIS based auto-adaptive MPC for path tracking in autonomous vehicles,” in 2021 IEEE International Conference on Networking, Sensing and Control (ICNSC), IEEE, vol. 1, 2021, pp. 1–6.
5. W. Stróżecki, N. Ait-Oufroukh, Y. Kebbati, D. Ichalal, and S. Mammar, “Automatic tuning of MPC for autonomous vehicle using bayesian optimization,” in 2021 IEEE International Conference on Networking, Sensing and Control (ICNSC), IEEE, vol. 1, 2021.
6. Y. Kebbati, V. Puig, N. Ait-Oufroukh, V. Vigneron, and D. Ichalal, “Optimized adaptive MPC for lateral control of autonomous vehicles,” in 2021 9th International Conference on Control, Mechatronics and Automation (ICCMA), IEEE, 2021, pp. 95–103.
7. Y. Kebbati, N. Ait-Oufroukh, V. Vigneron, D. Ichalal, and D. Gruyer, “Optimized self-adaptive PID speed control for autonomous vehicles,” in 2021 26th International Conference on Automation and Computing (ICAC), pp. 1–6, IEEE, 2021.

Under revision

1. Y. Kebbati, N. Ait-Oufroukh, D. Ichalal, and V. Vigneron, “RNN-based linear parameter varying adaptive model predictive control for autonomous driving” Asian Journal of Control, Mars 2023.
2. Y. Kebbati, N. Ait-Oufroukh, V. Vigneron, and D. Ichalal, “Learning-based model predictive control with moving horizon state estimation for autonomous racing,” International Journal of Control, May 2023.

Chapter 2

Background and State of the Art

Summary

This chapter provides general background information on autonomous driving technology; it gives an overview of the most widely used model-based and data-driven strategies for controlling autonomous vehicles. The chapter mainly focuses on lateral control and coupled control strategies and presents the latest corresponding research while discussing and comparing the strengths and weaknesses of each strategy. Motion planning algorithms, including graph-based, sampling-based, and optimization-based techniques, are also briefly reviewed. Finally, a comparative summary of the presented control approaches is provided in a table. This chapter is partially based on the following work:

- [14] Y. Kebbati, N. Ait-Oufroukh, D. Ichalal, and V. Vigneron, “Lateral control for autonomous wheeled vehicles: A technical review,” *Asian Journal of Control*, 2022.
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2.1 Introduction

Automatic control is an essential task for autonomous driving systems; it solves the problem of following a set reference defined as a path or a speed profile depending on the type of control task. Nonetheless, control is a complex task for autonomous vehicles because it must guarantee the stability of the vehicle and ensure certain levels of performance. In general, the control task accounts for three aspects [15]:

- The type of control can be lateral control, longitudinal control, or both at the same time.
- The vehicle model used for implementing the control can be kinematic or dynamic and linear or nonlinear.
- The control strategy can be coupled, coordinated, in cascade, etc.

Longitudinal control handles the longitudinal dynamics of the vehicle, namely the acceleration, to follow a predefined speed profile, the latter depends on the driving scenario. In urban driving, for instance, it depends mostly on speed limits, while for racing applications, it mostly depends on the handling limits of the vehicle. Lateral control deals with the yaw motion of the vehicle by acting on the steering angle of the front wheels. The goal is to follow a trajectory by reducing the angular and lateral position errors to zero. The trajectory can be predefined and generated offline or computed online, such as for obstacle avoidance and lane change maneuvers [16]. Lane keeping is completely dependent on lateral control where lanes can be detected from camera footage using image processing techniques or advanced deep learning methods. Generally speaking, two main streams are distinguished in the control approach; model-based techniques that require a model of the vehicle, and data-driven approaches which are mostly based on artificial intelligence. Sections 2 and 3 discuss several model-based controllers and other types of control. Model-free controllers are described in section 4, while section 5 discusses different planning approaches for autonomous driving.

2.2 Model-based Controllers

Model-based controllers require a model that describes the motion of the vehicle, these models are usually kinematic or dynamic depending on the type of controller, and can be linearized or nonlinear. Numerous studies have been carried out for model-based control, the following subsections present the most common controllers and the corresponding latest research.

2.2.1 Model predictive control

Model predictive control is a well-established strategy known as receding horizon control. MPC is based on formulating an optimization problem in the form of a finite horizon open-loop optimal control problem. The main idea of MPC is in using the discrete model of the system for predicting its behavior into the future, up to a specific time step called prediction horizon. A control input sequence is generated along several discrete time steps known as the control horizon. The control sequence solves

the optimization problem by minimizing a cost function while obeying certain constraints. At each time step, a finite horizon window (prediction horizon) is shifted, and new measurements of the system and the environment are used to solve the optimization problem resulting in a new control sequence. The whole process is repeated iteratively, and only the first control input is applied to the system. The advantage of MPC control is its ability to handle Multi-Input Multi-Output (MIMO) constraints that represent limitations on the actuators or physical and safety constraints. More details about MPC, its variants and its applications can be found in surveys [17], and [18].

In autonomous vehicle control, the MPC controller is generally composed of an optimizer and a prediction model that describes the vehicle’s behavior as demonstrated in Fig. 2.1. The optimizer oversees finding the optimal input by minimizing a cost function. The type of MPC controller depends on the vehicle model used for prediction. NMPC is very accurate but computationally expensive and often unsuitable for real-time applications. In contrast, linear MPC provides a better choice for real-time applications but compromises tracking accuracy.

Figure 2.1: MPC block diagram.

MPC is very suitable for the lateral control of autonomous vehicles since it can systematically handle constraints. Several studies have been published recently that show the excellent performance achieved by MPC and its ability to overcome model impressions and external disturbances. Yao *et al.* [19] proposed an MPC path tracking controller with longitudinal speed compensation to overcome the assumption of constant longitudinal speed along the control horizon. The speed compensation aims to reduce the control deviation due to the rapid speed and acceleration variations which affect the path tracking accuracy. The authors used the single-track bicycle

model with Fiala brush tire model [20] in the MPC design with constraints set on the tire cornering capabilities, the side-slip angle, the input, and the input rate. The compensation for the longitudinal speed is ensured by varying the velocity with constant acceleration. The proposed approach was evaluated against standard MPC through `MATLAB/Carsim` co-simulations where similar performance was observed during gentle curve variations, but the designed controller performed much better in sudden curvature variations.

Alcalá *et al.* developed in their work [21] a solution for the mixed lateral and longitudinal control for trajectory tracking. They divided the control strategy into a cascade control scheme with an internal layer to control the vehicle dynamics (velocity) and an external layer that controls the vehicle kinematics (position and orientation). The controller of the internal loop is a Linear Quadratic Regulator (LQR) formulated using the LPV approach as a dynamic (LPV-LQR) design, the employed LPV representation was transformed from the nonlinear model presented previously in [15]. The controller in the external loop was formulated as a quadratic optimization problem using the nonlinear kinematic model in an LPV form (Kinematic LPV-MPC), it controls the position and orientation of the vehicle. The designed control strategy was evaluated in `MATLAB` for a curved circuit using the dynamics of an electric rear-wheel drive car. The performances were compared to the NMPC controller, and the results showed that the LPV-MPC had similar performance to NMPC except for handling external disturbances. On the other hand, the LPV-MPC proved to be 50 times faster than the NMPC, which is very important for real-time applications. NMPC has been used in combination with multi-sensor fusion in [22], the authors aimed at exploring a parking lot autonomously and performing a parking maneuver. Three modules have been employed; a sensor fusion module for localization, mapping, and obstacle detection, a decision-making module for detecting parking spaces and for guidance, and a control module based on the NMPC strategy. The kinematic single-track model was used in this study as it is sufficient for the low speeds and small external forces encountered in a parking maneuver.

Li *et al.* [23] proposed an NMPC for trajectory tracking, the controller was based on nonlinear vehicle dynamics, and Pacejka tire model [24], and it tracks the yaw angle and lateral position. The authors used the Sigmoid function to generate a smoothly

curved reference. The NMPC was formulated as a standard optimization problem by discretizing the system dynamic equations, and constraints were imposed on the control input and incremental control to prevent actuator saturation. The performance evaluation was done through simulations in `Carsim` and `MATLAB` by comparing the NMPC to the Linear Time Varying (LTV) version of MPC; (LTV-MPC). The results showed better performance for NMPC against LTV-MPC which exhibited frequent oscillations with higher overshoots and less precision. However, the NMPC required very long computations compared to the LTV-MPC controller. LPV-MPC was used by Alcalá *et al.* [25] as a novel approach to perform autonomous racing, where an offline nonlinear model predictive planner was used to compute the optimal racing trajectory. The LPV-MPC approach was then used online to track the generated trajectory, it uses the standard nonlinear dynamic bicycle model to capture vehicle dynamics. The proposed control approach was evaluated through simulations and real experiments in a proposed circuit, where the trajectory planner aims to minimize the lap time, and the LPV-MPC aims to track the optimal trajectory. The results showed fast lap times and good trajectory tracking with certain errors attributed to non-modeled dynamics.

In [26], Wang *et al.* proposed an improved MPC control strategy that includes an adaptive fuzzy controller to change the weights of the cost function. The aim of this design is to tackle the problem of ride discomfort caused by fixed weights in classical MPC. The fuzzy controller uses five fuzzy sets, it has as inputs the errors of the lateral position and the heading and generates the weighting matrices for the cost function. The designed MPC was compared to pure-pursuit and standard MPC to evaluate its performance and ability to handle the ride discomfort problem. The comparison was done through `MATLAB/Carsim` co-simulations, and the results proved that it is more accurate than the pure-pursuit controller while providing smoother steering angle changes compared to the standard MPC. Xu *et al.* [27] designed a lane-keeping system based on LTV-MPC. In their work, the reference trajectory was generated by fitting five preview points to reduce the number of sensors needed, and the LTV-MPC was based on the linearized bicycle model. The trajectory tracking was solved as a QP problem, where the solution is a vector of optimal steering angles. The LTV-MPC controller was evaluated through `MATLAB/Carsim` co-simulation, and

the results showed good tracking performance in low and high speeds. However, some acceptable overshoots in steering angles were produced at high speeds.

Sun *et al.* [28] proposed an MPC with switched tracking errors to tackle the tracking deviation and overshoot at high speeds. A fuzzy-logic classifier was used to determine the switching phase and instant, the controller used the velocity heading deviation as the tracking error instead of the vehicle heading deviation. The fuzzy classifier switches between the real-time side-slip and steady-state side-slip so that the MPC computes the velocity heading deviation in the transient and steady-state conditions, respectively. The MPC controller was based on the single-track bicycle model with the Fiala brush tire model to capture the vehicle’s lateral dynamics. The latter was compared to the standard MPC and to MPC with fixed side-slip (steady-state or real-time). The designed controller achieved very high tracking accuracy. It scored the lowest tracking deviation Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) value but failed to reject disturbances and model uncertainties. Guo *et al.* [29] proposed an MPC path following controller that considers road regions delimited by curves and measurable disturbances accounting for model mismatch and small angle assumptions. The MPC was based on the bicycle dynamic model that includes measurable disturbances. The authors introduced a differential evolution algorithm to ensure faster online optimization. The proposed path following controller was tested on an experimental platform, where it outperformed PID and standard MPC, showing promising computation and control performances.

The authors of [30] developed an online learning MPC controller for autonomous racing. They adopted a simple dynamic bicycle model and improved it by learning the model errors online using Gaussian process regression [31]. The control problem was formulated as a contouring-based MPC [32] with a learning-based extension. The authors used the Gotthard autonomous vehicle (see Fig. 1.1c) to test the proposed controller which achieved improved performance and 10% shorter lap times compared to the standard controller without the learning extension. Paper [11] also dealt with autonomous race driving using NMPC for the F1/10 platform (see Fig. 1.1d). To keep the vehicle inside the track, the authors interpolated the circuit boundaries using 3rd order polynomials and implemented them as inequality constraints on the lateral position. A feed-forward neural network was introduced in the paper to learn to

mimic the NMPC using input-output data. In the same racing context, Verschueren *et al.* [33] handled autonomous racing as a time-optimal problem, in which a slip-free kinematic bicycle model was used to build an NMPC controller. The key objective is minimizing lap time, which is achieved by a spatial reformulation of the model to include time as an optimization variable. Simulations and experiments were conducted using **ACADO** for solving the Nonlinear Optimization Problem (NLP).

The same authors extended their work in [34], by including a full nonlinear dynamic bicycle model and using the same time-optimal control approach with spatial reformulation. In a similar approach, Kloeser *et al.* [35] addressed autonomous racing for a 1:43 scale race car using a singularity-free path parametric model for NMPC predictions. Contrary to [33], they used partial spatial reformulation of the model to exclude singularities. The authors implemented obstacle avoidance in the optimization problem as a constraint with the objective of maximizing progress on the path. The designed controller was validated both in simulation and experimentation, leading to good racing performance. Betz provides in [36] a thorough survey in the field of autonomous racing, where vehicles are driven at the limits of their performance with high speeds and accelerations.

2.2.2 Sliding mode control

Sliding Mode Control (SMC) is a robust control technique suitable for nonlinear systems with parametric uncertainties that are subject to external disturbances. In the SMC strategy, the states and control signals are not affected by the disturbances and uncertainties, because they are considered to be discontinuous. This technique forces the system to slide (converge) in a sliding surface by applying a fast switching control signal. The design of SMC controllers is a two-part task; the desired dynamics are defined by the sliding surface in the first part such that the design specifications are satisfied by the sliding motion. The second part is the design of a switching function that ensures the system slides in the desired sliding surface. The theory of SMC is reviewed in detail in [37]. The downside of SMC technique is its application limit due to its fast-switching nature which results in the chattering phenomenon. In reality, the actuators suffer from imperfections and delays, therefore, the SMC chattering phenomenon may damage the actuators, and result in discomfort or energy loss which

also creates additional disturbances. Researchers have adopted several methods to deal with this phenomenon, these methods include using higher order sliding mode [38], the use of smooth functions to replace the discontinuous sign function, and the inclusion of observers [39].

Many researchers adopted the SMC control technique to control autonomous vehicles. For instance, Wu *et al.* [40] designed a path following strategy based on SMC. They used the non-singular terminal sliding mode technique. The control problem was simplified into a yaw-tracking task to ensure that the displacement deviation converges to zero. The linearized dynamic bicycle model was used in the SMC design. Fig. 2.2 shows the path following algorithm where the linear-ESO is used to estimate the state and disturbance of the simplified yaw tracking system which ensures that the control algorithm works well even without an accurate mathematical model. The NTSM block represents the SMC controller which was based on a non-singular terminal sliding surface. Moreover, the controller was coupled with an exponential convergence law to improve the convergence speed. Simulations in *Carsim* showed solid performance of the designed SMC controller and proved its abilities to overcome uncertainties, reject disturbances, and achieve very small tracking errors.

Figure 2.2: Path following control algorithm [40].

Kada *et al.* [41] proposed a robust SMC that eliminates the drawbacks of regular SMC controllers. The authors used a disturbance observer to enhance the controller, a neural network was used to estimate model uncertainties, and a fuzzy logic system was added to handle parameter variations. The disturbance observer, detailed in [42], estimates the mismatch disturbances such as wind and unmodeled dynamics. The model uncertainties are estimated through a Radial Basis Function Neural Network (RBFNN) formed by three layers. The algorithm of this neural network approximates the different functions of the model. The fuzzy system was used for scheduling the

gains of the sign function in the SMC controller [43]. For performance evaluation, the authors compared their controller to traditional SMC, observer-based SMC and back-stepping SMC. The proposed controller ensured very fast convergence thanks to gain scheduling with the fuzzy system. In addition, the controller provided very precise tracking that easily overcame the other controllers even in sharp turns while eliminating the chattering problem.

The authors of [44] designed an adaptive distributed SMC for vehicular platooning. A distributed sliding surface for all the followers was used to control the full platoon. To ensure ride comfort, the authors employed an adaptive law to replace the switching function and compensate for model errors and avoid jerks. They proposed a structural decomposition method to decouple the sliding motion dynamics of the platoon. Moreover, they ensured the smoothness and quickness of the control by placing the poles of the sliding motion in predefined regions using Linear Matrix Inequality (LMI) approach. It was found that the performance of the designed controller was satisfactory, even though the platoon was composed of vehicles with uncertain parameters. However, the control performance was heavily affected by the interaction topology of the platoon. Norouzi *et al.* [45] designed an adaptive SMC for the task of autonomous lane change, the authors used a fuzzy boundary layer to address the chattering issues. The path planning for the lane change was performed using the mathematical quintic function and vehicle boundary conditions, and the vehicle lateral dynamics were modeled using the dynamic bicycle model. The authors tested their controller in *Carsim* under different road conditions and compared it to standard SMC. The results showed significant improvements, the use of adaptive rules improved the controller such that the range of uncertainties were no longer needed to be known and the use of the fuzzy boundary layer achieved smaller tracking errors.

Wang *et al.* [46] also worked on the path tracking problem, where they proposed an automatic steering control strategy based on the back-stepping sliding mode control. For higher precision modeling, the authors used both kinematic and dynamic vehicle models as well as a vehicle-road system model. To address the chattering problem, the authors replaced the sign function of the SMC by saturation and introduced a sliding mode term that overcomes disturbances and ensures the system state is always on the sliding surface which in turn guarantees robustness. The proposed strategy was

evaluated in *Carsim* and on a real vehicle at low speeds and closed road conditions. The results showed that the proposed strategy significantly improved the steering performance. In the same context, Alike *et al.* [47] improved the work presented in [39], which addressed the lateral control of autonomous vehicles using a higher order SMC with the super twisting algorithm. The authors enhanced the SMC by optimizing the controller performance using the PSO algorithm. They performed the optimization for two cases; first, they optimized the sliding surface parameters and then the controller parameters. The conducted simulations showed that the proposed controller outperformed the SMC developed in [39] and guaranteed much better trajectory tracking and more robustness.

2.2.3 H_∞ control

H_∞ is a robust control method that easily handles modeling uncertainties and external disturbances. The objective is to minimize the H_∞ norm of the system to be controlled by solving an optimization problem that involves the Riccati equation. The control problem formulation usually accounts for noise, modeling uncertainties, and disturbances and is solved through LMI methods to determine a state feedback gain. Although the H_∞ approach is known for robust stability and performance, it may easily become difficult to implement in practice. More details about H_∞ control theory and design can be found in [48].

Numerous research papers dealing with H_∞ for controlling autonomous vehicles exist in the literature. For instance, Sun *et al.* [49] developed a fuzzy model-based H_∞ controller with feed-forward for the lateral control of autonomous vehicles. The authors considered the desired yaw rate as an external disturbance of the vehicle dynamics and used the feed-forward loop to improve the performance of the closed-loop system. They used the bicycle kinematic model for the feed-forward loop and the bicycle dynamic model for the feedback loop. Fuzzy modeling was used to express the variation of vehicle's velocity and mass, which can change with the number of passengers onboard. The effectiveness of the proposed controller was demonstrated in *Simulink/Carsim* co-simulations. He *et al.* [50], proposed a robust H_∞ coordination control strategy to improve lateral motion control at handling limits. The approach was based on LMI method and coordinates front and rear wheel steering. The pro-

posed controller was verified on dry asphalt through `Simulink/Carsim` co-simulations where external disturbances on the front and rear vehicle axles were included. The results showed high path-tracking capabilities close to driving limits and proved that the proposed approach is robust to uncertain external disturbances.

Hu *et al.* [51], proposed a robust H_∞ control strategy for path following where the vehicle’s lateral velocity was not required to be known. The developed output feedback controller was based on a mixed approach involving a GA and LMI to obtain the optimal feedback gain. The approach takes into account both model and road uncertainties and external disturbances. The designed controller was tested for a lane change maneuver on a low-adherence road and for a J-turn maneuver on a high-adherence road under tough conditions. The results proved good overall performance and robustness. An LPV H_∞ controller for high-speed driving and evasive maneuvers was designed in [52] by Corno *et al.* Contrary to the feed-forward approach, the design was based on the lateral error and look-ahead distance of the vehicle to ensure better robustness. Moreover, the actuator nonlinearities under low speeds were taken into consideration. The proposed controller was experimentally validated on an instrumented vehicle for different bends and double lane change maneuvers, where sufficient and adequate performance for autonomous driving was achieved.

Chaib *et al.* [53] compared H_∞ to self-adaptive, fuzzy and PID controllers for the lateral control task. The H_∞ controller was designed based on the loop shape procedure and tested against the others under variable road adhesion and lateral wind disturbances. The simulation results favored the self-adaptive controller. However, the H_∞ along with the fuzzy controller performed just as well, while the PID controller was found to be the worst. Yang *et al.* [54] compared H_∞ with MPC for trajectory tracking control using a 3 Degrees of Freedom (DoF) vehicle dynamic model. The two controllers were tested for curves and double lane change maneuvers in `MATLAB/Carsim` co-simulations. The results showed that MPC outperformed H_∞ in terms of accuracy and response time. However, when tough conditions were introduced, H_∞ was able to achieve higher longitudinal speeds compared to its rival. Wang *et al.* [55] developed a robust H_∞ controller that takes into account estimation and measurement delays, and data dropouts through a general representation. The design of the proposed controller was enhanced by including varying external

disturbances. In addition, the uncertainties due to tire cornering stiffness coefficients were also included. Simulation results verified the effectiveness of the proposed approach, where good tracking was achieved even though the authors focused mainly on time-invariant delays and data dropouts which can be time-varying and unknown.

2.2.4 Linear quadratic regulator

The LQR approach is an optimal control technique that achieves excellent results at minimum cost. The idea is similar to MPC where a quadratic cost function is minimized resulting in an optimal feedback gain, this is achieved by solving the Riccati equation which is formulated based on the plant’s state space model.

Paper [56] developed an LQR-based lateral controller with road disturbance compensation, the road was modeled using clothoid cubic polynomials, and a dynamic lateral model with look-ahead distance was adopted. The authors redesigned the state reference by adding an additional term to compensate for the winding road disturbance. Experimental tests showed superior performance of the LQR with disturbance compensation compared to the standard LQR controller. Riofrio *et al.* [57] designed an LQR that handles lateral stability and rollover control taking into account the road bank angle, which was estimated using a Kalman filter. Several tests were carried out in `Trucksim` where the proposed LQR controller was compared to a fuzzy controller. The results showed significant improvements in load transfer, yaw rate, roll, and side-slip angles. Good vehicle behavior was achieved in banked surfaces, and the designed controller was able to prevent over-steering effects often caused by rollover controllers. Paper [58] conducted a comparative study between LQR, MPC, and Stanley controller for path tracking applications. The kinematic bicycle model was used, and the controllers were tested in `CarMaker` simulator. LQR and MPC provided optimal results compared to Stanley. MPC outperformed LQR at the expense of higher computation loads.

Articulated heavy-duty vehicles have large sizes and experience important mass variations which result in poor maneuverability. In this regard, Barbosa *et al.* [59] improved a robust LQR (RLQR) previously developed in [60] to take into account parametric variations. The proposed controller does not depend on offline parameter tuning, but rather uses an over-time vanishing penalty parameter to foresee smooth-

ness and robustness and maintain optimality. The proposed controller was evaluated against robust H_∞ , where the vehicle was subject to variable loads. The results showed a smoother and more robust performance of RLQR, especially for high loads with mass uncertainties. Kim *et al.* [61] also worked on the lateral control of articulated vehicles, the authors designed an active steering controller based on LQR theory. The articulated vehicle was modeled by a 3DoF representation where key parameters were identified with simulated annealing particle swarm optimization (SAPSO). The proposed LQR controller aims at minimizing yaw tracking error and side-slip angle simultaneously for both tractor and trailer. The performance of the proposed control strategy was validated through `Trucksim` simulations, and the results were satisfactory at low and high-speed maneuvers.

Authors of [62] addressed the lateral control of autonomous vehicles using a Lyapunov-based method with an LQR-LMI tuning approach. The controller was developed with an LPV kinematic bicycle model, and the resolution of the LQR-LMI determined optimal control parameters. To further complement the tuning process, the authors added a pole placement constraint to guarantee maximum achievable performance. The proposed control technique achieved good autonomous guidance in virtual reality and real scenario tests.

2.3 Other Control Methods

Other controllers include PID control which is often enhanced with neural networks or fuzzy logic systems to be adaptive to external disturbances and varying parameters [63–65]. Back-stepping control which is a recursive method that associates the Lyapunov function with feedback control [66–69]. Geometry-based controllers like the pure pursuit [70–72] and Stanley controller [73–75]. Several other techniques are developed in the literature.

For instance, Chen *et al.* [76] worked on autonomous parking. They introduced an adaptive pseudo-spectral method for solving time and energy optimal control for parking applications, which was handled as a nonlinear programming problem. The approach was compared to interior point and piecewise Gauss pseudo-spectral resolution methods. Simulations showed higher computation efficiency and better control

accuracy. Li *et al.* [77] used the hierarchical control method to reduce tire slip energy and improve vehicle stability with time-varying tire cornering stiffness and tire slip energy torque distribution. The authors handled tire slip energy with a scheme of semi-empirical tire slip energy model used with the previously mentioned hierarchical control, which ensures active steering and yaw control. Simulation results proved that considering time-varying cornering stiffness and tire slip energy has significant advantages on the control performance.

Paper [78] proposed a disturbance observer-based state-error port-controlled Hamiltonian (DOBC-SEPCH) control strategy to optimize energy consumption and enhance the tracking performance of unmanned surface vehicles. A disturbance observer was introduced to estimate environmental perturbations coupled with an energy-based controller, designed using the SEPCH technique. The performance of the proposed approach was validated in simulations with stability insurance. Several other geometric, kinematic, and dynamic controllers are reported in [79].

2.4 Model-free Control

Besides model-based controllers, model-free controllers provide an alternative solution when modeling becomes complex or inaccurate. Such types of control strategies are mostly data-driven. Data from sensors like camera, LIDAR, and IMU are exploited to predict control signals for the steering, acceleration, or braking actions.

2.4.1 Supervised learning control

Neural networks have seen huge advancements recently, especially in the fields of computer vision and control [80]. Autonomous driving applications are primarily based on fully connected neural networks, Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) and Recurrent Neural Network (RNN). Fully connected networks are composed of multiple layers of neurons interconnected by synaptic weights, they are inspired by brain neural networks. Generally, they consist of one input layer, one output layer, and one or more hidden layers which define the depth of the network. The training process of neural networks is mainly based on the gradient descent algorithm. The forward pass propagates the inputs throughout the network layers, where each neuron normalizes

its output by an activation function like the Sigmoid or the ReLU. The prediction error at the output layer is back-propagated throughout the network to readjust its weights. CNNs differ from fully connected networks as they contain convolution layers whose neurons are connected to only some neurons of the next layer. Weights are shared between multiple connections, which greatly reduces network complexity in terms of trainable parameters leading to faster training. On the other hand, RNNs are able to retain memory. They contain feedback loops where layer outputs are not only sent to the next layer but also sent back to the previous layers. Common training problems in these types of neural networks include the vanishing and exploding gradients [81], making the task of hyperparameter tuning more difficult. A typical example of each network is illustrated in Fig. 2.3.

Figure 2.3: Examples of neural network based controllers.

For instance, paper [82] used deep learning to control vehicle lateral and longitudinal motion. The authors used CNN in two different models; the first model tries to handle both control tasks at once, and the second model consists of two CNN-based controllers for separate steering and speed controls. Although different architectures with varying complexities were tested in the first model, none of them was able to handle the task and find patterns between input images and output control signals. However, using two separate CNN networks managed to achieve acceptable results where full autonomy was achieved on two different racing tracks. The authors used

the TORCS simulator for data collection and control tests. A complex CNN network was required for the steering task, while the speed control network was much simpler. Nevertheless, data collection and training remain tedious tasks in such strategies.

Jhung *et al.* [83] proposed end-to-end steering control with CNN-based closed-loop feedback. The authors divided the training process into supervised pre-training and reinforced closed-loop post-training where the latter improves the control performance. The proposed controller was tested in simulators and on a real autonomous car and was able to perform lateral control with acceptable errors. Paper [84] used CNNs and fully connected networks to develop control strategies for the coupled longitudinal and lateral control. The authors used a high-fidelity vehicle model to generate a data set for training. The inputs to the network are the trajectory and vehicle states, and the outputs are the steering angle and the applied torque on the wheels. Evaluation tests showed that both control strategies were able to handle the combined longitudinal and lateral control tasks, but the CNN-based controller performed better than the one based on Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP). Rausch *et al.* [85] also used CNNs to develop a steering controller, the network comprised three convolution layers with one fully connected layer. Steering angle data and front-facing camera footage were generated through simulations and used to train the network to learn appropriate steering controls. In [86] an RNN was combined with CNN to predict steering controls from input images, the RNN includes temporal dependencies which enhanced the predictions and control performance by 35% compared to using only CNNs. These methods are known as supervised learning since the data used for training the network is labeled by an expert.

2.4.2 Reinforcement learning control

Reinforcement learning is an unsupervised approach where the network learns from trial and error, this is usually modeled as a Markov Decision Process (MDP) illustrated in Fig. 2.4. In a general way, an MDP is defined by a state space S , an action space A , a state transition probability P , and a reward function R . The goal is to learn a policy $\pi(s_t, a_t)$ that links rewards and actions such that at each iteration, the agent observes the set of states s_t and takes an action a_t from the action space A . Then the environment transitions according to the probability model P . The agent

then observes a new set of states s_{t+1} and receives a reward r_t for the performed action a_t . The policy π seeks to find the actions that maximize the rewards enabling the agent to learn by applying actions and receiving rewards or penalties.

Figure 2.4: Markov decision process.

One of the most widely used reinforcement learning algorithms is Q-learning [87], the latter is a value-based approach where the reward is quantified by a value function $V(s)$ and the objective of the algorithm is to map each action to a value for each state. Another kind of algorithm is based on policy gradient, it parameterizes the policy instead of the value function to obtain the optimal policy. This is achieved through a loss function, whose gradient is estimated with regard to network parameters. Thus, the network parameters are adjusted according to the policy gradient. There are actor-critic algorithms as well, these use a hybrid approach combining value-based and policy gradient algorithms. Hence, one network estimates the reward for each action and another actor network estimates the optimal policy.

Paper [88] combined deep learning and reinforcement learning to steer an autonomous vehicle, the authors used a multi-task learning CNN to learn track features and localize the vehicle from camera images. Policy gradient reinforcement learning was used to control the steering wheel of an autonomous vehicle simulated in TORCS. In [89], LIDAR data was used to develop and test reinforcement learning controllers based on policy gradient and Q-learning for obstacle avoidance maneuvers. Paper [90] used reinforcement learning to perform lane change maneuvers, the authors designed a Q-function approximator with closed loop greedy policy to improve the computation efficiency. Evaluation tests showed that smooth and efficient control policies were achieved for lane-change maneuvers. The same authors developed a quadratic

Q-network for autonomous driving in [91], the quadratic form achieved more optimal control actions that were tested in lane-change maneuvers as well.

Deep Q-learning and actor-critic algorithms were proposed in [92], to learn optimal policies for lateral control. The developed controllers were tested in TORCS while considering interactions with other vehicles. The actor-critic algorithm, being a continuous deterministic approach, performed better by producing continuous control actions, especially in curves where the Q-learning algorithm suffered from discontinuous control actions. Yu *et al.* [93] also designed deep Q-learning algorithms to steer the vehicle. The authors investigated the effect of several reward functions and experimented with different hyper-parameters like gradient update rules and double Q-learning.

2.4.3 Fuzzy logic control

Fuzzy logic systems seek to model human expertise by using linguistic variables, these variables conceptualize the fuzziness in human decision-making. Such systems do not require high computational costs unlike conventional control methods, and they do not need any mathematical model, which makes them suitable for systems with complex models. Human operational experience is then conceptualized into a fuzzy controller that consists of (**IF/THEN**) rules. These rules simulate the expert’s ”know-how” as an algorithm governed by fuzzy sets and membership functions. An example of a fuzzy rule for steering control would be; **if** ”position error” is negative **then** ”steering angle” is positive, where the position error is the input, and the steering angle is the output. The downside to this control approach is the expertise needed to set the fuzzy rules. Fuzzy logic systems consist of four parts as shown in Fig. 2.5:

Figure 2.5: Structure of fuzzy logic controller.

- The fuzzifier converts the crisp inputs into fuzzy sets (fuzzification).
- The rule base contains the fuzzy rules in the form of (**IF/THEN**) conditions.
- The inference module determines the matching percentage between fuzzy inputs and rules.
- The defuzzifier extracts output values from the fuzzy sets (defuzzification).

Authors of [94] used fuzzy logic control for obstacle avoidance maneuvers, the control task was divided into collision detection and then decision-making. Each task was performed by a fuzzy controller, the obstacle distance and angle were chosen as inputs for the obstacle detection module, and the outputs were steering maneuver and safe cruising speed. The inputs to the second module were set as the tracking error, and the distance to obstacles and the output was defined as the magnitude of the control signal. The results showed smooth performance but were limited to straight roads only. Paper [95] dealt with path tracking for vehicles with electromechanical wheel systems, they developed a fuzzy logic controller that handles steering and speed control. The kinematic bicycle model was used, and the controller was simplified with only three fuzzy sets. However, the starting point and initial orientation were found to have a significant impact on controller performance.

Autonomous driving under varying loads was studied in [96] by designing a fuzzy inference system. The proposed fuzzy controller receives the tracking error and load as inputs and computes the speeds for the left and right wheels, the latter was subject to saturation. The controller was implemented on a microprocessor and tested for several scenarios. Shui *et al.* [97], presented a novel data-driven predictive control, the authors based their control approach on type 2 T-S fuzzy neural networks to achieve trajectory tracking of car-like mobile robots. The main advantage of such an approach is that it is completely independent of mathematical models. Simulation results showed that this approach was able to deal with the influence of uncertain factors, and obtain higher tracking accuracy. Korkmaz *et al.* [98] designed an autonomous vehicle control system based on fuzzy logic and deployed it into a JavaScript racer game. The authors used a simple sliding histogram window approach to detect road lanes and used this information in fuzzy logic reference position and velocity generators. The

fuzzy logic generators were based on a 7×7 rule base with triangular membership functions. The control of speed and position was ensured by a PD controller given the reference values obtained from the fuzzy logic generators.

Paper [99] introduced a fuzzy control algorithm for vehicles moving close to boundaries, the authors used a four-motion cycle program according to five collision proximity levels obtained from sensor data. Five linguistic variables with 25 fuzzy rules were used to develop the fuzzy controller. Evaluation tests showed that the proposed controller performed well and was able to overcome sensor imperfections. Van *et al.* [100] proposed a fuzzy logic controller with a CNN for steering control. PilotNet [101] was modified and used for predicting steering angles which in turn were used with the velocity of the vehicle and the steering angular velocity as inputs to the fuzzy logic system. The latter recommends optimal steering and velocity controls that are based on fuzzy rules inspired by human experience. Similarly, Chen *et al.* [102] used CMAC neural network [103] with fuzzy logic to control an autonomous vehicle. The neural network ensures the self-learning ability of the controller which eliminates errors, while the fuzzy logic module improves the control quality by suppressing disturbances and increasing robustness. The latter was formed by 56 fuzzy rules and receives the position and speed errors as inputs. The combined CMAC-fuzzy controller was tested on straight and curved roads, where its performance was superior compared to PID control.

Several research papers used fuzzy logic to improve classical controllers as well, especially PID control in [104–106], MPC control [26, 107, 108] and SMC [45, 109, 110]. Both model-based and model-free control methods have advantages and drawbacks. In many situations they can complement each other for a better altogether solution, an overall comparative summary is provided in table 2.1.

Table 2.1: Comparative summary of model-based and mode-free controllers.

Controller	Model type	Strengths	Weaknesses	Related work
MPC	Kinematic Dynamic Linear Nonlinear	Optimal results Predictive feature Handles constraints Handles MIMO systems	Online Optimization Requires accurate model High computation burden	[19, 21, 22, 111, 112] [23, 25–30, 32] [104–106]
SMC	Kinematic Dynamic Linear Nonlinear	Strong robustness Low computation burden Can handle MIMO systems Suitable for nonlinear systems Suitable for switching systems	Chattering phenomenon Cannot handle constraints Discrete control actions	[38–41, 43–47] [45, 109, 110]
LQR	Kinematic Dynamic Linear	Optimal results Off-line optimization Handles MIMO systems	Poor robustness Requires accurate model Linearisation assumptions States must be measurable	[56–62]
H_∞	Kinematic Dynamic Linear Nonlinear	Strong robustness Can handle MIMO systems Guaranteed system stability Suitable for nonlinear systems	Cannot impose constraints Disturbances must be bounded Impractical for large dimensions Complex design and implementation	[49–55]
LPV	Geometric Kinematic Dynamic Linear	Feedback control Captures Non-linearities Low computation burden Suitable for switching systems	Limited stability Requires instantiation Requires accurate model Difficult design and implementation	[21, 25, 113, 114] [52, 62]
Back-stepping	Kinematic Dynamic Linear Nonlinear	Recursive feature Disturbance rejection Extendable system dimension Handles unmodeled parameters	Difficult to implement States must be measurable Sensitive to parameter variation	[66–69]
Stanley Pure-pursuit	Geometric	Simple design Low computation burden	Limited to low speeds Excludes vehicle dynamics Unsuitable for reverse motion Cannot handle varying velocity Affected by the preview distance	[70–75, 79]
PID	–	Simple design Feedback control Easy implementation Widely used in the industry Requires only the error signal	Difficult gain tuning Limited performance Undershoot and overshoot Limited to single input systems Unsuitable for complex systems	[63–65, 115] [26, 107, 108]
Deep learning	–	Model-free Data-driven Versatile application Handles MIMO systems Suitable for feed-forward control	Black-box system Long off-line training Requires training data Several hyper-parameters Stability is not guaranteed	[82–86]
Reinforcement learning	–	Continuous learning No data required for training Can handle stochastic dynamics	No stability insurance Discret control actions Requires control policy Very long computations	[88–93]
Fuzzy logic	–	Model-free High precision Fast operation Intuitive design Linguistic feature Human like reasoning	Human expertise required Several tuning parameters Stability is not guaranteed Prone to dimensionality curse Cannot handle MIMO systems	[94–96] [98–100, 102]

2.5 Planning for Autonomous Driving

Motion planning is a fundamental task for autonomous vehicles since it allows the vehicle to navigate within dynamic environments where new trajectories are constantly required. Generally speaking, motion planning is divided into global planning and local planning. The former finds a high-level and global plan for the long term, while local planning seeks to generate rapid paths that take into account the handling limits of the vehicle and seeks to avoid possible obstacles present on the global path. Planning can also be categorized by its application type which can be online or offline. Furthermore, motion planning can be time-dependent which refers to trajectory planning. In this kind of planning, the evolution of the position and velocity is time-dependent and often represented by temporal-based functions. Contrary to trajectory planning, path planning has no time dependence, and the problem is reduced to simply finding a feasible path, and only the heading and lateral position of the vehicle are considered. The following subsections present the main planning algorithms used for autonomous driving.

2.5.1 Graph-based planning

The idea of these algorithms is to discretize the possible configuration space of the vehicle into a form of a graph. The main objective is to find the shortest feasible path from a starting point to a destination point using heuristic information. These algorithms are fitter for offline path planning and suitable for applications in mobile robotics. They are less common in autonomous driving because they usually do not take into account the vehicle dynamics and handling limits, and they are unsuitable for real-time applications. The best-known algorithms are the Dijkstra and the more enhanced A* family which are suitable for static environments. For dynamics environments, D* algorithms provide a better alternative [116].

2.5.2 Sampling-based planning

Sampling-based or incremental planning is a better solution than graph-based techniques for bigger configuration spaces, where a more extensive search is required. The approach is based on randomly sampling the configuration space and then connecting

the random samples with a cost-optimal path, which is continuously improved over iterations. Among the most widely used algorithms in autonomous driving, we find the Probabilistic Road Maps (PRM) and the Rapidly-exploring Random Tree (RRT) algorithms. RRT and PRM were succeeded by the RRT* and PRM* algorithms, which are more suitable for dynamic environments. Most of these planning approaches were used in the previously mentioned DARPA challenge [116]. For instance, Kuwata *et al.* [117] used RRT for path planning while also considering the controller and the vehicle dynamics. Generally, RRT methods give good planning results, but the solution is often sub-optimal. An analysis of the behavior of PRM and RRT can be found in [118]. RRT* was used for optimal motion planning by Jeon *et al.* [119] and Arab *et al.* [120]. Other algorithms include the Fast Machine Tree (FMT)* which was proposed by Janson *et al.* [121] as a more optimal and faster alternative to PRM* and RRT*.

2.5.3 Optimization-based planning

This approach relies on the optimization of a cost function which is usually subject to certain constraints. Vehicle handling limits and certain performance criteria related to lateral and longitudinal accelerations can be imposed as constraints. Likewise, road boundaries and obstacles can also be handled as constraints, especially in autonomous racing applications. Unlike graph-based and sampling-based algorithms which can only be applied for low accelerations and velocities, optimization-based algorithms are capable of planning optimal trajectories that ensure constraints under high accelerations and velocities with desirable properties. However, these methods may suffer from expensive computations, and their parameterization and implementation may become complicated. MPC is one of the most widely used planners for autonomous driving and more specifically for autonomous racing due to its predictive nature and optimal performance. Liu *et al.* [122] introduced a path planner based on NMPC for highway driving scenarios. Similarly, Ahmadi Mousavi *et al.* [123] also proposed a path planner for urban driving scenarios, where the strategy was based on LTV-MPC with a kinematic vehicle model. Paper [33] proposed a one-level planning and control strategy for racing applications, the authors used NMPC with an extended kinematic vehicle model. The same authors improved their work in [34]

by redesigning the same planner, but with a nonlinear dynamic model of the vehicle which outperformed the previous one. Kloeser *et al.* [35] proposed a similar approach with an NMPC planner for race line generation but with a singularity-free model. In [32], a linear MPC was introduced for path planning in racing applications. The strategy uses a linearized dynamic model of the vehicle and incorporates static obstacle avoidance in the algorithm. Alcalá *et al.* [25] also proposed an offline LPV-MPC planner for autonomous racing applications. A technical survey on the path and trajectory planning algorithms for autonomous driving can be found in [116].

2.6 Conclusions

This chapter provided a background and literature review on the most widely used path-tracking algorithms and the state-of-the-art control strategies applied in autonomous driving. The limits and strengths of each planning and control approach were also highlighted and compared. From a control point of view, although the trend seems to shift more and more towards data-based methods and black-box-like techniques, classical control still dominates since it can guarantee several system physical properties, such as stability. Moreover the majority of published works tend to focus on control performance optimization and disregard constraints and safety conditions. Nevertheless, stability insurance and lack of interpretability are still major barriers to the deployment of data-based approaches despite their good performance. Optimization-based planning algorithms were found to be the best-fit techniques for autonomous driving although they are prone to high computation loads.

Model predictive control has become one of the best control methods for the path tracking task due to its predictive feature and ability to guarantee state and input constraints. However, stability analysis for this type of control is still a challenge. H_∞ , SMC, and back-stepping control make a great choice for dealing with nonlinearities, parameter uncertainties, and disturbances at the expense of complicated theoretical derivations and design approaches. LQR, PID, and geometry-based controllers are suitable for low-speed applications, and simplified models with negligible disturbances and uncertainties. Except for MPC, most model-based controllers cannot impose constraints on system inputs, outputs, and states. This is an important quality for

guaranteeing safety and comfort in automated guidance, especially for preserving stability conditions and enforcing actuator limits.

On the other hand, model-free controllers are a key solution when modeling becomes a daunting task. These methods become a very interesting approach when sufficient data are available, they can ensure multitasking without being affected by the nonlinear characteristics of the system. AI-based methods can also be used to enhance and improve model-based controllers by learning complex models and control algorithms, the main downside of these methods is the black-box nature that cannot ensure stability and other physical properties.

Chapter 3

Vehicle Modeling

Summary

This chapter presents an overview of the most commonly used methods to model the vehicle for control design purposes. The three most used models, geometric, kinematic, and dynamic bicycle representations are explained in detail. In addition, tire modeling is also discussed, and more comprehensive and complete combined kinematic and dynamic bicycle models are also provided.

3.1 Introduction

Accurate modeling of the vehicle is fundamental for assessing its behavior and designing, testing, and validating control and estimation strategies, especially for model-based design. Three main distinctions can be made regarding the modeling approach. First, geometric modeling is the simplest approach that is mainly based on vehicle geometry (position/dimensions), it requires very few parameters. This approach has limited accuracy since the vehicle's motion is not considered. Second, kinematic modeling which focuses mainly on the vehicle's motion but disregards its dynamics. Then, there is dynamic modeling that studies the interacting forces between the vehicle and its environment. Modeling techniques differ in complexity ranging from multi-body to single-track vehicle models. Multi-body models treat the vehicle as a multi-articulate system consisting of multiple bodies [124]. Double-track dynamic models consider all vehicle wheels with movements in the three-dimensional space [125]. Such models are unsuitable for control design and are mainly used for validation and simulation purposes. Single-track models are simplified with certain assumptions to be suitable for control design, and they usually have reduced computation complexity [126]. This

chapter is divided into 8 sections, where sections 2, 3, and 4 discuss the geometric, kinematic, and dynamic modeling of the vehicle, respectively. Section 5 presents the most used tire models, while section 6 provides a combined kinematic and dynamic modeling approach. The full dynamic model of the vehicle is presented in section 7, and LPV modeling is discussed in section 8.

3.2 Geometric Model

The geometric model is one of the simplest ways to model a wheeled vehicle, where only three parameters are required, and these are the wheelbase E , the steering angle of the front wheel δ , and the curvature radius of the trajectory r . Such a model does not account for vehicle kinematics nor its dynamics which makes it less accurate in general but at the same time very simple for control design and implementation without any computation burden. The simplicity of the geometric model relies on the Ackerman assumption of steering geometry, which states that during turns both tires follow an arc with a common center. This assumption means that the tires perform pure rolling without any lateral acceleration during a turn. Although the geometric model has been extensively used in the literature, it remains functional only at low speeds. As the speed increases, the vehicle becomes subject to several forces, and its wheels start to slip and skid invalidating the Ackerman assumption.

The geometric bicycle model is used in several well-known control approaches, namely the pure pursuit and the Stanley controllers. The pure pursuit strategy projects the position of the vehicle on the trajectory and then uses this projection to define a point as a target. The latter will be used to determine the steering angle of the vehicle so as to reach the defined point on the trajectory, which can be expressed as follows:

$$\delta(t) = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{E}{r} \right). \quad (3.1)$$

The Stanley approach [127] further includes the heading error $\psi_e(t)$, the tracking error $e(t)$, again parameter K and the vehicle speed $v_x(t)$ into the model which makes it more accurate for control purposes, the steering angle is then expressed as:

$$\delta(t) = \psi_e(t) + \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{K e(t)}{v_x(t)} \right). \quad (3.2)$$

Figure 3.1: Geometric bicycle model.

More sophisticated geometric approaches are reported in the literature like Linderoth's method [128] and the vector pursuit controller [129], but their performance remains limited by the speed of the vehicle.

3.3 Kinematic Model

The kinematic model takes into consideration the kinematics of the vehicle, hence the name kinematic. The model describes the motion of the vehicle in terms of position, velocity, and acceleration, and it disregards the forces acting on the vehicle. Despite the fact that the kinematic model is more sophisticated compared to simple geometric models, it remains restricted and describes the vehicle motion under certain assumptions. The model works well when there are no slip angles, that is, the velocity vector and the orientation of the wheels are identical. Such an assumption holds true for low speeds only, typically below 5 m/s [20].

The simplified bicycle kinematic model is well developed and very common in the literature [130], yet it is mainly limited to low-speed applications and cannot be relied on for highly dynamic maneuvers. Rajmani [20] provided a full description of the model in its simplest form, it has been used in the design of numerous controllers.

Figure 3.2: Kinematic bicycle model.

The simplicity of the bicycle model is in reducing the two front and rear wheels to a single front wheel and a single rear wheel which resembles a bicycle. As described in [20], the bicycle kinematic model can be summarized by the following equations expressed in the inertial frame:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \dot{x} &= v \cos(\psi + \beta), \\
 \dot{y} &= v \sin(\psi + \beta), \\
 \dot{\psi} &= \frac{v}{l_r} \sin(\beta), \\
 \dot{v} &= \alpha, \\
 \beta &= \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{l_r}{l_f + l_r} \tan(\delta) \right).
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.3}$$

As can be seen in Fig. 3.2, x and y represent the coordinates of the vehicle's Center of Gravity (CG) in the inertial frame (XY). The heading is described by ψ , and v represents the velocity of the vehicle. The front and rear wheel axles are distant from the CG by l_f and l_r , respectively. β denotes the side-slip angle (angle between the velocity vector and vehicle longitudinal axis), and α is the vehicle longitudinal acceleration. The input to the model is the steering angles δ for the front and rear wheels.

Assumption 1 *In most cases, it is assumed that only the front wheel of the vehicle*

is steerable ($\delta_r = 0$) and ($\delta_f = \delta$).

The kinematic model requires the identification of two parameters only, which are the distances from the wheel axles to the CG (l_f and l_r). Hence, applying the same controller to other vehicles with different wheelbases is straightforward. The kinematic model can be further enhanced by including the position and orientation errors (x_e, y_e, ψ_e), these are defined as the difference between the actual position and orientation of the vehicle (x, y, ψ) and the desired ones (x_d, y_d, ψ_d). Since these errors are expressed in the inertial frame, a rotation around the orthogonal axis of the road is required to convert them into the vehicle frame resulting in the following expression:

$$\begin{bmatrix} x_e \\ y_e \\ \psi_e \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\psi) & \sin(\psi) & 0 \\ -\sin(\psi) & \cos(\psi) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x_d - x \\ y_d - y \\ \psi_d - \psi \end{bmatrix}. \quad (3.4)$$

By accounting for the non-holonomic constraint ($\dot{x} \sin(\theta) = \dot{y} \cos(\theta)$), deriving equation (3.4) and applying trigonometric identification, the kinematic model of (3.3) can be reformulated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{x}_e &= \psi y_e + v_d \cos(\psi_e) - v, \\ \dot{y}_e &= -\psi x_e + v_d \sin(\psi_e), \\ \dot{\psi}_e &= \dot{\psi}_d - \dot{\psi}, \end{aligned} \quad (3.5)$$

where the error terms and the desired position and orientation are expressed in the vehicle body frame. Since the desired values are used to build this model, it can be referred to as a reference-based kinematic model.

3.3.1 Curvature-based kinematic model

The kinematic model can be represented in the curvilinear coordinate system for improved control design. Thus, the model can be expressed as the lateral position and heading errors with respect to the center of the track, as illustrated in Fig. 3.3. The model obeys the following constraint [131]:

$$(r - y_e)\dot{\psi}_d = v_x \cos(\psi_e) - v_y \sin(\psi_e). \quad (3.6)$$

where v_x and v_y represent the respective linear longitudinal and lateral velocities, $\dot{\psi}_d$ is the desired rotation speed and r is the radius of the curve. By setting the road curvature κ as the inverse of radius r , the desired rotation speed can be expressed as (3.7), which then allows defining the orientation error by equation (3.8).

Figure 3.3: Curvature-based kinematic model.

$$\dot{\psi}_d = \frac{v_x \cos(\psi_e) - v_y \sin(\psi_e)}{1 - y_e \kappa} \kappa. \quad (3.7)$$

$$\dot{\psi}_e = \dot{\psi} - \frac{v_x \cos(\psi_e) - v_y \sin(\psi_e)}{1 - y_e \kappa} \kappa. \quad (3.8)$$

Based on equation (3.7), the derivative of the travelled distance \dot{s} is expressed by:

$$\dot{s} = r \dot{\psi}_d = \frac{v_x \cos(\psi_e) - v_y \sin(\psi_e)}{1 - y_e \kappa}. \quad (3.9)$$

Hence, assuming that the curvature $k(s)$ is known, the curvature-based kinematic representation can be defined as the following:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{y}_e &= v_x \sin(\psi_e) + v_y \cos(\psi_e), \\ \dot{\psi}_e &= \dot{\psi} - \frac{v_x \cos(\psi_e) - v_y \sin(\psi_e)}{1 - y_e \kappa} \kappa, \\ \dot{s}_e &= \frac{v_x \cos(\psi_e) - v_y \sin(\psi_e)}{1 - y_e \kappa}. \end{aligned} \quad (3.10)$$

3.4 Dynamic Model

A more accurate representation of the vehicle requires modeling its dynamics, which considers behaviors like side-slipping, over-steering, and friction. The dynamic model is more accurate than the kinematic model in the sense that it includes the applied forces on the vehicle and especially the tire forces. Newton's second law of motion and Euler Lagrange methods are applied to the vehicle system to obtain the dynamic model. The complete dynamic model is very complex and nonlinear accounting for translation and rotation motions in the 3D space and considering a full vehicle with four wheels [132]. Such models are used mainly for validation purposes and are too complicated for controller design, simplified two-wheel dynamic models are often used instead.

Assumption 2 *To simplify control design, the vertical dynamics related to the suspension system are neglected and assumed to have no effect on the longitudinal and lateral dynamics.*

The dynamic bicycle model accounts for 2D planar motion, translation in the X and Y axis (longitudinal/lateral), and rotation around the Z axis (yaw) of the reference frame. This yields a 3DoF vehicle model [126], and in some cases, the longitudinal dynamics are disregarded such as in path tracking where the task is reduced to controlling lateral dynamics and yaw motion resulting in a 2DoF model. Considering the simple bicycle model in Fig. 3.4 and applying Newton's laws results in the following model equations:

$$\begin{aligned}\sum F_x &= m\alpha_x, \\ \sum F_y &= m\alpha_y, \\ \sum M_z &= I_z\ddot{\psi},\end{aligned}\tag{3.11}$$

where I_z represents the moment of inertia, M_z the rotation moment around the Z axis and F_x and F_y are the longitudinal and lateral forces, respectively. These include the tire forces applied on the front and rear wheels. The terms α_x and α_y are the longitudinal and lateral inertial accelerations and are expressed in terms of longitudinal/lateral accelerations (\ddot{x}, \ddot{y}) , the yaw rate $\dot{\psi}$, the longitudinal/lateral velocities (\dot{x}, \dot{y}) as:

$$\begin{aligned}\alpha_x &= \ddot{x} - \dot{\psi}\dot{y}, \\ \alpha_y &= \ddot{y} + \dot{\psi}\dot{x},\end{aligned}\tag{3.12}$$

using equations (3.11) and considering the non-holonomic constraints, the full model can be derived as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}\ddot{x} &= \dot{y}\dot{\psi} - \frac{2}{m}(F_{yf}\sin\delta + F_{df}), \\ \ddot{y} &= -\dot{x}\dot{\psi} + \frac{2}{m}(F_{yf}\cos\delta + F_{yr}), \\ \ddot{\psi} &= \frac{2}{I_z}(l_f F_{yf} + l_r F_{yr}),\end{aligned}\tag{3.13}$$

F_{df} sums the friction and the drag forces and is formulated as follows:

$$F_{df} = \frac{C_d \rho A v_x^2}{2} + \mu mg.\tag{3.14}$$

where C_d represents the aerodynamic drag coefficient, ρ is the air density, A stands for the vehicle frontal area, and μ , m and g are the static friction coefficient, the mass of the vehicle and the gravity respectively.

Figure 3.4: Dynamic bicycle model.

The longitudinal and lateral tire forces are often linearized to be used in the simple bicycle model. The linearization of tire forces is possible under the assumption of small slip angles, and it is done by considering that slip angles and tire forces are proportional.

Assumption 3 *The slip angle is small for normal driving conditions, this limits the range of operation of the lateral forces to their linear region, which allows the use of a linear tire model.*

Typically, the linear region for longitudinal slip angles is under $\frac{1}{2}g$ accelerations, and for lateral slip angles under 5° [79]. In such cases, the lateral tire forces can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} F_{yf} &= C_{yf}\alpha_f, \\ F_{yr} &= C_{yr}\alpha_r, \end{aligned} \tag{3.15}$$

with C_{yf} and C_{yr} being the lateral cornering stiffness coefficients for front and rear tires, respectively. The terms α_f and α_r are the respective side-slip angles. The lateral and longitudinal forces (F_x, F_y) are obtained from the tire model as will be discussed in the next section.

3.4.1 Inertial coordinates

The kinematic and dynamic models presented in Sections 3.3 and 3.4 are defined in the vehicle's body frame. Hence, a frame conversion is needed to obtain the coordinates in the inertial frame (global frame), which is important for control applications. Such frame conversion is ensured by the following transformation:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{Y} &= \dot{x} \sin \psi + \dot{y} \cos \psi, \\ \dot{X} &= \dot{x} \cos \psi - \dot{y} \sin \psi. \end{aligned} \tag{3.16}$$

3.5 Tire Modeling

The tires of the vehicle interact with the surface of the road and undergo deformations with different maneuvers, resulting in tire forces in the longitudinal and lateral directions. These forces are nonlinear functions that depend on several parameters like the friction of the road, the surface and material of the tire, the slip angle, etc. The lateral slip angle, known as side-slip, depends on the wheel's lateral velocities v_y^w (see Fig. 3.5). Similarly, the longitudinal slip depends on the wheel's longitudinal velocity v_x^w , these velocities are defined in the wheel reference frame (X_w, Y_w) . The longitudinal

slip is caused by the wheel's longitudinal deformation which leads to rolling resistance, the latter is defined as the difference between the actual wheel's longitudinal velocity and the relative free rolling velocity v_{x-free}^w . Thus, the longitudinal slip ratio of a tire can be expressed as the following:

$$\lambda = \begin{cases} 1 - \frac{v_{x-free}^w}{v_x^w}, & v_x^w - v_{x-free}^w \geq 0 \text{ (acceleration)} \\ \frac{v_{x-free}^w}{v_x^w} - 1, & v_x^w - v_{x-free}^w < 0 \text{ (braking)} \end{cases} \quad (3.17)$$

On the other hand, the side-slip angle is caused by the lateral deformation of the tire induced by the lateral reaction force. The latter is very important for lateral control applications as it defines the angle between the velocity vector $v^w = [v_x^w \ v_y^w]^T$ and the wheel's longitudinal axle, which is given by the following equation:

$$\alpha = -\tan^{-1} \left(\frac{v_y^w}{v_x^w} \right). \quad (3.18)$$

Figure 3.5: Tire slip angle in the wheel's reference frame.

For single track models as illustrated in Fig. 3.4, the side-slip angles for front and rear wheels are defined in terms of the vehicle's lateral and longitudinal velocities (\dot{x}, \dot{y}) , heading rate $\dot{\psi}$, and the steering angle δ :

$$\begin{aligned}\alpha_f &= \delta - \tan^{-1}\left(\frac{\dot{y}+l_f\dot{\psi}}{\dot{x}}\right), \\ \alpha_r &= -\tan^{-1}\left(\frac{\dot{y}-l_r\dot{\psi}}{\dot{x}}\right).\end{aligned}\tag{3.19}$$

typically, for small slip angles, $\tan^{-1}(\theta)$ is approximated by (θ) to linearize the model resulting in the following linear formula:

$$\begin{aligned}\alpha_f &= \delta - \frac{\dot{y}+l_f\dot{\psi}}{\dot{x}}, \\ \alpha_r &= -\frac{\dot{y}-l_r\dot{\psi}}{\dot{x}}.\end{aligned}\tag{3.20}$$

3.5.1 Pacejka model

The Pacejka model known as the magic formula works well with nonlinear models, and it has been extensively used in the literature. The formula fits empirical data to model the tire dynamics which is generally expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned}Y(\lambda) &= D \sin(C \tan^{-1}(B\Theta(\lambda))) + S_v, \\ \Theta(\lambda) &= (1 - E)(\lambda + S_h) + \frac{E}{B} \tan^{-1}(B(\lambda + S_h)),\end{aligned}\tag{3.21}$$

where Y can be the longitudinal or the lateral tire force, λ is the slip ratio in the case of Y representing the longitudinal force and the slip angle when Y represents the lateral force. The terms B, C, D, E, S_h , and S_v are parameters fit from experimental data that define certain characteristics like the stiffness factor, the shape factor, the peak value, etc. Fig. 3.6 depicts the behavior of the lateral and longitudinal forces in function of slip angles.

Figure 3.6: Pacejka tire model.

As can be seen, two regions are distinguished, particularly region 2 between λ_{min} and λ_{max} delimits stable static friction where the tire is able to grip into the road. Regions 1 and 3 are unstable because the magnitude of the slip ratio changes the magnitude of tire forces. According to Coulomb's law, when the maximum or minimum values are exceeded, the tire shifts into an unstable sliding friction state.

3.5.2 Simplified Magic Formula

The complete Pacejka formula remains one of the best models to describe the behavior of the tire. Generally speaking, the linearized model, described in (3.15), is often used and works well for cases with small slip angles. However, the simplified magic formula presents a better solution providing a nonlinear yet simplified approach to accurately obtain the lateral forces. This simplified model can be summarized as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} F_{y_f} &= F_{z_f} d \sin(c \tan^{-1}(b\alpha_f)), \\ F_{y_r} &= F_{z_r} d \sin(c \tan^{-1}(b\alpha_r)), \end{aligned} \quad (3.22)$$

F_{z_f} and F_{z_r} represent the load force on the respective front and rear wheels, b and c are the stiffness factor and the shape factor respectively, and d is obtained as the peak value of the lateral force versus slip angle curve. The load force is the resultant of static load F_{z_0} and load transfer ΔF_z , the load transfer is positive during acceleration and negative when braking. Hence the load force on both tires can be described as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} F_{z_f} &= F_{z_f0} + \Delta F_{z_f}, \\ F_{z_r} &= F_{z_r0} + \Delta F_{z_r}. \end{aligned} \quad (3.23)$$

The vertical dynamics can also be expressed in function of longitudinal acceleration (α_x) and vehicle geometry, namely the height of the CG (h) and the distances between the CG and front/rear axles respectively (l_f, l_r):

$$\begin{aligned} F_{z_f} &= \frac{m(l_f g + h\alpha_x)}{l_f + l_r}, \\ F_{z_r} &= \frac{m(l_r g + h\alpha_x)}{l_f + l_r}, \end{aligned} \quad (3.24)$$

where m and g are the total mass of the vehicle and the acceleration of gravity.

3.5.3 Fiala tire model

Although the Pacejka formula is the most widely used tire model, there are other representations such as the Fiala model, which is based on the laws of physics. The model considers that the road-tire contact patch (the surface between the tire and the road) is covered with brushes. These brushes bend when touching the road, and they are the reason for the alternative name brush model. According to [133], the Fiala model can be summarized in the following equations:

$$\begin{cases} \lambda_x &= \left| \frac{\omega R_w - v}{\omega R_w} \right|, \\ \lambda^* &= \frac{\mu F_z}{2C_x}. \end{cases} \quad (3.25)$$

Case 1 $|\lambda_x| < \lambda^*$:

$$F_x = \lambda_x C_x. \quad (3.26)$$

Case 2 $|\lambda_x| \geq \lambda^*$:

$$F_x = \text{sign}(\lambda_x) \left[\mu F_z - \frac{(\mu F_z)^2}{4|\lambda_x| C_x} \right], \quad (3.27)$$

with μ being the coefficient of friction, C_x being the longitudinal stiffness coefficient, and F_z representing the normal load. F_x is the longitudinal tire force, λ_x denotes the longitudinal slip, while v , ω , and R_w represent the car's velocity, the wheel's angular velocity, and its radius respectively. Similarly, the lateral force can be expressed as:

$$\begin{cases} \lambda_y &= \tan \alpha, \\ \lambda^* &= \frac{3\mu F_z}{C_y}. \end{cases} \quad (3.28)$$

Case 1 $|\lambda_y| < \lambda^*$:

$$\begin{cases} h &= 1 - \frac{C_y |\lambda_y|}{3\mu F_z}, \\ F_y &= \mu F_z (1 - h^3) \text{sign}(\alpha). \end{cases} \quad (3.29)$$

Case 2 $|\lambda_y| \geq \lambda^*$:

$$F_y = \mu F_z \text{sign}(\alpha), \quad (3.30)$$

where α is the side-slip angle, F_y denotes the lateral tire force, C_y is the lateral cornering stiffness coefficient. The lateral force in Fiala's model becomes a cubic function when the vehicle is not in full sliding, which is delimited by the quantity λ^* .

The model is then much simpler than the Pacejka formula, which makes it suitable for computationally efficient identification algorithms.

3.5.4 Dugoff tire model

Inspired by the analysis of Fiala, Dugoff developed an analytical model, where he assumes a constant coefficient of friction and a constant vertical load distribution.

Dugoff's model is expressed as the following [134]:

$$\begin{cases} F_x = C_x \frac{\lambda_x}{1-\lambda_x} \tau, \\ F_y = C_y \frac{\tan(\alpha)}{1-\lambda_x} \tau. \end{cases} \quad (3.31)$$

The term τ is used to account for the combined slip such that:

$$\tau = \begin{cases} (2 - \sigma) & \text{if } \sigma < 1 \\ 1 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3.32)$$

where:

$$\sigma = \frac{(1 - \lambda_x) \mu F_z}{2 \sqrt{C_x^2 \lambda_x^2 + C_y^2 \tan^2(\alpha)}}. \quad (3.33)$$

Fig. 3.7 provides a comparison of the longitudinal tire force between the three models, namely; the Magic formula, Fiala's model (also known as brush model), and Dugoff's model [134]. It can be seen that the brush model and Dugoff's model are almost identical, but they remain less accurate when compared to the magic formula, which is widely used by car manufacturers to simulate and validate tire dynamic performances.

Figure 3.7: Comparison of tire models.

3.6 Combined Kinematic and Dynamic Model

The combination of both kinematic and dynamic models yields a complete combined model that is suitable for more accurate control design, especially for applications that require the vehicle to operate at its dynamic limits. Such models can be used for planning and estimation as well. In this regard, by using the dynamic model introduced in Section (3.4) with the simplified magic formula (3.22) and the curvature-based kinematic model presented in Section (3.3.1), the combined model can be defined as [131]:

$$\dot{x} = \begin{cases} \dot{v}_x = \alpha - \frac{\sin \delta d F_{zf}}{m} \sin \left(c \tan^{-1} \left(b \delta - b \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{v_y - l_f \dot{\psi}}{v_x} \right) \right) \right) - \mu g + \dot{\psi} v_y, \\ \dot{v}_y = \frac{F_{zf} d \cos(\delta) \sin \left(c \tan^{-1} \left(b \delta - b \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{v_y - l_f \dot{\psi}}{v_x} \right) \right) \right) + F_{zr} d \sin \left(c \tan^{-1} \left(-b \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{v_y + l_r \dot{\psi}}{v_x} \right) \right) \right)}{m} - \dot{\psi} v_x, \\ \ddot{\psi} = \frac{l_f F_{zf} d \cos(\delta) \sin \left(c \tan^{-1} \left(b \delta - b \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{v_y - l_f \dot{\psi}}{v_x} \right) \right) \right) - l_f F_{zr} d \sin \left(c \tan^{-1} \left(-b \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{v_y + l_r \dot{\psi}}{v_x} \right) \right) \right)}{I}, \\ \dot{y}_e = v_x \sin \psi_e + v_y \cos \psi_e, \\ \dot{\psi}_e = \dot{\psi} - \frac{v_x \cos \psi_e - v_y \sin \psi_e}{1 - y_e \kappa} \kappa, \\ \dot{s} = \frac{v_x \cos \psi_e - v_y \sin \psi_e}{1 - y_e \kappa}. \end{cases} \quad (3.34)$$

3.7 Full Dynamic Model

Although the single-track bicycle dynamic model is fit for control design, it lacks precision due to the simplifications and assumptions imposed on building the model. As discussed earlier, full vehicle dynamic models are a more realistic representation of vehicle dynamics. Such models take into account all four wheels of the vehicle and do not neglect the vertical dynamics as presented in [125, 132]. Fig. 3.8 shows a 3DoF dual-track full vehicle model that is defined by equations (3.35-3.41).

$$\dot{Y} = \dot{x} \sin \psi + \dot{y} \cos \psi \quad (3.35)$$

$$\dot{X} = \dot{x} \sin \psi - \dot{y} \cos \psi \quad (3.36)$$

$$m\ddot{x} = F_{x,FL} + F_{x,FR} + F_{x,RL} + F_{x,RR} - F_{aero}. \quad (3.37)$$

$$m\ddot{y} = F_{y,FL} + F_{y,FR} + F_{y,RL} + F_{y,RR}. \quad (3.38)$$

$$I_x \ddot{\theta} = l_\omega (F_{z,FL} + F_{z,RL} - F_{z,FR} - F_{z,RR}) + Z (F_{y,FL} + F_{y,FR} + F_{y,RL} + F_{y,RR}). \quad (3.39)$$

$$I_z \ddot{\psi} = L_f (F_{y,FL} + F_{y,FR}) - L_r (F_{y,RL} + F_{y,RR}) - l_\omega (F_{x,FR} + F_{x,RR} - F_{x,FL} - F_{x,RL}). \quad (3.40)$$

$$I_y \ddot{\phi} = L_r (F_{z,RL} + F_{z,RR}) - L_f (F_{z,FL} + F_{z,FR}) - Z (F_{x,FL} + F_{x,FR} + F_{x,RL} + F_{x,RR}). \quad (3.41)$$

Figure 3.8: Full dynamic model.

where F_x and F_y are the longitudinal and lateral tire forces, respectively. F_z is given in equation (3.42), and it represents the displacement of the suspension that models the vertical dynamics and load transfer between the four tires. The indices (F,R) and (R,L) refer to front/rear and right/left wheels, respectively. I_z , I_y , and I_x represent the respective yaw, pitch, and roll inertias of the vehicle. The vertical dynamics are expressed as:

$$F_z = -k_s \zeta(\theta, \phi) - d_s(\dot{\zeta})(\theta, \phi). \quad (3.42)$$

with $\zeta(\theta, \phi)$ being the displacement of the suspension for the given roll (ϕ) and pitch (θ) angles, while k_s and d_s define the suspension stiffness and damping.

The longitudinal and lateral tire forces are functions of the slip-ratio, and side-slip angle as discussed in Section 3.4, which is usually modeled by the Pacejka combined slip formula [24], taking into account the coupled interaction between longitudinal and lateral slipping. Note that this model only represents the chassis dynamics, More elaborate models may incorporate engine and brake dynamics as well.

3.8 LPV Modeling

Linear parameter-varying models, first introduced by Shamma *et al.* [135], are a class of linear systems that represent a dynamical system whose state-space representation linearly depends on external time-varying parameters. When the time-varying parameters are exogenous, meaning that they are completely external to the system, then we are dealing with pure LPV systems. When at least one of the time-varying parameters is endogenous, meaning that it is not external to the system and can be a state, input, or output of the system, then we are dealing with Quasi-LPV systems. Generally speaking, almost all systems that need to be controlled are nonlinear. Moreover, the standard linear time-invariant (LTI) models that are widely used for control design, are valid at a single given operating point only. LPV modeling allows extending such models to work in several operating points, in other words, the LPV approach converts a nonlinear system into a linear one that depends on a vector of time-varying parameters known as the scheduling vector. The Quasi-LPV systems are suitable for controlling nonlinear systems since the nonlinearities are embedded in the scheduling vector. In its basic form, an LPV system can be defined as follows:

$$\begin{cases} \dot{x}(t) &= A(\zeta(t))x(t) + B(\zeta(t))u(t), \\ y(t) &= C(\zeta(t))x(t) + D(\zeta(t))u(t). \end{cases} \quad (3.43)$$

where x , u , and y are the state, input, and output vectors. $A(\zeta(t))$, $B(\zeta(t))$, $C(\zeta(t))$, and $D(\zeta(t))$ are the time-varying system matrices with $\zeta(t)$ being the scheduling vector.

Remark 1 *In general, not all the system matrices have to be time-varying and depend*

on the scheduling vector, it is possible to have constant matrices and varying matrices in the same model.

Assumption 4 *The magnitude and the rate of change of the time-varying parameters in the scheduling vector ζ are bounded, and their variation is smooth within the bounds and along linear trajectories.*

The formulation of an LPV representation can be done in several ways, the affine and the polytopic representations are the most widely used approaches. A system is said to be affine LPV if it can be defined as follows:

$$\begin{cases} \dot{x}(t) &= \sum_{i=1}^N \zeta_i(t)(A_i x(t) + B_i u(t)), \\ y(t) &= \sum_{i=1}^N \zeta_i(t)(C_i x(t) + D_i u(t)). \end{cases} \quad (3.44)$$

Likewise, a system is said to be a polytopic LPV representation, if it can be modeled by the matrices $A(\zeta(t))$, $B(\zeta(t))$, $C(\zeta(t))$, and $D(\zeta(t))$ under the following representation:

$$\begin{cases} \dot{x}(t) &= \sum_{i=1}^N \mu_i(\zeta)(A_i x(t) + B_i u(t)), \\ y(t) &= \sum_{i=1}^N \mu_i(\zeta)(C_i x(t) + D_i u(t)). \end{cases} \quad (3.45)$$

The scheduling vector ζ ranges over a fixed polytope Θ of N vertices, and the system matrices A_i , B_i , C_i , and D_i define the vertex system. The vertex membership function or scheduling function is denoted by μ which is given by:

$$\begin{cases} \mu_i(\zeta) &= \prod_{j=1}^N \xi_{ij}(\eta_0^j, \eta_1^j), \\ \eta_0^j &= \frac{\bar{\zeta}_j - \zeta_j(t)}{\zeta_j - \underline{\zeta}_j}, \\ \eta_1^j &= 1 - \eta_0^j. \end{cases} \quad (3.46)$$

the term $\xi_{ij}(\eta_0^j, \eta_1^j)$ corresponds to the weighting function which depends on the rule i . The vertex membership function must satisfy the following condition:

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \mu_i(\zeta) = 1, \quad \mu_i(\zeta) \geq 0, \quad \forall \zeta \in \Theta. \quad (3.47)$$

The models discussed in the previous sections, especially the combined kinematic and dynamic models, can be reformulated into LPV systems allowing the embedding

of nonlinearities into linear systems that do not require very expensive computation. The formulation of LPV systems using the nonlinear embedding approach is discussed in [136], Rotondo *et al.* [137] details the LPV formulation using the concept of sector nonlinearity. Other formulation methods use experimental data such as LPV input-output modeling [138]. LPV modeling techniques are advantageous when dealing with real-time control applications. Furthermore, they allow the system to be functional around several operating points whilst being adaptive to the varying parameters, thereby, increasing the model's accuracy and adaptability.

3.9 Conclusions

This chapter presented several methods to model the behavior of the vehicle for control design, three models were discussed for the lateral control design applications, namely the geometric bicycle model, the kinematic bicycle model, and the dynamic one. The magic formula for tire dynamics modeling was briefly explained, and a simplified version was also introduced. Finally, the LPV modeling approach has been introduced, and a combination of kinematic and dynamic models suitable for coupled longitudinal and lateral control design was presented. Generally speaking, the geometric model is suitable for low-speed and less challenging paths, with the advantage of simplicity and low computations. The kinematic model is useful for lateral control applications without highly dynamic maneuvers where no slipping is involved, typically for speeds not exceeding 5 m/s. Finally, the dynamic model and the combined kinematic and dynamic one are suitable for more complicated control scenarios like autonomous driving in challenging trajectories or racing applications where the vehicle operates at its dynamic limits.

Chapter 4

Longitudinal Control Using Self-adaptive PID

Summary

This chapter presents a solution to address the longitudinal control for autonomous vehicles. The control strategy is based on the simple PID theory augmented with online gain adaptation to improve control performance relative to the varying speed profile, road slope, and external wind disturbances. In the first approach, a genetic algorithm is proposed to optimize the PID gains to work for varying parameters such as wind velocity and road slope. The resulting optimal gains are used in a lookup table approach to achieve online gain adaptation. In a second approach, a shallow neural network is proposed for the online gain adaptation, where the PID equations are used to learn the impact of each gain and adapt its value correspondingly. This chapter is based on the following work:

- [115] Y. Kebbati, N. Ait-Oufroukh, V. Vigneron, D. Ichalal, and D. Gruyer, “Optimized self-adaptive PID speed control for autonomous vehicles,” in 2021 26th International Conference on Automation and Computing (ICAC), pp. 1–6, IEEE, 2021.
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4.1 Introduction

The longitudinal control part seeks to ensure that the vehicle follows a certain velocity profile by acting on the acceleration and braking of the vehicle. One of the main applications of longitudinal control is the cruise control system (CC) which has been the subject of extensive research. Simple CC systems work well in highway driving only above certain speeds, since braking control is usually not addressed [139], this has been demonstrated by Osman *et al.* [140] and Simorgh *et al.* [141]. Adaptive cruise control systems were introduced later on to handle both acceleration and braking [142]. Such systems can be divided into high-level controllers that compute

the required acceleration or deceleration, and low-level controllers which actuate the throttle or the brake. These systems allowed to automate vehicles even for urban driving. Due to the importance of longitudinal control, researchers have proposed a variety of controllers. Sliding mode control was introduced by Gao *et al.* [44] for vehicle platooning in uncertain topologies. Xu *et al.* [143] proposed a preview controller for accurate speed control, their approach integrates road slope, speed profile, and vehicle dynamics to form an augmented optimal control. A model predictive controller was developed in [144] for low-level acceleration control.

Actually, most control systems in the industry are based on the PID theory which is easy to design and yet performs very well. However, the non-linearities of the vehicle subsystems and the variety of disturbances that face the vehicle such as road elevation, wind speed, and road conditions require the PID to be adaptive to these changing parameters. Adaptive PID control using the inverse model theory was developed in [141] and [139] for speed control applications. In [145], the authors used the radial basis function to adapt PID gains for the longitudinal control.

Most of the above-mentioned studies are based on oversimplified models excluding or simplifying external disturbances which significantly affect performance in real-life situations. In addition, most adaptation methods require the measurement of certain parameters that are not easily accessible. In this chapter, two PID adaptation methods are proposed to control the velocity of the vehicle; the first method is based on a GA with a full nonlinear vehicle model taking into account external disturbances, and the second method uses a feed-forward NN that utilizes only the error and control signal to learn and adapt the PID gains online. The performance of the designed controllers is assessed and compared through simulations for a predefined velocity profile under varying road slopes and wind disturbances. The modeling of the vehicle longitudinal dynamics is addressed in section 2, and section 3 presents the design, optimization, and adaptation strategies for the controller. The performance of the controller is evaluated and discussed in section 4.

4.2 Vehicle Modeling

The vehicle is mainly propelled by the drive torque produced by the engine and stopped by the braking torque produced by the braking system. The longitudinal dynamics of the vehicle are composed of multi-subsystems that generally account for the propulsion system, the braking system, the wheel, and the tire dynamics.

4.2.1 Vehicle body dynamics

The vehicle body dynamics are obtained by applying Newton's second law as shown in Fig. 4.1, this results in a simplified point mass model [146]:

$$\begin{cases} F_t = m \frac{dv}{dt} + F_a + F_g + F_r, \\ F_g = mg \sin \theta, \\ F_a = \frac{1}{2} \rho C_d A v^2, \\ F_r = mg C_r \cos \theta. \end{cases} \quad (4.1)$$

The parameters are defined as follows: m represents the total mass of the vehicle, F_t , F_a , F_g , and F_r are the traction force, the aerodynamic drag, the downgrade force, and the rolling resistance force applied on the vehicle's CG, respectively. The terms ρ , C_r , and C_d are the air density, the rolling resistance, and the drag coefficients, respectively. The vehicle's cross-sectional area is represented by A , and $\frac{dv}{dt}$ is either the vehicle's acceleration or deceleration.

Figure 4.1: Forces and disturbances affecting the vehicle's longitudinal dynamics.

4.2.2 Engine dynamics

The engine and transmission dynamics make up the vehicle's propulsion system and are highly non-linear. In this chapter, we consider electric vehicles, since it is mostly the case for autonomous vehicles. The engine is then an electric motor that supplies power to the wheels through the transmission. The latter is linked to the electric drive through a gearbox which can be modeled under assumption 5 by equation (4.2):

Assumption 5 *For simplicity, losses induced by the transmission system are neglected.*

$$\begin{cases} T_g &= k_g T_e, \\ \omega_g &= k_g \omega_e. \end{cases} \quad (4.2)$$

where ω_g and ω_e are the angular speeds of the gear and the engine, T_g and T_e are the gear and electric drive torque and k_g represents the ratio of the gearbox. The electric torque is generated by the electric machine, and its model can be static or dynamic [147]. The dynamic model depends on the type of machine whether it is a DC or AC (synchronous/asynchronous) motor. It links the input current/voltage to the output electric torque. The static model in equation (4.3) has been used in this chapter. The latter is a data-driven model based on the electric drive efficiency map.

$$\begin{cases} T_e &= T_{e\text{-ref}}, \\ I_b &= \frac{T_e \omega_g}{u_b \eta^k}. \end{cases} \quad (4.3)$$

with $k = 1$ if $T_e \omega_g \geq 0$, $k = -1$ otherwise. $T_{e\text{-ref}}$ represents the reference electric torque obtained from the motor efficiency map, u_b denotes the battery voltage, I_b and η are the battery current and motor efficiency respectively. Positive currents discharge the battery while negative currents, as in regenerative braking, charge the battery.

4.2.3 Wheel dynamics

The wheel translates the gear torque into a traction force that propels the vehicle. Thus, the angular speed of the wheel determines the velocity of the vehicle, this can be modeled by (4.4), under assumption 6.

Assumption 6 *To simplify modeling, the longitudinal slip is assumed to have minimal effect on the vehicle's longitudinal dynamics.*

$$\begin{cases} F_{t/b} &= \frac{1}{R_w} T_{g/b}, \\ \omega_w &= \frac{1}{R_w} v. \end{cases} \quad (4.4)$$

where $F_{t/b}$ and $T_{g/b}$ denote either the tractive force (Fig. 4.1) and the drive torque or the braking force and braking torque, respectively. The terms R_w and v are the respective wheel radius and vehicle's longitudinal velocity.

4.2.4 Tire dynamics

To take into account the tire non-linearities, the full Pacejka model [24] introduced in Section 3.5.1 is adopted in this chapter. Recall that the longitudinal tire dynamics formula is expressed as:

$$F_x = F_z D \sin(C \tan^{-1}[Bk - E[Bk - \tan^{-1}(Bk)]]). \quad (4.5)$$

with F_x and F_z being the tire longitudinal force and vertical load, k representing the wheel slip, and B, C, D and E being the previously mentioned empirical tire coefficients.

4.2.5 Brake dynamics

The brakes of the vehicle can either be a drum or a disk system. The disk braking system has been used in this work for both front and rear wheels. The braking torque delivered by the mechanism is given as:

$$T_b = \frac{\mu_p P \pi B_a^2 R_m N_{pads}}{4}. \quad (4.6)$$

where P, R_m , and B_a are the applied brake pressure, the mean radius of the brake pad, and the brake actuator diameter respectively. Parameters μ_p and N_{pads} are the disc-pad friction coefficient and the number of pads respectively.

4.2.6 Battery modeling

The electric motor is powered by the battery voltage u_b which can be modeled by a resistor R_b in series with an open circuit voltage V_{oc} . Both of them depend on the

state of charge (SOC):

$$\begin{cases} u_b &= N_s(V_{oc}(SOC) + \frac{I_b}{N_p}R_b(SOC)), \\ SOC &= \frac{1}{C_b} \int_0^t \frac{I_b}{N_p} dt. \end{cases} \quad (4.7)$$

where N_s and N_p are the numbers of cells in series and in parallel respectively, and the denominator C_b is the capacity of the battery.

MATLAB Power-train block-set has been used to build a high-fidelity longitudinal model (see Fig. 4.2). The characteristic parameters of the vehicle, the motor, and the battery were based on the Renault Zoe Vehicle (see table 4.1). The rest of the parameters are block-set default values. Moreover, both the brake and accelerator pedal actuators are modeled as a first-order system with time constants $\tau_a = 0.75s$ and $\tau_b = 1s$ respectively [142]. The controller generates either a braking or an acceleration command at once. Based on the sign of the control signal, the switching logic sends the command to the braking system or to the engine such that a negative control signal means that braking is activated, otherwise, acceleration is activated [145].

Figure 4.2: Model block diagram.

4.3 Controller Design

The longitudinal control of an autonomous vehicle regulates its speed to follow a speed profile. The latter is obtained from a speed planner or profiler based on changes in the external environment like the shape of the road, traffic signs, and weather conditions.

Table 4.1: Simulation parameters.

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
m	1575 kg	C_d	0.29
C_r	0.007	k_g	3.4
A	1.6 m ²	R_w	0.329 m
ρ	1.225 kg/m ³	N_s	96
μ	0.9	g	9.81 m/s ²
R_m	0.1778 m	N_b	2
Height of CG	0.35 m	N_{pads}	2
Front axle to CG	1.2 m	η	95%
Rear axle to CG	1.6 m	C_b	132 Ah

4.3.1 PID control

The PID controller is heavily used in the industry due to its simple design and satisfactory performance. The input to the controller is the error signal defined as the difference between the set-point and the output of the system as shown in Fig. 4.5. The output of the controller depends on the PID gains and is governed by the following equation:

$$u(t) = K_p e(t) + K_i \int e(\tau) d\tau + K_d \frac{de(t)}{dt}, \quad (4.8)$$

where K_p , K_i , and K_d are the proportional, integral, and derivative gains and $e(t)$ is the error between set-point R and output Y . The discrete form of the PID has been used in this work, where the control law is obtained using the Tustin method with T_s sampling time:

$$\begin{cases} \Delta u(k) &= \alpha e(k) + \beta e(k-1) + \gamma e(k-2), \\ \alpha &= K_p + \frac{K_d}{T_s} + \frac{K_i T_s}{2}, \\ \beta &= \frac{K_i T_s}{2} - 2\frac{K_d}{T_s} - K_p, \\ \gamma &= \frac{K_d}{T_s}. \end{cases} \quad (4.9)$$

The performance of a PID controller is measured in terms of overshoot O_s , rising

time R_t , and settling time S_t . It depends on the choice of gains which is not straightforward, there are several tuning techniques such as root locus, gain-phase margin and the widely used Ziegler Nichols [148]. However, these methods are generally limited to linear systems and have poor disturbance rejection. To account for the effects of road angle and wind speed on the controller performance, the designed model is simulated with the GA to optimize the gains of the PID controller. The choice of this meta-heuristic optimization method is based on its excellent performance reported in the literature [149].

4.3.2 GA-based PID optimization

Genetic algorithms are inspired by the biological evolution theory, which is based on the process of natural selection and genetics [149]. The algorithm uses population sets of multiple potential encoded solutions called chromosomes. Each chromosome is rated by a fitness function (4.10) that determines how good of a solution it is.

$$\text{Fitness}_{\text{value}} = \frac{1}{\text{Performance}_{\text{index}}}. \quad (4.10)$$

The GA uses crossover and mutation operations (Fig. 4.3) to enhance the existing solutions. The crossover operation merges existing chromosomes together, while the mutation operation modifies the encoding of existing chromosomes to yield new and better chromosomes. The fitness score of each chromosome is assigned by an objective function and only fit chromosomes are selected to evolve in the next operation. In the context of PID tuning, the objective function minimizes the error that is fed to the controller. The Mean Squared Error (MSE) has been used as the objective function for a consistent performance comparison between GA-PID and NN-PID. The GA optimization tool in (Algorithm 1) has been used in the optimization process. The process initiates a random population of a certain size containing values (chromosomes) for the PID gains (K_p , K_i , and K_d), with which the vehicle is simulated.

The fitness value of each chromosome is assessed through the MSE function. Only fit chromosomes with high fitness scores are selected as fit parents, while unfit chromosomes with low fitness scores are discarded. The GA then performs mutation and crossover on the best-fit parents and produces a new population. The number of

Figure 4.3: Genetic operations.

Algorithm 1 Genetic algorithm.

Require: Gen_{max}, N_p ▷ Generations, Population Size
 $Pop \leftarrow N_p$ Parents ▷ Random Population
while $Generation < Gen_{max}$ **do**
 $Child \leftarrow emptyPop$ ▷ Create Child Population
 while $Child \leq full$ **do**
 $Parent1 \leftarrow RWS(Pop)$ ▷ RWS Selection
 $Parent2 \leftarrow RWS(Pop)$
 $Child1, 2 \leftarrow UCrossover(Parent1, Parent2)$ ▷ Perform Uniform Crossover
 $Child1, 2 \leftarrow GMutation(Child1, Child2)$ ▷ Perform Mutation
 $Fitness \leftarrow Evaluate(Child1, Child2)$ ▷ Evaluate new offsprings
 $Offspring \leftarrow Child1, Child2$
 end while
 $Pop \leftarrow Offspring$ ▷ Replace Population
end while
 $Solution \leftarrow Best\ fitness$ ▷ Save Best Solution

best-fit parents to be enhanced is predefined as a percentage called elite count value. This whole process is repeated over many generations. Moreover, the first selection of population individuals is based on the roulette wheel method (RWS) [150]. The PID gains are optimized with regard to the varying parameters of the model and new optimal PID gains are generated for each case of the varying parameters. A variety of cases were tested and the results were stored in a data set. The data set is then used in a lookup table to select the optimal gains corresponding to the varying parameters. This method allows continuous adaptation of the PID gains as the varying parameters change along a speed profile or drive cycle.

4.3.3 Neural network based PID adaptation

The use of a neural network inside the control loop makes it possible to adapt the PID gains online. This method presents a better and more suitable alternative to offline optimization with GA. The NN is trained online using the back-propagation of the error generated from previous PID gains. The architecture of the NN is an MLP composed of an input layer with four inputs, a hidden layer with four neurons, and an output layer with three neurons (Fig. 4.4). The Sigmoid activation function has been used for the hidden layer, while contrary to existing works, instead of the identity, the ReLU function has been used for the output layer to avoid predicting negative gains. The overall system is given in Fig. 4.5.

Figure 4.4: Neural network architecture.

The inputs to the hidden layer (S_j) and output layer (Z_j) are given by (4.11). w_{ij}^i are the weights between the input and hidden layer and w_{ij}^h are the weights between the hidden and output layer, n_h and n_o represent the number of hidden units and output units, respectively. Parameters x_i are the inputs to the network, the outputs of the hidden layer h_j and the outputs of the network o_j are given in equations (4.12) where f and g are the Sigmoid and ReLU activation functions respectively.

$$\begin{cases} S_j = \sum_{i=1}^{n+1} w_{ij}^i x_i, & \text{for } j = 1, \dots, n_h \\ Z_j = \sum_{i=1}^{n_h+1} w_{ij}^h h_i, & \text{for } j = 1, \dots, n_o \end{cases} \quad (4.11)$$

$$\begin{cases} h_j = f(S_j), \\ o_j = g(Z_j). \end{cases} \quad (4.12)$$

Figure 4.5: Block diagram of the system.

The gradient descent algorithm minimizes the MSE function $E(k) = \frac{1}{2}e(k)^2$, which is back-propagated through the network using the chain rule [151]. The gradient of the error term is given by:

$$\frac{\delta E(k)}{\delta w_{ij}^h(k)} = \frac{\delta E(k)}{\delta e(k)} \frac{\delta e(k)}{\delta y(k)} \frac{\delta y(k)}{\delta u(k)} \frac{\delta u(k)}{\delta o_j} \frac{\delta o_j}{\delta w_{ij}^h(k)}. \quad (4.13)$$

where

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{\delta E(k)}{\delta e(k)} \frac{\delta e(k)}{\delta y(k)} = e(k), \\ \frac{\delta y(k)}{\delta u(k)} \approx \text{sign}\left(\frac{y(k)-y(k-1)}{u(k)-u(k-1)}\right), \\ \frac{\delta u(k)}{\delta o_1} = e(k) - e(k-1), \\ \frac{\delta u(k)}{\delta o_2} = \frac{T_s}{2}(e(k) + e(k-1)), \\ \frac{\delta u(k)}{\delta o_3} = \frac{1}{T_s}(e(k) - 2e(k-1) + e(k-2)), \\ \frac{\delta o_j}{\delta w_{ij}^h} = h_i. \end{array} \right. \quad (4.14)$$

The term $\frac{\delta y(k)}{\delta u(k)}$ is not accessible in the network, therefore, it is approximated by $\text{sign}\left(\frac{y(k)-y(k-1)}{u(k)-u(k-1)}\right)$, which shows whether the control law is improving. To avoid singularities, the expression $\text{sign}((y(k) - y(k-1)) \times (u(k) - u(k-1)))$ is used instead. For the hidden layer, the error term is defined as:

$$\frac{\delta E(k)}{\delta w_{ij}^i(k)} = \frac{\delta E(k)}{\delta h_j(k)} \frac{\delta h_j(k)}{\delta S_j(k)} \frac{\delta S_j(k)}{\delta w_{ij}^i(k)}. \quad (4.15)$$

where: $i = 1, \dots, n_i + 1$, and $j = 1, \dots, n_h$.

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\delta E(k)}{\delta h_j(k)} &= -e(k) \frac{\delta y(k)}{\delta u(k)} \sum_{i=1}^{n_0} \frac{\delta u(k)}{\delta o_i(k)} w_{jl}^h(k), \\ \frac{\delta h_j(k)}{\delta S_j(k)} &= h_j(k)(1 - h_j(k)), \\ \frac{\delta S_j(k)}{\delta w_{ij}^i(k)} &= x_i(k). \end{cases} \quad (4.16)$$

The weights are updated according to the gradient descent rule with learning rate η as follows:

$$\begin{cases} w_{ij}^h(k+1) &= w_{ij}^h(k) - \eta \frac{\delta E(k)}{\delta w_{ij}^h(k)}, \\ w_{ij}^i(k+1) &= w_{ij}^i(k) - \eta \frac{\delta E(k)}{\delta w_{ij}^i(k)}. \end{cases} \quad (4.17)$$

4.4 Results and Discussion

The designed PID controllers have been tested with the vehicle's longitudinal model given in Section 4.2. The GA algorithm is used to optimize the PID gains for three scenarios:

- **Sc1:** A velocity profile without disturbances ($v_w = 0$ and $\theta = 0$).
- **Sc2:** A velocity profile subject to wind disturbance and road slope (Fig. 4.6).
- **Sc3:** Optimization for different values of v_{ref}, v_w and θ separately.

Figure 4.6: Wind speed and road slope profiles.

Both scenarios 1 and 2 produce a triplet of optimal gains (K_p, K_i , and K_d) for the specific speed and disturbance profiles. Scenario 2 shows the effect of the disturbances (v_w and θ) on the performance of the controller. Scenario 3 is adaptive and

more generalized and produces a data set of optimized gains corresponding to the changing values of v_{ref} , v_w , and θ . The GA-PID is compared to the NN-PID with optimized initial weights and learning rate. Initialization of the weights and choice of the learning rate are very important stages for the performance of the NN-PID and its convergence speed. The learning rate is selected by trial and error after the first few simulations.

The GA optimization for scenarios 1 and 2 results in the triplets $\{K_{p1} = 999.75, K_{i1} = 0.1, K_{d1} = 0.3\}$ and $\{K_{p2} = 383.79, K_{i2} = 0.11, K_{d2} = 128.84\}$, respectively. The corresponding results are compared in Fig. 4.7 where the speed tracking and error variation signals are in (m/s) and the acceleration and braking signals are in percentage (%). For scenario 3, the GA-PID gains are optimized for $v_{\text{ref}} \in [0, 30]$ m/s, $\theta \in [-10^\circ, 10^\circ]$ and $v_w \in [-10, 15]$ m/s. The GA algorithm runs offline for several hours and generates a data set of 3500 data points, corresponding to the different varying parameters. The PID adaptation using the generated data set through a lookup table is compared to that of the NN-PID in Fig. 4.8.

In scenario 1, the GA-PID produces a smoother and faster response with no overshoots due to the absence of disturbances. On the other hand, the inclusion of road slope and wind disturbance in scenario 2 increases the response time which corresponds to real-life situations, this results in slower tracking with slight overshoots resulting in less smooth responses. The GA-PID in scenario 3 is smoother than the NN-PID which is more aggressive since the adaptation takes place at each iteration. On the other hand, the NN-PID is more robust to disturbances and faster because it reacts immediately whenever the error magnitude changes and adapts the PID gains to quickly reject the disturbances. Overall, both GA-PID and NN-PID ensure adaptive control with very good performance and disturbance rejection.

Table 4.2 compares the controller performance in terms of the total MSE errors and evaluates the response time R_t , the settling time S_t , and the overshoot O_s for a step response using different values for the hidden layer neurons (h) and learning rate (η). The GA-PID in scenario 2 has the best performance, while the NN-PID with (h=10, $\eta=0.01$) is the second best controller.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 4.7: (a) Speed tracking, (b) Tracking error, (c) Acceleration/Brake signals for Sc_1 and Sc_2 .

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 4.8: (a) Speed tracking, (b) Tracking error, (c) Acceleration/Brake signals for S_{C3} vs NN-PID.

Table 4.2: Controller performance for different h and η .

Method	T-MSE	$R_t(s)$	$S_t(s)$	$O_s(\%)$
GA-PID(Sc1)	7.563	0.87	1.164	6.68
GA-PID(Sc2)	7.502	0.348	0.444	4.79
GA-PID(Sc3)	7.534	0.449	0.616	1.52
NN-PID($\eta=0.01$, $h = 4$)	7.596	0.348	0.445	4.6
NN-PID($\eta=0.1$, $h = 4$)	7.605	0.37	0.445	4.59
NN-PID($\eta=0.8$, $h = 4$)	7.604	0.37	0.445	4.59
NN-PID($\eta=0.01$, $h = 10$)	7.555	0.348	0.445	4.6
NN-PID($\eta=0.8$, $h = 15$)	7.597	0.348	0.445	4.59
NN-PID($\eta=0.8$, $h = 20$)	7.557	0.348	0.445	4.6

4.5 Conclusions

In this chapter, adaptive PID control has been addressed using two different approaches for the longitudinal control of autonomous vehicles. In the first approach (GA-PID), the GA has been used to optimize the PID gains for a variety of working conditions with changing velocities, road slopes, and wind disturbances, where the MSE has been used as a cost function. A look-up approach is used for real-time gain adaptation. The advantages of this approach are (a) optimization with a full vehicle model, unlike the other approaches, which use simplified models in the form of a transfer function or a state space representation. (b) optimization for a variety of cases and adaptation via a look-up table. The downside of this approach is the heavy calculations required. The second approach (NN-PID) was based on online learning with an MLP-NN, where the PID gains are adapted with back-propagation. This approach has the following advantages: (a) automatic online PID adaptation and learning capability. (b) adaptation only requires error and control signals. (c) fast

instant reaction to error changes at every iteration.

These characteristics make the NN-PID more robust and better at rejecting disturbances. On the other hand, the GA-PID produces optimized PID gains in terms of response speed, precision, and overshoot but does not generalize well for different cases of disturbances and set points. The NN-PID has been found to be more efficient in terms of adaptability and generalization. However, its performance significantly depends on weights initialization and choice of learning rate. In general, the GA-PID was smoother and faster than the NN-PID, while the latter was more adaptive and more robust.

Chapter 5

Lateral Control Using Optimized Adaptive MPC

Summary

This chapter proposes optimal adaptive MPC for the path tracking task, Laguerre functions are introduced to approximate the MPC control signal and improve the computation speed which is very important for real-time applications. This method allows solving the optimization problem for long prediction and control horizons without using a large number of parameters. Furthermore, a new improved PSO algorithm is introduced for optimizing the performance of the MPC controller by tuning its different parameters offline. Then, three different approaches are presented to achieve controller adaptability. In the first approach, parameter adaption is realized online using the lookup table scheduling technique. In the second approach, an MLP neural network is developed to learn the data of optimal MPC parameters that were generated during the optimization phase. The latter is then used for online MPC parameter adaptation. In the final approach, an ANFIS system is proposed to learn to adapt the MPC controller using the previously generated data set. The developed controllers are assessed and compared to the standard MPC and the pure pursuit controller. The content of this chapter is based on the following papers:

- [111] Y. Kebbati, V. Puig, N. Ait-Oufroukh, V. Vigneron, and D. Ichalal, “Optimized adaptive MPC for lateral control of autonomous vehicles,” in 2021 9th International Conference on Control, Mechatronics and Automation (ICCMA), IEEE, 2021, pp. 95–103.
- [112] Y. Kebbati, N. Ait-Oufroukh, V. Vigneron, and D. Ichalal, “Neural network and ANFIS based auto-adaptive MPC for path tracking in autonomous vehicles,” in 2021 IEEE International Conference on Networking, Sensing and Control (ICNSC), IEEE, vol. 1, 2021, pp. 1–6.

5.1 Introduction

Path tracking is a fundamental part of autonomous driving, it ensures that the vehicle follows a predefined trajectory, and this is achieved by controlling the vehicle’s lateral

dynamics. Various control strategies for this task are reported in the literature. For example, authors of [152] developed a lateral control system based on the adaptive pure pursuit controller. An output-feedback robust controller is introduced in [153] to assist in the path-tracking task. Han *et al.* [65] designed an adaptive neural network PID controller for path tracking, and Hu *et al.* [154] introduced an integral sliding mode controller. However, most of the above-mentioned strategies cannot handle constraints that are imposed by the safety and physical limitations of actuators. MPC stands out in this field due to the fact that it systematically handles constraints on control, output, and state signals, in addition to the fact that it easily handles MIMO systems. Although this technique was first introduced for slow process control due to its long optimizations, recent hardware breakthroughs made it possible to apply MPC to fast dynamic systems like autonomous vehicles. The theory of MPC has matured enough over the last decades, and nowadays its applications cover the vast majority of fields, especially autonomous driving. For example, Guo *et al.* [29] developed a path-tracking MPC controller that considers measurable disturbances, and solves the optimization problem using the differential evolution algorithm. In MPC control methods, there are many parameters to tune such as the weighting matrices and prediction and control horizons which is not trivial. Authors of [26] and [155] used fuzzy inference systems (FIS) to tune the weighting matrices of the MPC. Papers [156], and [157] used GA and PSO to optimize the MPC tunable parameters. Nevertheless, the controllers in these approaches remain non-adaptive to varying parameters and external uncertainties. In [158], Lin *et al.* designed an adaptive MPC controller that adapts to estimated varying road friction and cornering stiffness coefficients. Paper [159] introduced an adaptive MPC for lane-keeping systems, where the steering offset was continuously learned from measured data and adapted. Nonetheless, research on learning the control algorithm is still limited, and most studies only consider constant longitudinal velocities. As the previous chapter addressed longitudinal control, this chapter follows on by proposing adaptive MPC control for the lateral control task. A new approach to learning and adapting the MPC algorithm to external disturbances and varying working conditions is introduced. The developed solutions are tested and compared for different scenarios under a variety of disturbances. Section 2 of this chapter presents the vehicle modeling and controller design, and section 3 discusses

controller optimization. Sections 4 and 5 demonstrate controller adaptation with neural networks and ANFIS, while controller performance is evaluated and compared in section 6.

5.2 Vehicle Modeling and Controller Design

5.2.1 Vehicle lateral dynamics model

Path tracking is associated with the lateral motion of the vehicle, which is the displacement on the y-axis and the yaw motion around the z-axis. Therefore, a 2DoF dynamic bicycle model is derived from the model presented in Section 3.4 by decoupling the lateral and longitudinal dynamics. Considering equation (3.16), using angle approximation and substituting equation (3.20) into (3.15) and then (3.15) into (3.13) we obtain the lateral dynamics model as the following:

$$\begin{cases} m(\ddot{y} + v_x \dot{\psi}) &= 2[C_{yf}(\delta_f - \frac{\dot{y} + l_f \dot{\psi}}{v_x}) + C_{yr} \frac{l_r \dot{\psi} - \dot{y}}{v_x}], \\ I_z \ddot{\psi} &= 2[l_f C_{yf}(\delta_f - \frac{\dot{y} + l_f \dot{\psi}}{v_x}) - l_r C_{yr} \frac{l_r \dot{\psi} - \dot{y}}{v_x}]. \end{cases} \quad (5.1)$$

The above-mentioned model can be transformed into the following continuous state space representation:

$$\begin{cases} \dot{x}_c &= A_c x_c + B_c u, \\ y_c &= C_c x_c. \end{cases} \quad (5.2)$$

where $x_c = [\dot{y} \ \psi \ \dot{\psi} \ y]^T$ is the state vector, $y_c = y$ is the output of the system, $u = \delta_f$ is the control input and A_c , B_c and C_c are the respective state, control and output matrices given by:

$$A_c = \begin{bmatrix} -2\frac{C_{yf} + C_{yr}}{mv_x} & 0 & -v_x - 2\frac{C_{yf}l_f - C_{yr}l_r}{mv_x} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -2\frac{C_{yf}l_f - C_{yr}l_r}{I_z v_x} & 0 & -2\frac{C_{yf}l_f^2 + C_{yr}l_r^2}{I_z v_x} & 0 \\ 1 & v_x & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad B_c = \begin{bmatrix} 2\frac{C_{yf}}{m} \\ 0 \\ 2\frac{C_{yf}l_f}{I_z} \\ 0 \end{bmatrix},$$

$$C_c = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}.$$

5.2.2 MPC controller design

The linear MPC controller with Laguerre functions is considered in this chapter due to its high computational efficiency. We quickly remind that the idea of MPC control is to use a descriptive model of the plant to predict its behavior in the future along a prediction horizon N_p , and then produce an optimal control sequence along the control horizon N_c , that minimizes the error between the set-point and the output of the plant. In the context of path tracking, MPC aims to minimize the gap between the reference trajectory and the predicted trajectory. The optimal control sequence is achieved by minimizing a quadratic cost function subject to constraints, therefore, solving a constrained convex optimization problem. However, only the first term of this sequence is applied at each iteration, and the whole prediction-optimization process is repeated iteratively. This is known as the receding horizon principle (Fig. 5.1). The linearized vehicle dynamic model in equation (5.1) is discretized to be used as the prediction model of the MPC controller:

Figure 5.1: MPC receding horizon concept.

$$\begin{cases} x_{(k+1)} &= A_{v_x}x_{(k)} + Bu_{(k)}, \\ y_{(k)} &= Cx_{(k)}. \end{cases} \quad (5.3)$$

To allow the MPC controller to be adaptive to varying longitudinal speeds, the state matrix A_{v_x} is iteratively updated with the current longitudinal velocity to produce an adaptive prediction model for varying speed profiles and not only fixed longitudinal

speeds as is the case in most studies in the literature [26, 158–160]. This standard model is then augmented by embedding an integrator and introducing the output $y(k)$ to the state vector as follows:

$$\begin{cases} \tilde{x}_{(k+1)} &= \tilde{A}_{v_x} \tilde{x}_{(k)} + \tilde{B} \Delta u_{(k)}, \\ \tilde{y}_{(k)} &= \tilde{C} \tilde{x}_{(k)}. \end{cases} \quad (5.4)$$

where the new state $\tilde{x} = [\Delta x_{(k)} \ y_{(k)}]^T$ is connected to the output, the new input signal is $\Delta u_{(k)}$ and the augmented system matrices are given by:

$$\tilde{A}_{v_x} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{v_x} & o_m^T \\ CA_{v_x} & I_{q \times q} \end{bmatrix}, \tilde{B} = \begin{bmatrix} B \\ CB \end{bmatrix}, \tilde{C} = [o_m \ I_{q \times q}].$$

o_m is a $q \times n$ zero matrix, and $I_{q \times q}$ is the identity matrix with n and q being the number of states and outputs, respectively. A , B and C have the respective dimensions $n \times n$, $n \times m$ and $q \times n$, with m being the number of inputs, .

Assumption 7 *At $k_i > 0$, the state vector $x(k)$ is assumed available, providing the current plant information.*

The future control trajectory along the control horizon N_c is given by:

$$[\Delta u(k_i), \Delta u(k_i + 1), \dots, \Delta u(k_i + N_c - 1)].$$

The future plant information is predicted along the prediction horizon N_p using the model given in equation (5.4) and the future control parameters through the following equation:

$$Y = Fx_{(k_i)} + \Phi \Delta U. \quad (5.5)$$

where Y is the future output, F is the future prediction matrix, Φ is the future control matrix and ΔU is the future control sequence given by:

$$Y = [y(k_i + 1|k_i) \ y(k_i + 2|k_i) \ y(k_i + 3|k_i) \ \dots \ y(k_i + N_p|k_i)]^T.$$

$$\Delta U = [\Delta u(k_i) \ \Delta u(k_i + 1) \ \Delta u(k_i + 2) \ \dots \ \Delta u(k_i + N_c - 1)]^T.$$

$$F = \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{C}\tilde{A}_{v_x} \\ \tilde{C}\tilde{A}_{v_x}^2 \\ \tilde{C}\tilde{A}_{v_x}^3 \\ \vdots \\ \tilde{C}\tilde{A}_{v_x}^{N_p} \end{bmatrix}, \Phi = \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{C}\tilde{B} & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ \tilde{C}\tilde{A}_{v_x}\tilde{B} & \tilde{C}\tilde{B} & \dots & 0 \\ \tilde{C}\tilde{A}_{v_x}^2\tilde{B} & \tilde{C}\tilde{A}_{v_x}\tilde{B} & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \tilde{C}\tilde{A}_{v_x}^{N_p-1}\tilde{B} & \tilde{C}\tilde{A}_{v_x}^{N_p-2}\tilde{B} & \dots & \tilde{C}\tilde{A}_{v_x}^{N_p-N_c}\tilde{B} \end{bmatrix}.$$

The goal of MPC is to find the best ΔU that minimizes the error $(R_s - Y)$, where $R_s = [1 \ 1 \dots 1]r(k_i)$ is the reference trajectory containing N_p set-point information $r(k_i)$. Then, the constrained optimization problem is formulated as follows:

$$\min J = (R_s - Y)^T Q (R_s - Y) + \Delta U^T R \Delta U. \quad (5.6)$$

$$s.t : x(k+1) = \tilde{A}_{v_x}x(k) + \tilde{B}\Delta u(k). \quad (5.7)$$

$$\Delta u_{min} \leq \Delta u \leq \Delta u_{max}. \quad (5.8)$$

$$u_{min} \leq u \leq u_{max}. \quad (5.9)$$

$$y_{min} \leq y \leq y_{max}. \quad (5.10)$$

Equation (5.6) is the cost function to be minimized, (5.7) is the vehicle dynamic model, and equations (5.8) to (5.10) represent the constraints on the control, control increment, and output signals. Q and R are weighting matrices that penalize the tracking precision and control magnitude, respectively. The set of constraints can be reformulated and expressed in terms of the decision variable ΔU as:

$$M\Delta U \leq \gamma. \quad (5.11)$$

such that M contains 3 reformulation sub-matrices and γ contains the set of upper and lower bounds on the control, control increment, and output signals. The model predictive control becomes a QP problem with quadratic cost function and linear inequality constraints formulated in the following form:

$$\begin{cases} J = \frac{1}{2}x^T E x + x^T F, \\ Mx \leq \gamma. \end{cases} \quad (5.12)$$

where E, F, M , and γ are compatible matrices and vectors and x is the decision variable (ΔU) in the quadratic programming problem. E is assumed symmetric and positive definite.

5.2.3 Laguerre function approximation

The Laguerre function is used to reduce the computation burden by approximating the control sequence ΔU . The orthogonal feature of the Laguerre function allows to realize long control horizons without using many parameters. The discrete form of a Laguerre function is given by:

$$\begin{aligned}\Gamma_1(z) &= \frac{\sqrt{1-\alpha^2}}{1-\alpha z^{-1}}. \\ \Gamma_2(z) &= \frac{\sqrt{1-\alpha^2}}{1-\alpha z^{-1}} \frac{z^{-1}-\alpha}{1-\alpha z^{-1}}. \\ &\vdots \\ \Gamma_N(z) &= \frac{\sqrt{1-\alpha^2}}{1-\alpha z^{-1}} \left(\frac{z^{-1}-\alpha}{1-\alpha z^{-1}} \right)^{N-1}.\end{aligned}\tag{5.13}$$

where $0 \leq \alpha < 1$ is the pole of the discretized Laguerre network called the scaling factor and N is the number of terms. The orthonormality of the Laguerre functions in the time domain is expressed by:

$$\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} l_i(k)l_j(k) = 0 \quad \text{for } i \neq j.\tag{5.14}$$

$$\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} l_i(k)l_j(k) = 1 \quad \text{for } i = j.\tag{5.15}$$

The discrete Laguerre function expression is simplified into a vector form as the following:

$$L(k) = [l_1(k) \ l_2(k) \ \dots \ l_N(k)]^T.\tag{5.16}$$

where $l_i(k)$ is the inverse z-transform of $\Gamma_i(z, \alpha)$:

$$\Gamma_k(z) = \Gamma_{k-1}(z) \frac{z^{-1}-\alpha}{1-\alpha z^{-1}}.\tag{5.17}$$

Based on equation (5.17), the Laguerre sequence can be expressed recursively by:

$$L(k+1) = A_l L(k).\tag{5.18}$$

with A_l being an $N \times N$ matrix and a function of α and $\beta = (1 - \alpha^2)$, and $L(0)$ as initial condition given by:

$$L(0)^T = \sqrt{\beta}[1 \ -\alpha \ \alpha^2 \ -\alpha^3 \ \dots \ (-1)^{N-1}\alpha^{N-1}].$$

For $N=5$, we have: $A_l = \begin{bmatrix} \alpha & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \beta & \alpha & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -\alpha\beta & \beta & \alpha & 0 & 0 \\ \alpha^2\beta & -\alpha\beta & \beta & \alpha & 0 \\ -\alpha^3\beta & \alpha^2\beta & -\alpha\beta & \beta & \alpha \end{bmatrix}$, $L(0)^T = \sqrt{\beta} \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ -\alpha \\ \alpha^2 \\ -\alpha^3 \\ \alpha^4 \end{bmatrix}$.

For the case of $\alpha = 0$, the Laguerre function becomes just a set of pulses and the MPC design becomes equivalent to the traditional approach discussed earlier. Thus, the control increment at $(k+i)$ is represented by the Laguerre terms as the following:

$$\Delta u(k+i) = \sum_{j=1}^N c_j(k) l_j(i) = L(i)^T \eta, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, N_c. \quad (5.19)$$

where $\eta = [c_1 \ c_2 \ \dots \ c_N]^T$ is the Laguerre fitting coefficient, solving the QP problem becomes a matter of finding the optimal fitting coefficient η_{opt} . The solution of the QP problem given in equations (5.12) can be divided into two cases; minimization with equality constraints and minimization with inequality constraints. For equality constraints, the QP problem is solved using Lagrange multipliers:

$$J = \frac{1}{2} x^T E x + x^T F + \lambda^T (M x - \gamma). \quad (5.20)$$

The Lagrange expression is subject to equality constraints ($M x = \gamma$), and the solution is obtained by finding the optimal Lagrange multiplier λ and corresponding decision variable x through partial derivatives equated to zero:

$$\frac{\partial J}{\partial x} = E x + F + M^T \lambda = 0. \quad (5.21)$$

$$\frac{\partial J}{\partial \lambda} = M x - \gamma = 0. \quad (5.22)$$

Hence, the solution is the optimal λ_{opt} which contains the Lagrange multipliers, and the optimal decision variable x_{opt} which denotes ΔU in the context of predictive control:

$$\lambda_{opt} = -(M E^{-1} M^T)^{-1} (\gamma + M E^{-1} F). \quad (5.23)$$

$$x_{opt} = -E^{-1} (M^T \lambda_{opt} + F). \quad (5.24)$$

For inequality constraints, ($M x \leq \gamma$) is divided into active ($M x = \gamma$) and inactive ($M x < \gamma$) constraints and these are defined in terms of Lagrange multipliers through

the Kuhn-Tucker conditions:

$$\begin{aligned}
 Ex + F + M^T\lambda &= 0, \\
 Mx - \gamma &\leq 0, \\
 \lambda^T(Mx - \gamma) &= 0, \\
 \lambda &\geq 0.
 \end{aligned} \tag{5.25}$$

The solution in this case requires the identification of active constraints first and then solving the optimization for those active constraints while inactive constraints are eliminated. In this chapter, the Hildreth's QP method has been used to solve the QP problem of (5.20), more details about this method can be found in [161].

5.3 Controller Optimization with Improved PSO

Particle swarm optimization is a swarm intelligence algorithm that mimics animal group behavior, such as bird flocks and fish swarms. It is an evolutionary population-based algorithm where each individual (particle) represents a possible solution and the group of individuals makes up a swarm. Due to its flexibility and ease of implementation, the PSO tool is used in various fields [162–164]. In an optimization problem with N dimensions, each i^{th} particle is attributed with a velocity vector $v_i = [v_{i1}, v_{i2}, \dots, v_{in}]$ and a position vector $p_i = [p_{i1}, p_{i2}, \dots, p_{in}]$. The classic algorithm is defined by:

$$\begin{cases} v_i(k+1) = \omega v_i(k) + c_1 r_1 (Pb_i(k) - x_i(k)) + c_2 r_2 (Gb(k) - x_i(k)), \\ x_i(k+1) = x_i(k) + v_i(k+1). \end{cases} \tag{5.26}$$

where at each iteration k , v_i and p_i are the velocity and position of particle i , and ω is the inertia weight. The coefficients $c_{1,2}$ are learning factors called cognitive and social accelerations, respectively. The terms $r_{1,2} \in [0, 1]$ are random numbers, Pb_i represents the position with the best fitness score for particle i , and Gb is the global best position in the swarm. In the classic algorithm ω and $c_{1,2}$ are constant values, but several improved versions have been reported in the literature such as [165] and [166] where w and $c_{1,2}$ are dynamic according to equation (5.27) and table 5.1:

$$\omega = \omega_{max} - (\omega_{max} - \omega_{min}) \frac{g}{G}. \tag{5.27}$$

where ω_{max} and ω_{min} are the maximum and minimum of the inertia weight, g and G represent the number of the actual generation and the maximum number of generations, respectively.

Table 5.1: Rules for updating c_1 and c_2 .

Phase	c_1	c_2
Exploration	Big increase	Big decrease
Exploitation	Small increase	Small decrease
Convergence	Small increase	Small increase
Jumping out	Big decrease	Big Increase

The cognitive acceleration coefficient c_1 is increased during the exploration phase to explore the swarm and pull the particles towards the best position Pb . During the exploitation phase, the social acceleration coefficient c_2 is increased to push the swarm towards the global best position Gb . In the convergence phase, the swarm begins to find the globally optimal region, and increasing c_2 while slightly decreasing c_1 helps accelerate the convergence. At the final phase of the optimization, the global best particle moves from a local optimum, where most particles are clustered, towards a better optimum (the new global best). Therefore, all clustered particles must move as fast as possible toward the new global best. To achieve this, c_2 is greatly increased during this phase while c_1 is greatly decreased. To balance the four phases in table 5.1, we control c_1 and c_2 by the following logic which promotes the global search capabilities of PSO:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} c_1(k+1) = c_1(k) + \alpha, \\ c_2(k+1) = c_2(k) + \beta, \\ \alpha = -\beta = 0.05 \quad \text{for } \frac{g}{G} \leq 20\%, \\ \alpha = -\beta = 0.02 \quad \text{for } 20\% \leq \frac{g}{G} \leq 35\%, \\ \alpha = -\beta = -0.035 \quad \text{for } 35\% \leq \frac{g}{G} \leq 75\%, \\ \alpha = -\beta = -0.0015 \quad \text{for } \frac{g}{G} \geq 75\%. \end{array} \right. \quad (5.28)$$

According to (5.27), ω decreases linearly over iterations, where small values of ω

promote the local search of PSO [166]. A new formula for updating the inertia weight is proposed in this chapter (5.29), which ensures an exponential decrease rather than a linear one.

$$\omega = \omega_{min} + \frac{\exp(\omega_{max} - \lambda_1(\omega_{max} + \omega_{min})\frac{g}{G})}{\lambda_2}. \quad (5.29)$$

This has been found to effectively enhance the overall search capabilities of PSO when coupled with the control logic of $c_{1,2}$. Unlike a linear decrease, an exponential decrease of ω ensures faster convergence and better overall optimization. Parameters $\lambda_{1,2}$ are adjustable constants introduced to achieve a decrease from ω_{max} to ω_{min} . The performance of the proposed PSO algorithm is compared to the improved version of [166], the modified PSO of [165] and the latter enhanced with a damped inertia weight instead of a constant one ($\omega(k+1) = \omega(k) \times \omega_{dmp}$). The sphere function ($f_1(x) = \sum_{i=1}^n x_i^2$) is used as a benchmark test similar to [166], and the optimization is carried out with the parameters given in table 5.2 and the logic stated by equations (5.28). The obtained results in Fig. 5.2, show that the proposed PSO is much faster than the other PSO versions and able to find better optimal solutions. After 41 generations, the proposed PSO reached a fitness of 10^{-3} compared to 2.1 and 3.11 for the improved PSO and the classic damped PSO respectively, while the classic PSO reached only 5.59.

Figure 5.2: Performance of the proposed PSO.

The proposed PSO algorithm is used to optimize the parameters of the MPC

Table 5.2: PSO hyperparameters.

Parameter	Interpretation	Value
G	Number of generations	150
N_{Pop}	Number of particles	20
ω_{max}	Maximum inertia weight	0.99
ω_{min}	Minimum inertia weight	0.1
ω_{dmp}	Damping constant	0.99
c_{1i}	Initial cognitive acceleration coefficient	2
c_{2i}	Initial social acceleration coefficient	2
λ_1	Constant	30
λ_2	Constant	3

designed with the Laguerre function in Section 5.2.3. These parameters include; the prediction and control horizons N_p and N_c , the weighting matrices Q and R and the number of Laguerre terms N . To the best of our knowledge, existing research has not addressed the tuning and adaptation of these parameters altogether. Thus, the proposed approach allows us to optimize the controller performance in terms of its tunable parameters and Laguerre approximation at the same time without losing computation efficiency. The MSE is used as a fitness function to assess the optimality of the solutions. The schematic diagram of the proposed approach is given in Fig. 5.3, where y_{ref} , y , v_x and x_{state} are the reference path, the vehicle's lateral position, the longitudinal velocity, and the states vector respectively.

Figure 5.3: Schematic diagram of the proposed approach.

5.4 Results and Discussion for Adaptive MPC

A high-fidelity vehicle model has been built using the Vehicle Dynamics Blockset of MATLAB, the latter consists of a 3DoF dual track lateral dynamics block with nonlinear Pacejka tire formula [24]. In addition, a simplified powertrain block is added to accommodate varying speed profiles with the predictive longitudinal driver block. The proposed MPC controller is optimized with the proposed PSO algorithm using the parameters given in table 5.2. The optimization is done for multiple longitudinal speeds (v_x (m/s) $\in [3, 27]$) and reference lateral positions (y_{ref} (m) $\in [-15, 15]$). The adaptive MPC denoted (AMPC) has been tested against the pure pursuit controller (P.P) and the standard MPC (tuned by trial and error) for three scenarios:

1. Sc_1 consists of a double lane change with constant longitudinal velocity $v_x = 9$ m/s subject to wind gust as external disturbance (Fig. 5.4c).
2. Sc_2 is a double lane change with varying longitudinal velocity (Fig. 5.4a) where the AMPC is adapted to both trajectory and velocity profile subject to wind gust (Fig. 5.4c).
3. Sc_3 where the AMPC is tested for a general trajectory with varying longitudinal velocity (Fig. 5.4b) subject to wind disturbance (Fig. 5.4c).

The parameters of the dynamic model (5.1) and the MPC controller are listed in table 5.3. The results of (Sc_1) show that the three controllers are able to track the double lane change trajectory. However, the proposed AMPC outperforms the other two controllers where the sum of total MSE errors results in $e_1 = 0.097$ compared

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 5.4: (a) Velocity profile for Sc_2 , (b) Velocity profile for Sc_3 , (c) Wind disturbance profile.

to $e_2 = 0.422$ and $e_3 = 0.482$ for the standard MPC and pure pursuit controllers, respectively. Fig. 5.5 compares the tracking performance ($Y_{position}$), the steering angles (δ_f) and the heading rates ($\dot{\psi}$) for the three controllers.

Table 5.3: MPC and dynamic model parameters.

Parameter	Interpretation	Value
m	Vehicle mass	1575 (kg)
I_z	Inertia moment	2875(kg.m ²)
l_f	Front axle to CG	1.2(m)
l_r	Rear axle to CG	1.6(m)
C_f	Front cornering stiffness	19000(N/rad)
C_r	Rear cornering stiffness	33000(N/rad)
T	Sampling time	0.1(s)
N_p	Prediction horizon	45
N_c	Control horizon	15
$\Delta u_{max/min}$	Control increment constraints	$\pm \frac{\pi}{12}$ (rad)
$u_{max/min}$	Control constraints	$\pm \frac{\pi}{6}$ (rad)
R	Control magnitude weight	0.01
Q_y	Tracking precision weight	10
N	Number of Laguerre terms	5
α	Laguerre scale factor	0.75

On the other hand, the P.P controller could not perform the double lane change of (Sc_2), while the proposed AMPC tracked the trajectory significantly better than the standard MPC. Their respective MSE values result in $e_1 = 0.124$ against $e_2 = 0.489$. Fig. 5.6 shows the position tracking performance, the control signals, and the heading rates. The results for (Sc_3) confirm the better tracking ability of the proposed AMPC.

Fig 5.7 shows the tracking performance for a constant velocity $v_x = 11$ m/s. The

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 5.5: (a) Path tracking, (b) Control signal, (c) Heading rate for S_{C_1} .

MSE values are $e_1 = 10.79$, $e_2 = 21.234$, and $e_3 = 76.639$ for the AMPC, MPC, and P.P respectively.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 5.6: (a) Path tracking, (b) Control signal, (c) Heading rate for S_{C_2} .

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 5.7: (a) Path tracking, (b) Control signal, (c) Heading rate for S_{C_3} with constant velocity.

In Fig. 5.8, the same trajectory is simulated with a varying velocity profile (Fig. 5.4b). The performance of AMPC is much improved compared to the standard MPC, although both are able to track the trajectory with the respective MSE values of $e_1 = 7.219$ and $e_2 = 25.079$.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 5.8: (a) Path tracking, (b) Control signal, (c) Heading rate for S_{c_3} with varying velocity.

Fig. 5.9 shows the corresponding parameter adaptation. Generally speaking, the values of prediction and control horizons tend to increase whenever the driving conditions become more challenging such as for high wind disturbances. Similarly, the values for Q R matrices change with regard to the tracking error. For instance, higher tracking errors lead to increased Q values.

(a)

(b)

Figure 5.9: Adaptation of (a) MPC parameters, (b) Q & R for S_{c3} with varying velocity.

For the same trajectory and velocity profile, the lateral wind disturbance profile shown in Fig. 5.4c is applied to the high-fidelity vehicle model to verify the controller robustness. The simulation results (Fig. 5.10) show that at certain wind speeds, the standard MPC is not able to reject the external disturbance, and its performance deteriorates and diverges. On the other hand, the proposed AMPC still manages to track the trajectory despite the introduced disturbances. This is due to its adaptive

feature with the optimized parameters which allows the AMPC to overcome the perturbations.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 5.10: (a) Path tracking, (b) Control signal, (c) Heading rate for S_{c_3} under wind disturbance.

5.5 MPC Adaptation with Neural Networks

After the offline optimization phase with PSO, a data set of optimal MPC parameters is generated. In the first approach, four feed-forward neural networks are used to learn the optimal MPC parameters for the sake of online adaptation. The proposed neural networks consist of four layers; the first layer contains the same four inputs (see Fig. 5.11), the first hidden layer consists of 16 neurons, the second hidden layer contains 8 hidden neurons, and the output layer corresponds to one of the four MPC parameters: N_p , N_c , Q , and R . The Sigmoid activation function is used for the hidden layers and the ReLU function is used for the output layer since this is a regression problem for positive values only. The loss function used for the back-propagation is the MSE along with the gradient decent algorithm with momentum. The forward pass in the neural network is governed by equations (5.30-5.32):

$$H_j^1 = f\left(\sum_{i=1}^{n+1} w_{ij}^1 x_i\right), \text{ for } j = 1, \dots, n_{h1} \quad (5.30)$$

$$H_j^2 = f\left(\sum_{i=1}^{n+1} w_{ij}^{h1} x_i\right), \text{ for } j = 1, \dots, n_{h2} \quad (5.31)$$

$$O_j = g\left(\sum_{i=1}^{n+1} w_i^{h2} x_i\right) \quad (5.32)$$

where f and g are the Sigmoid and ReLU functions respectively, w_{ij} and x_i are the respective layer weights and inputs. The training is carried out for 1000 epochs using a data set of 6400 samples.

Figure 5.11: Neural network for MPC adaptation

5.6 MPC Adaptation with ANFIS

The ANFIS tool is used in the second approach to learn the data of MPC optimal parameters in order to achieve online adaptation. Adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference systems are a hybrid AI technique that combines fuzzy logic and artificial neural networks to learn a mapping from input-output data [167]. The general architecture of an ANFIS system, illustrated in Fig. 5.12, is composed of the following:

Figure 5.12: General architecture of ANFIS

- Layer 1: the fuzzification layer obtains fuzzy clusters from the input data by using membership functions as given below:

$$O_i^1 = \mu_{A_i}(x) \quad (5.33)$$

with x being the input to node i , and A_i the linguistic label of the node function. O_i^1 is the membership function.

- Layer 2: the rule layer computes the strengths by multiplying the membership values coming from the fuzzification layer:

$$\omega_i = \mu_{A_i}(x) \times \mu_{B_i}(y) \quad (5.34)$$

- Layer 3: the normalization layer computes the normalized strengths that belong to each rule by applying the following formula:

$$\bar{\omega}_i = \frac{\omega_i}{\sum_i^n \omega_i} \quad (5.35)$$

where $\bar{\omega}_i$ is the normalized strength and n is the number of nodes.

- Layer 4: the diffuzification layer calculates the weighted values of rules through first-order polynomials:

$$\bar{\omega}_i f_i = \bar{\omega}_i(p_i x + q_i y + r_i) \quad (5.36)$$

with f_i being the polynomial composed of the parameter set $\{p_i, q_i, r_i\}$ called consequence parameters.

- Layer 5: the summation layer sums all the outputs of the diffuzification layer to obtain the ANFIS output:

$$O_i^5 = \frac{\sum_i \omega_i f_i}{\sum_i \omega_i} \quad (5.37)$$

The adaptation system consists of four ANFIS subsystems with four inputs each and one output corresponding to N_p , N_c , Q , and R . The hybrid training approach combining gradient descent with RLS algorithm is used to train the ANFIS and avoid local minima. The scattering method is used for input space partitioning since there are four inputs. Fig. 5.13 illustrates the proposed approach where v_x , v_w , μ , and y_{ref} are the longitudinal velocity, the lateral wind velocity, the road adhesion coefficient, and the reference lateral position.

Figure 5.13: ANFIS-based adaptation approach

5.7 Results and Discussion for NN/ANFIS-MPC

Both NN-MPC and ANFIS-MPC are tested against the standard MPC for a triple lane change scenario, which is often performed in multi-lane highways. The longitudinal velocity of the vehicle is varied according to Fig. 5.14a. The vehicle was exposed to wind gusts and varying road adhesion coefficients (see Figs. 5.14b and 5.14c). The resulting adaptation signals of N_c , N_p , Q , and R for the triple lane change scenario are presented in Fig. 5.15. The observed behavior of the adaptation is similar to one with the lookup table approach. Nevertheless, it is clearly seen that both NN-MPC and ANFIS-MPC perform much more adaptations of the different controller parameters since both methods are able to generalize beyond the generated data-set.

Figure 5.14: (a): Triple lane change velocity profile, (b): Lateral gust profile, (c): Road adhesion coefficient, (d): General trajectory velocity profile.

The corresponding trajectory tracking, steering angle, tracking error, and yaw rate signals are given in Fig. 5.16. As can be seen from the figures, NN-MPC has the best tracking performance with an MSE of (0.0051) compared to (0.0062) and (0.0318) for

the ANFIS-MPC and standard MPC, respectively. On the other hand, ANFIS-MPC exhibits smoother control signals but is slightly less accurate. Overall, both adaptive controllers overcome the standard MPC and are much more robust and adaptive to wind disturbance and changing road conditions.

Figure 5.15: ANFIS and NN adaptation signals ((a): N_c and N_p , (b): Q and R).

Figure 5.16: Triple lane change ((a): Trajectory tracking, (b): Tracking error, (c): Steering command, (d): Vehicle yaw rate).

Furthermore, the controllers are tested for a general trajectory where the velocity profile is given in Fig. 5.14d. Wind gust, road adhesion coefficient and N_c , N_p , Q ,

and R adaptation signals are shown in Fig. 5.17, respectively. The corresponding results in Fig. 5.18 show a similar performance to the previous test. The NN-MPC and ANFIS-MPC proved higher tracking accuracy, better disturbance rejection, and are more adaptive compared to regular MPC. Similarly, NN-MPC was slightly more accurate in this test with an MSE of (0.132) compared to (0.1349) and (0.5896) for ANFIS-MPC and standard MPC, respectively. Contrary to NN-MPC, the main drawback of ANFIS-MPC is the curse of dimensionality. The latter is due to the exploding number of input membership functions, which makes such an approach very demanding in terms of computational power and less practical for real-time applications.

Figure 5.17: (a): Lateral gust profile, (b): Road adhesion coefficient, (c): N_c/N_p adaptation, (d): Q/R adaptation.

Figure 5.18: General trajectory ((a): Trajectory tracking, (b): Tracking error, (c): Steering command, (d): Vehicle yaw rate).

5.8 Conclusions

This chapter addressed the lateral control task in autonomous vehicles for which adaptive MPC control is proposed using three different approaches. First, a new improved PSO algorithm is introduced to optimize and tune the MPC controller for varying working conditions, which results in a data set containing optimal MPC parameters. The MPC controller is formulated with the linearized bicycle model and Laguerre functions, and it is solved through the QP method. Parameter optimization is performed for different scenarios, and the generated optimal parameters are used for controller adaptation. In the first approach, the look-up table technique is used to adapt the MPC parameters online, which were optimized by the proposed PSO algorithm. The performance of the proposed controller was tested against the standard MPC and the pure pursuit controller using a high-fidelity vehicle model. The results demonstrated that the designed AMPC is able to perform much better tracking accuracy, especially for varying longitudinal velocities. Moreover, the AMPC

is able to handle varying working conditions and reject external disturbances. This good performance is achieved thanks to its adaptive feature and well-optimized parameters through the proposed PSO algorithm. In the second approach, an MLP neural network was designed to learn the data set of optimal MPC parameters in order to predict and adapt them online as the working conditions change. In the third approach, an ANFIS system was developed for the same task and trained using the same data set. The developed controllers NN-MPC and ANFIS-MPC were tested against the standard MPC for a triple lane change scenario and a general trajectory. Furthermore, lateral gust was introduced with varying road conditions. The proposed controllers showed improved tracking accuracy, robustness, and adaptability to disturbances and varying parameters. NN-MPC proved to be slightly more accurate while ANFIS-MPC was found to be smooth but very demanding in terms of computation. The approach of NN-MPC and ANFIS-MPC provides a better alternative to the lookup table adaptation method, and it ensures a better generalization beyond the data set of optimal MPC parameters.

Chapter 6

Combined Longitudinal and Lateral Control for Autonomous Driving

Summary

This chapter addresses the autonomous driving problem by handling the coordinated and the coupled lateral and longitudinal control of autonomous vehicles. The chapter is divided into two parts. In the first part, linear parameter varying MPC control is introduced for the path tracking task, coordinated with PSO-optimized PID for the speed tracking. For the lateral control, the LPV-MPC cost function is enhanced with exponential weight, and the MPC prediction model is adaptive where the cornering stiffness coefficients are estimated online using an RLS estimator. In the second approach, a more advanced LPV-MPC controller is proposed with an adaptive prediction model. Unlike the first approach, the second one handles the coupled lateral and longitudinal dynamics, and it is tuned via an improved GA. A feed-forward neural network is proposed to predict the cornering stiffness coefficients online from measurable parameters only. The controllers developed in both parts are assessed and compared in a challenging trajectory tracking problem under wind disturbances. The content of this chapter is based on the following papers:

- [113] Y. Kebbati, N. Ait-Oufroukh, V. Vigneron, and D. Ichalal, “Coordinated PSO-PID based longitudinal control with LPV-MPC based lateral control for autonomous vehicles,” in 2022 European Control Conference (ECC), IEEE, 2022, pp. 518–523.
- [114] Y. Kebbati, N. Ait-Oufroukh, P. Vicenc, V. Vigneron, and D. Ichalal, “Autonomous driving using GA-optimized neural network based adaptive LPV-MPC controller,” in 2022 IEEE International Conference on Networking, Sensing and Control (ICNSC), IEEE, vol. 1, 2022, pp. 1–6.

6.1 Introduction

Accurate motion control is among the most important tasks for proper autonomous driving. The latter, being divided into longitudinal control in charge of speed tracking and lateral control in charge of the steering task, can be addressed in two different ways as reported in the literature. In this regard, the literature research is divided into two categories; those who address the longitudinal and lateral control separately and then coordinate them together, and those who couple both tasks at once.

For instance, Attia *et al.* [168] developed a combined lateral and longitudinal control strategy for autonomous driving, where NMPC was used to manage lateral guidance, and the longitudinal control was based on Lyapunov theory. The control strategy achieved good results, but NMPC requires very expensive computations. Although nowadays it can be applied in real-time, it still requires expensive hardware. To address the mixed lateral and longitudinal control, Alcalá *et al.* developed in [21] a solution for trajectory tracking. Their control strategy was divided into a cascade control scheme, with an internal layer for controlling vehicle dynamics and an external one for vehicle kinematics. The same authors developed in [169] a Takagi-Sugeno based MPC (TS-MPC) for autonomous driving. They used a data-driven approach to learn a Takagi-Sugeno representation of the vehicle dynamics, which was used in MPC with MHE for achieving coupled longitudinal and lateral control. Chebly *et al.* [170] also addressed coupled lateral and longitudinal control. A multi-body formalism was used to accurately model the four-wheeled vehicle, and the control laws were developed based on the Lyapunov function, then on the immersion and invariance with the sliding mode approach. Robust speed and trajectory tracking were achieved with both methods. The controller based on immersion and invariance showed better performance than its rival since it is less model-dependent. However, the design of this type of controller is a difficult task, and its practical implementation is not guaranteed. Generally speaking, research on coupled longitudinal and lateral control is less abundant.

While the two previous chapters were related to lateral control and longitudinal control only, this chapter addresses the problem of autonomous driving using two distinct methods. The first approach in section 2 presents a combined lateral and

longitudinal control strategy to handle both tasks separately and then coordinate them simultaneously whilst preserving lateral stability. An LPV-MPC controller with an improved cost function and adaptive prediction model is developed for the steering task. For speed tracking, a PSO-PID controller is designed and coordinated with the LPV-MPC controller. The second approach in section 3 introduces a more advanced LPV-MPC controller. The latter exploits a more accurate LPV prediction model derived from the full nonlinear bicycle model, that takes into account the coupling between lateral and longitudinal dynamics. Furthermore, the controller is adaptive with a neural network that is able to predict the tire cornering stiffness coefficients from measurable parameters only. Finally, the cost function of the LPV-MPC controller is further optimized by a new improved GA.

6.2 Coordinated Lateral and Longitudinal Control

In this part of the chapter, the lateral and longitudinal control tasks are addressed separately and coordinated simultaneously to achieve combined automatic control. The vehicle dynamics are highly nonlinear where the longitudinal dynamics affect the lateral dynamics of the vehicle. To achieve coordinated lateral and longitudinal control, a nonlinear longitudinal model that accounts for nonlinear power-train and tire longitudinal dynamics is coordinated with a linear parameter varying bicycle model for the lateral dynamics.

6.2.1 Longitudinal dynamics model

In the first part of this chapter, the full control of the vehicle is achieved by coordinating both lateral and longitudinal control tasks. Therefore, the longitudinal dynamics model previously introduced in Section 4.2 is used for realizing speed control, the latter consists of the vehicle chassis, the engine, the transmission, the wheels, the tires, and the brakes.

6.2.2 Lateral dynamics model

For the lateral control task, the vehicle lateral dynamics are modeled using an LPV version of the standard bicycle model presented in Section 5.2.1. Recall that the

motion in this model accounts for translation on the y-axis and rotation around the z-axis. In this part, we consider the vehicle longitudinal velocity and the cornering stiffness coefficients to be linearly varying parameters. Thus, the corresponding affine LPV state space representation is given by:

$$\begin{cases} \dot{x} &= A(\rho)x + B(\rho)u, \\ y &= Cx. \end{cases} \quad (6.1)$$

where $X = [\dot{y} \ \psi \ \dot{\psi} \ y]^T$, $Y = [y \ \psi]^T$, and $u = \delta_f$ represent the state vector, the output vector, and the control signal, respectively. The system matrices A and B depend on an LPV scheduling vector $\rho(t) = [v_x \ \frac{c_f}{v_x} \ \frac{C_r}{v_x} \ C_f]^T$. All the parameters are bounded, and the system matrices are affine with respect to the parameters of the scheduling vector. The system matrices are defined by:

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} a_{11}(\rho) & 0 & a_{13}(\rho) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ a_{31}(\rho) & 0 & a_{33}(\rho) & 0 \\ 1 & a_{42}(\rho) & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad B = \begin{bmatrix} b_{11}(\rho) \\ 0 \\ b_{13}(\rho) \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad C = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}.$$

where the terms of A and B are defined as follows:

$$a_{11}(\rho) = -2\frac{C_f+C_r}{mv_x}, \quad a_{13}(\rho) = -v_x - \frac{l_f C_f - l_r C_r}{mv_x}, \quad a_{31}(\rho) = -2\frac{l_f C_f - l_r C_r}{I_z v_x}, \quad a_{33}(\rho) = -2\frac{C_f l_f^2 + C_r l_r^2}{I_z v_x}, \quad a_{42}(\rho) = v_x, \quad b_{11}(\rho) = 2\frac{C_f}{m}, \quad b_{13}(\rho) = 2\frac{C_f l_f}{I_z}.$$

The parameters C_f and C_r are obtained by using an RLS estimator based on the linear tire cornering stiffness equations:

$$\begin{cases} F_f &= C_f \alpha_f, \\ F_r &= C_r \alpha_r. \end{cases} \quad (6.2)$$

The RLS algorithm given in equation (6.3) uses the above-mentioned equations as a parameter identification form, where $z(k)$ is the measured value, $\phi(k)$ is a regression vector, $\theta(k)$ represents the estimated parameters, and $e(k)$ is the identification error. These are defined in equations (6.4):

$$z(k) = \phi^T(k)\theta(k) + e(k). \quad (6.3)$$

$$\begin{cases} z(k) &= [F_f \ F_r]^T, \\ \phi^T(k) &= \begin{bmatrix} \alpha_f & 0 \\ 0 & \alpha_r \end{bmatrix}, \\ \theta^T(k) &= [C_f \ C_r]^T. \end{cases} \quad (6.4)$$

The values of $z(k)$ and $\phi(k)$ are obtained from the vehicle simulator **Carsim** and are fed to the RLS estimator, but in reality, the lateral forces and side-slip angle are very hard to measure, and they are usually estimated [171, 172].

6.2.3 Controller design

The coordinated lateral and longitudinal control strategy must preserve lateral stability when performing lateral maneuvers. In this regard, both road geometry and lateral dynamics are to be considered [168]. The road information is used by the speed planner to estimate the maximum allowable longitudinal speed for the steering maneuver, the cruise speed has to be reduced in function of the curvature and must respect the following condition:

$$v_{\max} = \sqrt{\frac{g \phi_r + \mu}{k(1 - \phi_r \mu)}}. \quad (6.5)$$

with g , μ , ϕ_r , and k being the gravity, the adhesion coefficient, the camber angle, and the curvature, respectively. This criterion is used as a predictive measure to guarantee admissible speeds before initiating lateral maneuvers. However, additional criteria related to lateral dynamics must be validated, and in particular, the side slip angle (β) must obey criterion (6.6):

$$\beta \leq 10 - \frac{7v_x^2}{40}. \quad (6.6)$$

The latter can be reformulated in terms of steering angle and implemented as a constraint on the control signal. According to [20], the side slip angle can be expressed by:

$$\beta = \arctan\left(\frac{l_f \tan \delta_r + l_r \tan \delta_f}{l_r + l_f}\right). \quad (6.7)$$

where the rear wheel steering angle can be set to zero as only the front wheels are steerable ($\delta_r = 0$). Hence, using equation (6.7), criterion (6.6) can be reformulated into:

$$|\delta_f| \leq \arctan \left(\frac{(l_r + l_f) \tan(10 - \frac{7v_x^2}{40})}{l_r} \right). \quad (6.8)$$

6.2.3.1 PSO-PID control

For the speed tracking task, a PSO-optimized PID controller is proposed. The improved PSO algorithm introduced in Chapter 5, is used to optimize the PID gains $\{K_p, K_i, K_d\}$ using the full longitudinal dynamics model. The approach is illustrated in (Fig. 6.1) where the MSE is used as the fitness function of the PSO algorithm. The switch module in the figure decides whether the control signal is a braking or an acceleration command based on its sign, the switching logic sends the command either to the braking system or to the engine at a time [145].

Figure 6.1: PSO-PID approach.

6.2.3.2 LPV-MPC control

The lateral control performs the position and orientation tracking, and an LPV-MPC formulation is proposed for this task. Model (6.1), discretized using sampling time T_s , is used as the MPC prediction model, where $A_d = I + T_s A$ and $B_d = T_s B$.

$$\begin{cases} x_{k+1} &= A_d(\rho)x_k + B_d(\rho)u_k, \\ y_k &= C_d x_k. \end{cases} \quad (6.9)$$

The above-mentioned model predicts the behavior of the vehicle along the prediction horizon N_p , these predictions are used to solve the resulting optimization problem

by finding the control sequence that minimizes the error between the predicted vehicle behavior and the desired behavior. At each iteration, a new adapted instance of the LPV model is used for the MPC predictions which improves the overall prediction accuracy. Moreover, constraints are imposed on the control signal, its rate and system states to account for actuator limits and ride comfort. In addition to optimality, the possibility to handle constraints is a major advantage of model predictive control. The standard optimization problem is given in equations (6.10-6.14):

$$\min J = (Y_r - Y_p)^T Q (Y_r - Y_p) + \Delta U^T R \Delta U. \quad (6.10)$$

$$s.t : x(k+1) = A_d(\rho)x(k) + B_d(\rho)\Delta u(k). \quad (6.11)$$

$$\Delta u_{\min} \leq \Delta u(k) \leq \Delta u_{\max}. \quad (6.12)$$

$$u_{\min} \leq u(k) \leq u_{\max}. \quad (6.13)$$

$$x_{\min} \leq x(k) \leq x_{\max}. \quad (6.14)$$

where ΔU , Y_p and Y_r represent the respective control sequence, the predicted and the reference trajectories, and Q and R are the weighting matrices that penalize the tracking error and the control effort. The constraints on the control and rate of control signal ensure a comfortable ride and impose actuator limits, in addition to the lateral stability criterion given in equation (6.8). To improve the optimization, an enhanced cost function is used by adding a relaxation factor (ϵ) to avoid the infeasibility of strict constraints. An exponential weight (ξ^{-k}) is also implemented which decreases with iteration k . This decreasing weight ensures that the first control input increments are more important in the sequence [160]. Therefore, immediate actions are favored to penalize immediate tracking errors more than future tracking errors since MPC is based on the receding horizon principle. The cost function is then reformulated into equation (6.15):

$$J = \sum_{j=1}^{N_p} \xi^{-j} \|y_r(k+j|k) - y_p(k+j|k)\|_Q^2 + \sum_{j=1}^{N_c} \xi^{-j} \|\Delta u(k+j|k)\|_R^2 + \rho\epsilon^2. \quad (6.15)$$

The LPV-MPC is coded in MATLAB using Yalmip platform and solved using Gurobi optimization solver. The algorithm runs at 20Hz on a laptop with 2.6Ghz I7 10750H

and 32GB of RAM. The coordinated control strategy is implemented and tested in Matlab/Carsim co-simulations as shown in Fig. 6.2, where α_t and α_b represent the throttle and brake signals. The terms v_d , Y_{ref} , and Ψ_{ref} are the desired longitudinal velocity, the lateral position, and the heading trajectories. The desired velocity is generally obtained via a speed planner and must verify condition (6.5). The LPV-MPC and PSO parameters are tuned iteratively until the desired performance is obtained. These are given in table 6.1.

Figure 6.2: Structure of the control approach.

Table 6.1: Model parameters.

N_p	9	Q	$diag(35 \ 3.25)$	R	1.25
ρ	15	ϵ	0.5	ξ	3.5
T_s	0.1s	Δu_{\max}	$\frac{\pi}{12}$	Δu_{\min}	$-\frac{\pi}{12}$
u_{\max}	$\frac{\pi}{6}$	u_{\min}	$-\frac{\pi}{6}$	G	25
ω_{\max}	1	ω_{\min}	0.1	c_{i1}	2.2
λ_1	3	λ_2	30	c_{i2}	2.2

6.2.4 Results and discussion for the coordinated control

The proposed control strategy is evaluated for a double lane-change maneuver where the velocity varies between 50 and 65 km/h, and the vehicle is exposed to lateral and longitudinal wind disturbances. The test road is flat asphalt with an adhesion coefficient $\mu = 0.95$. For this test, the PSO optimization generated the PID triplet $\{K_p = 5.52, K_i = 0.0547, K_d = 0.469\}$. The LPV-MPC with regular cost function (6.10) is compared to the one with the enhanced cost function (6.15), they are denoted "MPC" and "E-MPC", respectively. Fig. 6.3 shows the wind speed (with variable direction), the speed tracking performance, and control signals. The results show smooth speed tracking with adequate accuracy, with an $MSE=0.0213$. Fig. 6.4 shows the lateral tracking performance, the advantage of *E-MPC* is obvious in both position and yaw tracking with smoother steering, which results in a more comfortable ride. The accuracy is measured by the MSE value for the position and orientation tracking, where *E-MPC* scored $2.118e^{-4}$ against 0.601 for *MPC* with the standard cost function. For the orientation tracking, *E-MPC* scored $1.228e^{-4}$ against $6.756e^{-4}$. The highest position tracking error of *E-MPC* does not exceed 5 cm in this test.

Figure 6.3: Wind profile, speed tracking, and control signals.

Figure 6.4: LPV-MPC tracking performance and steering control.

Furthermore, the effectiveness of *E-MPC* is verified for a general trajectory (see Fig. 6.5) with different bends and a varying velocity profile. The same road characteristics were maintained, and external wind disturbances were also applied. The PSO optimization in this test produced the PID triplet $\{K_p = 1.884, K_i = 0.048, K_d = 0.325\}$. The wind profile, speed tracking performance, and control signals are respectively shown in Fig. 6.6, where the observed performance is similar to the previous test, the tracking accuracy is indeed acceptable ($MSE=0.187$) and the controls are smooth. The respective lateral tracking performance along with the corresponding steering control are shown in Fig. 6.7. Despite the challenging trajectory and speed profile with imposed wind disturbances, the proposed LPV-MPC showed good performance overall. The latter was able to track both position and orientation with a resulting MSE of 0.32 and $6.56e^{-4}$ for position and orientation tracking, respectively.

Figure 6.5: Trajectory tracking.

Figure 6.6: Wind profile, speed tracking, and control signals.

Figure 6.7: Tracking performance and steering control.

6.3 Coupled Lateral and Longitudinal Control

6.3.1 Vehicle modeling

For the coupled control strategy, the combined kinematic and dynamic bicycle model presented in Section 3.6 is adopted as it is accurate for control design whilst being simple for real-time implementation. The full model (see Fig. 6.8) accounts for longitudinal, lateral and yaw dynamics (6.16) as well as tire forces (6.17) and heading and lateral position errors (6.18):

$$\begin{cases} \dot{v}_x &= \alpha_x + \omega v_y - \frac{1}{m}(F_{yf} \sin \delta + F_d), \\ \dot{v}_y &= \frac{1}{m}(F_{yf} \cos \delta + F_{yr}) - \omega v_x, \\ \dot{\omega} &= \frac{1}{I}(F_{yf} l_f \cos \delta - F_{yr} l_r). \end{cases} \quad (6.16)$$

$$\begin{cases} F_{yf} &= C_f \alpha_f, \\ F_{yr} &= C_r \alpha_r, \\ F_d &= \mu m g + \frac{1}{2} \rho C_d A v_x^2. \end{cases} \quad (6.17)$$

$$\begin{cases} \dot{y}_e = v_x \sin \psi_e + v_y \cos \psi_e, \\ \dot{\psi}_e = \dot{\psi} - \frac{v_x \cos \psi_e - v_y \sin \psi_e}{1 - y_e k} k. \end{cases} \quad (6.18)$$

Figure 6.8: Bicycle dynamic model with tracking error.

The parameters v_x , v_y , and $(\omega \equiv \dot{\psi})$ represent the linear longitudinal and lateral velocities and yaw rate in the body frame. $F_{y(f,r)}$ are the tire lateral forces of the front and rear wheels, respectively. F_d is the total drag force where C_d and A represent the drag coefficient and the vehicle cross-sectional area. y_e and ψ_e represent the lateral position error and the heading error with k being the road curvature. I and m are the inertia and the mass of the vehicle and $l_{(f,r)}$ are the distances between the vehicle center of gravity and the front and rear wheel axles, respectively. α_x and δ are the acceleration and steering controls, and μ and g represent the friction coefficient and the gravity. Finally, $C_{(f,r)}$ represent the respective front and rear tire cornering stiffness coefficients, and $\alpha_{(f,r)}$ are the slip angles of the front and rear wheels, with ϵ being an additional term to avoid singularities in the model. The slip angles are given by:

$$\begin{cases} \alpha_f = \delta - \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{v_y}{v_x + \epsilon} - \frac{l_f \dot{\psi}}{v_x + \epsilon} \right), \\ \alpha_r = - \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{v_y}{v_x + \epsilon} + \frac{l_r \dot{\psi}}{v_x + \epsilon} \right). \end{cases} \quad (6.19)$$

The full model can be summarized as a non-linear function of the state vector (x), input vector (u) and the road curvature (k) as follows:

$$\dot{x} = f(x, u, k). \quad (6.20)$$

where $x = [v_x \ v_y \ \omega \ y_e \ \psi_e]^T$ and $u = [\delta \ \alpha_x]^T$.

6.3.2 Controller design

The control task is achieved based on LPV-MPC approach [25], where the model presented in the previous section is reformulated in an LPV form. The model is then transformed into a state space representation where the state and control matrices are functions that depend on a scheduling vector of varying parameters. Embedding linear varying parameters into these matrices allows to capture the non-linearities of the full model providing a simple but accurate model for control design. The LPV state space formulation of the system is given by equation (6.21), based on the scheduling vector $\phi = [\delta \ v_x \ v_y \ \psi_e \ y_e \ k]^T$.

$$\dot{x} = A(\phi)x + B(\phi)u. \quad (6.21)$$

According to [25, 136], the state matrix $A(\phi)$ and control matrix $B(\phi)$ can be derived as the following:

$$A(\phi) = \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} & A_{13} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & A_{22} & A_{23} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & A_{32} & A_{33} & 0 & 0 \\ A_{41} & A_{42} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ A_{51} & A_{52} & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad B(\phi) = \begin{bmatrix} B_{11} & 1 \\ B_{21} & 0 \\ B_{31} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}.$$

where the terms of the matrices are given by:

$$\begin{aligned} A_{11} &= \frac{-\mu g}{v_x} - \frac{\rho C_d A v_x}{2m}, \quad A_{12} = \frac{C_f \sin \delta}{m v_x}, \quad A_{13} = \frac{C_f l_f \sin \delta}{m v_x} + v_y, \quad A_{22} = -\frac{C_r + C_f \cos \delta}{m v_x}, \\ A_{23} &= -\frac{C_f l_f \cos \delta - C_r l_r}{m v_x} - v_x, \quad A_{32} = -\frac{C_f l_f \cos \delta + C_r l_r}{I v_x}, \quad A_{33} = -\frac{C_f l_f^2 \cos \delta + C_r l_r^2}{I v_x}, \\ A_{41} &= \sin \psi_e, \quad A_{42} = \cos \psi_e, \quad A_{45} = v_x, \quad A_{51} = -\frac{k \cos \psi_e}{1 - y_e k}, \quad A_{52} = \frac{k \sin \psi_e}{1 - y_e k}, \\ B_{11} &= -\frac{C_f \sin \delta}{m}, \quad B_{21} = \frac{C_f \cos \delta}{m}, \quad B_{31} = \frac{C_f l_f \cos \delta}{I}. \end{aligned}$$

The LPV model, discretized with sampling time T_s , is used as the MPC prediction model. Hence, at each iteration, the scheduling vector is used to instantiate the LPV model. The parameters of the scheduling vector can be obtained from sensors, planners or previous MPC predictions. In this regard, the MPC problem can be formulated as the following constrained quadratic optimization:

$$\begin{aligned}
\min_{\Delta U_k} J_k &= \sum_{i=0}^{N_p-1} \left((r_{k+i} - x_{k+i})^T Q (r_{k+i} - x_{k+i}) + \Delta u_{k+i} R \Delta u_{k+i} \right) + x_{k+N_p}^T Q x_{k+N_p}, \\
s.t : \\
x_{k+i+1} &= x_{k+i} + A(\phi_{k+i})x_{k+i} + B(\phi_{k+i})u_{k+i}dt, \\
u_{k+i} &= u_{k+i-1} + \Delta u_{k+i}, \\
\Delta u_{min} &\leq \Delta u_k \leq \Delta u_{max}, \\
u_{min} &\leq u_k \leq u_{max}, \\
x_{min} &\leq x_k \leq x_{max}.
\end{aligned} \tag{6.22}$$

The terms x , u , and N_p are the previously defined state vector, control vector, and prediction horizon. $Q \in \mathbb{R}^{5 \times 5}$ and $R \in \mathbb{R}^{2 \times 2}$ are positive semi-definite weighting matrices that penalize the states and the control effort. r_{k+i} is the reference vector and the terms $[u_{min}, u_{max}]$, $[\Delta u_{min}, \Delta u_{max}]$, and $[x_{min}, x_{max}]$ are the upper and lower bounds on the control actions, control increments, and states, respectively.

6.3.2.1 Controller adaptation with neural network

The majority of research in the literature considers a linearized tire model, where the relation between tire force and slip angle is governed by a constant called the cornering stiffness coefficient. However, this is only valid for relatively small slip angles and not during fast and challenging maneuvers. To remedy this, we use machine learning to predict the cornering stiffness coefficients online from measurable parameters. We assume these parameters (namely, the longitudinal (v_x) and lateral (v_y) velocities, the steering angle (δ), the acceleration (α_x), and the yaw rate ($\dot{\psi}$)) are enough to capture the tire dynamics. Using this approach (see Fig. 6.9), the prediction model of the LPV-MPC is adapted online to improve the prediction capability and precision.

Figure 6.9: Adaptive LPV-MPC approach.

6.3.2.2 Controller tuning with improved GA

Manually tuning the MPC is time-consuming and may not yield the best performance. Thus, to optimize the designed LPV-MPC, we propose an improved GA to tune the weighting matrices of the quadratic cost function. The GA operations being; the selection, the crossover, and the mutation control the search capability and the quality of the solutions. These operations consist of different functions which influence the performance and optimality of the algorithm at different degrees [173]. Briefly speaking, the selection process chooses the best chromosomes to be enhanced by the crossover and mutation operations. The crossover seeks to produce high-quality solutions by mixing genetic data, while mutation introduces new genes to complement the crossover as was illustrated in Fig. 4.4. To improve the GA performance, researchers have essentially tried to enhance the genetic operations. For instance, the most common selection operations are the roulette wheel (RWS) and tournament selection (TS) [150, 173]. Similarly, crossover versions include single/multi-point, uniform, and shuffle crossover, while in mutation, one finds swap, inversion, and random resetting. Details about these methods and GA can be found in [174].

Rather than improving the operators themselves, we combine RWS and TS selection operations to improve the selection of potential genes which is a critical phase of the GA. In particular, RWS strategy provides a higher chance for good genes to

be selected, which enhances exploitation and accelerates the convergence of the algorithm. However, RWS is mainly based on the fitness value, which makes it prone to premature convergence by possibly selecting the same dominant genes every time. On the other hand, the TS method allows for controlling the selection pressure. A smaller tournament size ensures more chances for weak genes to be selected, unlike RWS. This feature retains the diversity of the search space and increases the possibility of converging to a global optimum at the expense of slower convergence. In this improved GA, both methods are used with random percentages at each iteration to increase both convergence speed and optimality by combining the advantages of both methods. Furthermore, uniform crossover has been used with mutation based on Gaussian distribution (see Algorithm 2).

Algorithm 2 Proposed genetic algorithm

Require: Gen_{max}, N_p ▷ Generations, Population Size
 $Pop \leftarrow N_p$ *Parents* ▷ Random Population
while $Generation < Gen_{max}$ **do**
 $Child \leftarrow emptyPop$ ▷ Create Child Population
 while $Child \leq full$ **do**
 $RWS \leftarrow \%_r$ ▷ Generate RWS Percentage
 $TS \leftarrow \%_t$
 if $\%_r \geq \%_t$ **then**
 $Parent1 \leftarrow RWS(Pop)$ ▷ RWS Selection
 $Parent2 \leftarrow RWS(Pop)$
 else
 $Parent1 \leftarrow TS(Pop)$ ▷ TS Selection
 $Parent2 \leftarrow TS(Pop)$
 end if
 $Child1,2 \leftarrow UCrossover(Parent1, Parent2)$ ▷ Perform Uniform Crossover
 $Child1,2 \leftarrow GMutation(Child1, Child2)$ ▷ Perform Mutation
 $Fitness \leftarrow Evaluate(Child1, Child2)$ ▷ Evaluate New Offsprings
 $Offspring \leftarrow Child1, Child2$
 end while
 $Pop \leftarrow Offspring$ ▷ Replace Population
end while
 $Solution \leftarrow Best\ fitness$ ▷ Save Best Solution

6.3.3 Results and discussion for the coupled control

For testing the proposed approach, a Renault Zoe vehicle is used. The behavior of this vehicle is simulated in Matlab using a high-fidelity nonlinear dynamic model [25] with the Pacejka formula for the lateral tire forces [24]. Model parameters are presented in table 6.3.

6.3.3.1 Learning and optimization results

The proposed GA algorithm is tested on a 5D sphere function ($f(x) = \sum_{i=1}^5 x_i^2$) as a benchmark test [175], and the resulting performance over 100 iterations is compared to GA with RWS and TS methods, respectively. Fig. 6.10 shows that the improved version is indeed faster and able to find more optimal solutions, reaching a cost value of 25.029 compared to 27.725 and 28.722 for the GA with RWS and TS respectively.

Figure 6.10: Performance of the improved GA.

Table 6.2 lists the parameters used in the GA algorithm for optimizing the weighting matrices in the cost function of the LPV-MPC controller. The fitness function is chosen as the RMSE for longitudinal velocity, heading, and lateral position tracking. The GA optimization achieved minimum RMSE scores of 0.0217, 0.0465, and 0.101 for the position, heading, and velocity tracking, respectively. The resulting weighting matrices are as follows:

$$Q = \text{diag}(0.008, 0.0007, 0.0133, 3, 0.021, 5)^T,$$

$$R = \text{diag}(0.0337, 0.0117)^T.$$

Table 6.2: GA parameters.

Parameter	Name	Value
Gen	Number of generations	15
N_P	Size of population	20
O_p	Percentage of offsprings	0.8
ζ	Selection pressure	0.75
μ_r	Mutation rate	0.3
σ	Mutation variance	0.15

As discussed in Section 6.3.2.1, the cornering stiffness coefficient is learned from data. `Carsim` is used to perform multiple driving scenarios and collect data for training. Then, a deep neural network consisting of an input layer with 5 neurons, four hidden layers with 16, 28, 16, and 9 hidden neurons respectively, and an output layer with two neurons corresponding to the rear and front wheel cornering stiffness coefficients. The depth, width, and hyperparameters of the neural network are tuned by trial and error. The Sigmoid function is used for activation in all the layers except the output layer which uses Identity as this is a regression task. The model is built using Keras-Tensorflow and trained for 2500 epochs with a batch size of 64. The whole data set consists of 10752 data points split into 75% for training and 25% for validation. Adam was used as the optimizer with a learning rate of 5×10^{-4} . The training curve of the neural network in Fig. 6.11a shows that the model is able to learn the data without over-fitting. The final validation loss value is minimized to 0.226, while the training loss reached 0.196. The evaluation of the model on the training and the test data sets achieved an R_2 score of 0.88 and 0.78, respectively. Fig. 6.11b, 6.11c shows the accuracy of the model by comparing the predicted values to the expected ones over a few data points of the test data set.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 6.11: (a) Learning curve, (b) Data fitting, (c) Prediction vs true value.

6.3.3.2 Control results

The proposed controller is coded in `Yalmip` platform and solved using `Gurobi` solver. The algorithm runs at 95Hz on a laptop with 3.2Ghz Ryzen7 5800H and 32gb of RAM. The LPV-MPC is implemented and evaluated in `Matlab` simulations using the high-fidelity nonlinear dynamic model [25] with the Pacejka formula for the lateral tire forces [24]. Table 6.3 presents the MPC parameters. The evaluation is performed for a general trajectory and speed profile under wind disturbances varying between 25 and 50 m/s (see Fig. 6.12). Furthermore, it is compared to the LPV-MPC coordinated with PSO-optimized PID that was developed in the first part of this chapter, the latter is denoted *LMPC*. Such comparison shows the significance of accurate modeling and of the coupling of lateral and longitudinal dynamics for controller design. Fig. 6.12 shows the velocity profile varying between 5 and 21 m/s. Overall, the LPV-MPC is more accurate in speed tracking where the MSE is evaluated at 0.0476 compared to 0.187 for the PSO-PID whose parameters were already optimized. In addition, PSO-PID is more aggressive as it cannot handle constraints.

Table 6.3: MPC and model parameters.

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
m	1575 (kg)	C_d	0.29
I_z	2875 (kg.m ²)	A	1.6 (m ²)
l_f	1.2 (m)	$y_{e_{max/min}}$	0.3 (m)
l_r	1.6 (m)	$u_{max/min}$	$\pm \frac{\pi}{6}$ (rad)
ρ	1.225 (kgm ³)	$\Delta u_{max/min}$	$\pm \frac{\pi}{12}$ (rad)
μ	0.95	N_p	10
g	9.81 (m/s ²)	T_s	0.033 (s)

The results in Fig. 6.13 show that the proposed LPV-MPC is indeed superior to LMPC in terms of tracking accuracy. In fact, the obtained MSE score is as low as 0.02 compared to 0.32 for LMPC, which means the LPV-MPC tracking is almost ideal. The zoomed regions of the figure illustrate the significant difference in track-

ing accuracy, which is partly due to the different models used to develop the MPC controller.

Figure 6.12: Wind velocity and velocity tracking performance.

Figure 6.13: Trajectory tracking.

Figure 6.14: Steering, acceleration, and lateral velocity signals.

Figure 6.15: Tracking performance.

Figure 6.16: MPC computation time.

Fig. 6.14 shows the steering and acceleration controls, and the lateral velocity of the vehicle. The tracking errors for longitudinal velocity, heading, and lateral position are respectively shown in Fig. 6.15. The maximum velocity tracking error does not exceed 0.087 m/s , while the heading and position tracking errors are kept below 11° and 8 cm respectively. Finally, Fig. 6.16 presents the computation time required by the LPV-MPC for solving the optimization problem. The mean computation time is evaluated at (0.0113 s) which is very suitable for real-time applications.

6.4 Conclusions

In this chapter, the problem of lateral and longitudinal control is addressed to achieve autonomous driving. The first part of the chapter dealt with the coordination of separate lateral and longitudinal control by developing an LPV-MPC controller for the lateral dynamics and a PSO-optimized PID controller for the longitudinal dynamics and then coordinating both strategies simultaneously. Exponential weight with a relaxation factor has been introduced to enhance the cost function for the LPV-MPC controller whose prediction model was based on the single-track linear bicycle model. Furthermore, the tire cornering stiffness coefficients were estimated online by

a recursive estimator which allowed the prediction model to be adaptive and more accurate. The proposed controllers were validated in `Matlab/Carsim` co-simulations for a double lane-change scenario and a general trajectory tracking problem. The results showed satisfactory performance for both lateral and longitudinal tracking, while being relatively robust against wind disturbances. The second part addressed the coupled lateral and longitudinal control for autonomous driving by developing an adaptive LPV-MPC controller. In this part, the prediction model was derived as an LPV version from the nonlinear full vehicle model. Furthermore, a data-driven approach based on Machine Learning has been proposed to predict the tire cornering stiffness coefficients online from measurable parameters only, and then adapt the LPV-MPC prediction model for more accurate predictions. In addition, An improved GA has been proposed to optimize the cost function of the LPV-MPC controller. The proposed control strategy has been tested on the same trajectory as part one, and the performance of both speed and trajectory tracking has been compared with the first approach. The obtained results proved that the LPV-MPC controller introduced in the second part has superior performance and ensures higher speed and trajectory tracking accuracy.

Chapter 7

Learning-based MPC with MHE State Estimation for Autonomous Racing

Summary

In this chapter, a more challenging application of autonomous driving is addressed, namely autonomous racing. First of all, the optimal racing problem is solved by an NMPC-based off-line trajectory planner, that computes the best trajectory while considering the physical limits of the vehicle and track boundaries. Then, a real-time NMPC is introduced to achieve accurate race line tracking. For fast computations, the NMPC is developed based on an extended kinematic bicycle model that takes into account the vehicle's longitudinal dynamics. The proposed controller is coupled with an MHE that estimates vehicle states from noisy measurements in real time. Furthermore, the developed controller is enhanced with a learning extension based on Gaussian process regression. The learning extension aims to compensate for the mismatch between the NMPC prediction model and real vehicle dynamics, which allows for better racing capabilities. The controller, state estimator, race line planner, and learning extension are evaluated and compared for two challenging race tracks. The content of this chapter is based on the following paper:

- [176] Y. Kebbati, R. Andreas, N. Ait-Oufroukh, D. Ichalal, and V. Vigneron, "Learning-based model predictive control with moving horizon state estimation for autonomous racing," *International Journal of Control*, May 2023.
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7.1 Introduction

Self-driving vehicles have seen tangible advancements in recent years, especially in the fields of decision-making, planning, and control. Many Advanced Driver Assistance Systems (ADAS) such as cruise control, emergency braking, and lane keeping have been deployed in modern commercial vehicles for quite some time. However,

challenging driving situations call for more sophisticated control algorithms. Full driving autonomy requires simultaneous lateral and longitudinal vehicle control, and the driving task can range from simple highway and urban driving to more complex driving like autonomous racing. In such applications, the objective is to go as fast as possible where the vehicle racing autonomously has to operate at its handling limits, leading to a more challenging control problem. Knowing the physical limits of the vehicle is important for such driving scenarios, which implies the necessity of an accurate model. Autonomous racing, as a sub-field of autonomous driving, has recently attracted considerable research attention [11, 30, 32, 34] and [25]. In this regard, the literature distinguishes MPC by its optimal performance and ability to handle autonomous driving, since it allows to accurately predict the required driving behavior even in challenging situations. Furthermore, MPC is distinguished by its unique features such as imposing safety and physical constraints and handling MIMO systems, in addition to its predictive nature that can foresee the vehicle’s behavior beforehand. The latter suffers a compromise between precision and fast computation [25, 33], such that using complex nonlinear models yields accurate results at the expense of slow computations which is unsuitable for real-time applications.

In addition to control, race line planning is a very important task in autonomous racing. Several techniques exist for this purpose, sampling-based planning algorithms tend to quickly find feasible trajectories, but they may not be optimal. These are divided into graph-based methods like the Dijkstra, and A* algorithms and incremental search algorithms like the famous RRT and RRT* [116]. RRT has been investigated by Hwan et al. [119] to generate a time-optimal trajectory for a 180° curve. Alternatively, optimization-based methods such as optimal control can find the fastest race line while taking into account the physical limits of the vehicle. Papers [34], and [32] proposed a one-level approach combining control and planning in a single optimization problem. Alcalá et al. [25] proposed using two separate layers, one for control and another layer for planning, claiming that one-level methods complicate the control problem and may require more computation resources. In this chapter, we propose a complete setup for autonomous racing using an NMPC with a kinematic model that takes into account the longitudinal dynamics. In addition, an MHE is designed for real-time state estimation to complement the control layer. To generate

the complete optimal track race line we use an offline NMPC with a high-fidelity non-linear dynamic model. The main contribution in this chapter is the combination of online control and state estimation, in addition to optimal offline trajectory planning and a learning extension to further improve the control performance.

7.2 Vehicle Modeling

The vehicle in question is a 1/10 scale electric race car modeled as one rigid body with mass m and inertia I_z . A single-track bicycle model can be formulated assuming the car is symmetrical and considering in-plane motions only (see Fig. 7.1). This modeling approach is one of the most common ways to model racing cars [11, 30, 32], where the state vector is defined as $\check{x} = [X, Y, \psi, v_x, v_y, \omega]^T$, and the control input is defined as $u = [\delta, D]^T$. The model is governed by 6 ordinary differential equations (ODEs).

$$\dot{X} = v_x \cos(\psi) - v_y \sin(\psi), \quad (7.1a)$$

$$\dot{Y} = v_x \sin(\psi) + v_y \cos(\psi), \quad (7.1b)$$

$$\dot{\psi} = \omega, \quad (7.1c)$$

$$\dot{v}_x = \frac{F_{x,r} - F_{y,f} \sin(\delta) + mv_y \omega}{m}, \quad (7.1d)$$

$$\dot{v}_y = \frac{F_{y,r} - F_{y,f} \cos(\delta) - mv_x \omega}{m}, \quad (7.1e)$$

$$\dot{\omega} = \frac{F_{y,f} l_f \cos(\delta) - F_{y,r} l_r}{I_z}. \quad (7.1f)$$

Recall that v_x , v_y , and ω are linear longitudinal, linear lateral, and angular velocities respectively. X , Y , and ψ are the respective global coordinates of the car's position and its orientation, while the inputs to the model are the front steering angle δ and the duty cycle of the motor D . Furthermore, the tire-road interactions are modeled using the simplified Pacejka tire model discussed in Section 3.5.2, which is considered realistic enough for high-speed maneuvers at handling limits.

Figure 7.1: Bicycle model.

$$F_{y,f} = D_f \sin(C_f \arctan(B_f \alpha_f)), \quad (7.2a)$$

$$F_{y,r} = D_r \sin(C_r \arctan(B_r \alpha_r)), \quad (7.2b)$$

$$\alpha_f = \delta - \arctan\left(\frac{v_y + l_f \dot{\psi}}{v_x}\right), \quad (7.2c)$$

$$\alpha_r = \arctan\left(\frac{l_r \dot{\psi} - v_y}{v_x}\right). \quad (7.2d)$$

As discussed previously, equations (7.2a-7.2b) define the tire lateral forces where B , C , and D determine the semi-empirical curve. The subscripts (f,r) refer to the front and rear wheels, respectively. The term α is the side-slip angle of the corresponding (front/rear) wheel, and l is the distance between the vehicle's CG and corresponding wheel's axle. Finally, the rear traction force is modeled by a simplified representation of a DC motor with air drag and rolling resistance. Parameters C_r , C_d , and $C_{m(1,2)}$ are rolling resistance, drag, and motor coefficients, respectively:

$$F_{x,r} = (C_{m1} - C_{m2}v_x)D - C_r - C_d v_x^2. \quad (7.3)$$

The model described above is very accurate with high fidelity, but expensive in terms of computation for real-time applications. Hence, its use in this chapter is for simulating vehicle behavior and validating the controller. At this stage and to simplify control design under a low computation burden, we make use of a low-order vehicle model that efficiently runs within real-time optimization. For this model, load changes, pitch and roll dynamics, and road tire interactions are neglected resulting in a slip-free model summarized in equations (7.4) [33]:

$$\dot{X} = v \cos(\psi + g_1 \delta), \quad (7.4a)$$

$$\dot{Y} = v \sin(\psi + g_1 \delta), \quad (7.4b)$$

$$\dot{\psi} = v \delta g_2, \quad (7.4c)$$

$$\dot{v} = (C_{m_1} - C_{m_2} v) D - C_{r_2} v^2 - C_{r_1} - (v \delta)^2 C_1^2 C_2. \quad (7.4d)$$

where g_1 and g_2 are geometric parameters properly identified along with the other parameters in table 7.1. The velocity of the car is approximated, assuming a small steering angle δ , as follows [33]:

$$v_x \approx v, \quad v_y \approx v g_1 \delta.$$

Thus, the full velocity of the vehicle is obtained as $v^2 = v_x^2 + v_y^2$. Observing model (7.4), one can notice that equations (7.4a-7.4c) define the vehicle kinematics, while equation (7.4d) represents the longitudinal dynamics that depend on the duty cycle D and the resistive force.

7.3 Control Strategy

7.3.1 NMPC controller

To ensure accurate trajectory tracking, an NMPC controller is formulated to handle both steering and acceleration controls. The NMPC controller uses the vehicle's model (7.4), discretized by the sampling time T_s , to predict the vehicle's behavior over a certain prediction horizon N . Then, it generates a sequence of optimal control actions to minimize tracking errors by solving a constrained NLP. In this regard, the NLP problem reads as follows:

Table 7.1: Modeling parameters.

Parameter	Unit	Value	Parameter	Unit	Value
m	kg	1.98	B_f	—	29.5
I_z	kg.m ²	0.1217	C_f	—	0.087
l_f	m	0.125	D_f	—	42.53
l_r	m	0.125	B_r	—	26.97
C_{m_1}	m/s ²	12	C_r	—	0.163
C_{m_2}	s ⁻¹	2.17	D_f	—	161.59
C_{r_1}	m ⁻¹	0.6	g_1	—	$(l_r/(l_r + l_f))$
C_{r_2}	m/s ²	0.1	g_2	m ⁻¹	$(1/(l_r + l_f))$

$$\min_{\Delta U_k} \sum_{k=1}^N \{ \|r_k - x_k\|_Q^2 + \|\Delta u_k\|_R^2 \} + \|x_{k+N+1}\|_P^2. \quad (7.5a)$$

$$s.t : x_{k+1} = f(x_k, u_k), \quad (7.5b)$$

$$u_k = u_{k-1} + \Delta u_k, \quad (7.5c)$$

$$u_k \in U, \quad (7.5d)$$

$$\Delta u_k \in \Delta U, \quad (7.5e)$$

$$x_k \in X, \quad (7.5f)$$

$$x_{k_{\{1,2\}}} \leq B_R(k), \quad (7.5g)$$

$$B_L(k) \leq x_{k_{\{1,2\}}}. \quad (7.5h)$$

The states and control inputs are defined as $x = [X, Y, \psi, v]^T$, $u = [\delta, D]^T$, with N being the prediction horizon. The positive semi-definite diagonal matrices Q and R penalize the states and the control effort, and r_k is the reference trajectory with global X and Y coordinates. The last term of (7.5a) is the terminal cost used to increase stability. As demonstrated in [177], adding a terminal cost to the MPC formulation and using a sufficiently long prediction horizon ensures MPC stability without the need for terminal constraints. The system dynamics are defined in (7.5b), while (7.5d-7.5f) represent the constraints on the control inputs, on their rates, and on the states, respectively. To keep the vehicle inside the circuit, hard constraints (7.5g,7.5h) are

imposed on the vehicle’s position (X and Y coordinates), where the terms B_L and B_R are 3^{rd} order spline approximations of the circuit’s boundaries.

Autonomous racing is a complicated task in which the vehicle must operate at the limit of its handling capabilities. Moreover, the trajectory to be followed needs to be a time-optimal race line that allows the vehicle to go as fast as possible while operating at its dynamic limits, meaning that the vehicle is exposed to higher lateral and longitudinal accelerations compared to normal driving. The planning of such a race line is explained in the following subsection.

7.3.2 Race line planning

The objective of path planning for racing is to generate an optimal race line that minimizes lap time, this time optimality can be seen as the maximum feasible progress along the racing track. The latter is achieved by exploiting spatial coordinates instead of time domain coordinates, meaning that vehicle properties such as positions, angles and so on are represented in the spatial domain. To generate the race line, an offline NMPC with the previously introduced full vehicle model (7.1) is formulated in the spatial domain where the center line of the circuit is used as a measure of progress. The key point here is to use a long prediction horizon and low weights on the tracking error to maximize progress at the expense of tracking accuracy. Using the full vehicle dynamic model with a long prediction horizon requires very long computations, which is why this phase is computed offline to generate the race line. The reference path is parameterized, using offline-fitted polynomial interpolation, by the arc length $\theta \in [0, L]$ with L being the total length. Hence, any known point of the center-line $(X_{ref}(\theta), Y_{ref}(\theta))$ can be evaluated using the aforementioned parameterization (see Fig. 7.1). At this point, one can minimize the deviation of the car’s position from the reference point $(X_{ref}(\theta), Y_{ref}(\theta))$ by using a projection operator as follows [32]:

$$\nabla(X, Y) \triangleq \min_{\theta} [(X - X_{ref}(\theta))^2 + (Y - Y_{ref}(\theta))^2]. \quad (7.6)$$

Using the definition $\nabla \triangleq \nabla(X, Y)$, the orthogonal distance between the car and the reference path is given by the following expression:

$$e(X, Y, \nabla) \triangleq \sin(\phi(\nabla))(X - X_{ref}(\nabla)) - \cos(\phi(\nabla))(Y - Y_{ref}(\nabla)). \quad (7.7)$$

where:

$$\phi(\cdot) \triangleq \arctan \left\{ \frac{\partial Y_{ref}(\cdot)}{\partial X_{ref}(\cdot)} \right\}. \quad (7.8)$$

The objective now becomes a matter of minimizing the orthogonal distance $e(X, Y, \nabla)$ while maximizing the racing progress represented by the projection ∇ over a long prediction horizon N_p . Hence, the optimization problem can be posed as follows:

$$\min_{u, \theta} \sum_{k=1}^{N_p} \{ \|e(X_k, Y_k, \nabla)\|_q^2 \} - r \nabla_{N_p}. \quad (7.9a)$$

$$s.t : x_{k+1} = g(x_k, u_k), \quad (7.9b)$$

$$u_k \in U, \quad (7.9c)$$

$$x_k \in X, \quad (7.9d)$$

$$B_L(k) \leq x_{k_{\{1,2\}}} \leq B_R(k). \quad (7.9e)$$

The trade-off between progress and reference tracking is obtained through the weights q and r . Equation (7.9b) is the discrete version of the full vehicle dynamics given in (7.1) and the rest is the same as in problem (7.5). Notice that the objective function in (7.9a) depends on the projection operator (7.6) and is not real-time feasible. Hence, this part is computed offline to generate the race line, which will be used in the real-time control problem (7.5) with the simplified model (7.4).

7.3.3 Moving horizon estimation

The goal of the MHE is to predict the dynamic states of the vehicle's model for future control iterations. This is achieved by solving a constrained optimization problem online over a fixed estimation horizon. Autonomous vehicles are equipped with a variety of sensors that can measure most of the dynamic states of the vehicle. Still, information from cheap sensors is always noisy and contains inaccuracies, which calls for rigorous post-processing. Hence, MHE becomes a convenient solution since it makes use of past measurements to produce accurate estimates of the states.

The goal of the moving horizon estimator MHE is to predict the dynamic states of the vehicle for future control iterations. This is achieved by solving a constrained optimization problem online over a fixed estimation horizon. Although the Kalman filter is a mature and well-known state estimation technique, it usually is limited to linear unconstrained systems and cannot handle nonlinear constrained problems. The obvious advantage of MHE is its ability to optimally handle constrained nonlinear systems using a finite horizon of measurement data, which allows it to bind the optimization problem. MHE can be seen as the dual problem of the NMPC controller discussed in Section 7.3.1, where at each iteration k , the MHE acquires past measurements over the estimation horizon N_e and then finds the states' trajectory that best fits the considered window of measurements (as illustrated in Fig. 7.2), which is achieved by solving the following NLP problem:

Figure 7.2: Moving horizon estimation process.

$$\min_{x,u} \sum_{i=k-N_e}^k \|\tilde{y}(i) - h(x(i))\|_V^2 + \sum_{i=k-N_e}^{k-1} \|\tilde{u}(i) - u(i)\|_W^2. \quad (7.10a)$$

$$s.t. : x(i+1) = f(x(i), u(i) + \omega_u(i)), \quad (7.10b)$$

$$y(i) = h(x(i)) + \omega_y(i), \quad (7.10c)$$

$$u_k \in U, \quad (7.10d)$$

$$x_k \in X. \quad (7.10e)$$

with equation 7.10b being the state propagation model (same system dynamics introduced in (7.4)), and 7.10c representing the sensor measurement model. Here $\omega_y \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_y)$ and $\omega_u \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_u)$ represent the output and input measurement noise with their respective covariance matrices σ_y and σ_u . \tilde{y} and \tilde{u} are the measured system outputs and inputs, and $\|\cdot\|_{\{V,W\}}$ represents the Euclidean norm with V and W being positive-definite weighting matrices .

7.3.4 Learning extension

The purpose of the learning extension is to improve MPC predictions to enable the vehicle to drive more aggressively and increase its racing speed. Hence, the aim is to try to find the mismatch between the high-fidelity model (7.1) and the model used in the MPC design (7.4), which can be expressed as the error between predicted states and actual vehicle states. Let us define $F_{vehicle}$ as the high-fidelity model, and F_{mpc} as the MPC prediction model. The model mismatch takes into account the four common states between the two models and has the following form: $[e_X, e_Y, e_\psi, e_v, 0, 0]^T$. Therefore, a Gaussian process regressor is learned for each faulty state using recorded data from previous racing laps with the regular NMPC controller.

Gaussian processes are a collection of random variables having a joint Gaussian distribution. Consider noisy observations denoted by o that are coming from a model function $f : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ through a Gaussian noise model: $o = f(x) + \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_n^2)$ with $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$. The Gaussian process of o is defined by the mean function $\mu(x)$ and the covariance function $k(x, x')$ [31].

$$\begin{aligned} \mu(x, \zeta) &= \mathbb{E}[f(x)], \\ k(x, x', \zeta) &= \mathbb{E}[(f(x) - \mu(x))(f(x') - \mu(x')))] + \sigma_n^2 \delta(x, x'). \end{aligned} \tag{7.11}$$

the term $\delta(x, x')$ is known as the Konecker delta function, and ζ is a hyperparameter vector that parameterizes the mean and covariance functions.

The training data are obtained from both $F_{vehicle}$ and F_{mpc} in addition to the corresponding control inputs. The model mismatch can be expressed as:

$$F_{error}(x_k, u_k) = F_{vehicle\{1:4\}}(x_{k+1}) - F_{mpc}(x_k, u_k). \tag{7.12}$$

where $k \in \{0, 1, \dots, T\}$ and T is the length of the racing lap. The learned Gaussian process regressors are of the following form:

$$e_i = \mathcal{GP}(X, Y, \psi, v, \delta, D), \quad i \in \{X, Y, \psi, v\} \quad (7.13)$$

where i corresponds to the faulty states defined as $e_Y \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu_Y, \sigma_Y)$, $e_X \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu_X, \sigma_X)$, $e_\psi \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu_\psi, \sigma_\psi)$ and $e_v \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu_v, \sigma_v)$. Each μ and σ represent the mean and variance of the corresponding distribution (\sim). The learned model is used for MPC predictions and can be obtained by adding the prediction model mismatch to model 7.4:

$$F_{learned}(x_k, u_k) = F_{mpc}(x_k, u_k) + F_{error}(x_k, u_k) \quad (7.14)$$

The overall approach with MPC controller, MHE estimator, and \mathcal{GP} learning extension is shown in Fig. 7.3.

Figure 7.3: Overall control approach.

7.4 Results and Discussion

7.4.1 Estimation and \mathcal{GP} learning results

The three optimization problems, MPC for control and planning and MHE for state estimation, are coded in `Matlab` using `CASADI` framework and solved with `IPOPT`. Both the MHE estimator and the NMPC controller run at an average frequency of $130Hz$ on a laptop with `Ryzen 7 5800H` CPU and `32GB` of RAM. Note that this

execution time is more than enough for real-time implementation. The NMPC uses state estimates obtained by the MHE to compute the necessary control actions for tracking the planned racing trajectory. The MHE and NMPC weighting matrices are found by iterative tuning until the desired performance is obtained, they are given along with the measurement noise covariance matrices as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 Q &= \text{diag}(0.015, 0.015, 0, 0) \\
 R &= \text{diag}(0.003, 0.0025) \\
 \sigma_y &= \text{diag}(0.05, 0.05, 0.035, 0.1) \\
 \sigma_u &= \text{diag}(0.2, 0.035)
 \end{aligned} \tag{7.15}$$

The parameters used for implementation are all properly listed in table 7.2. Observing Fig. 7.4, one can notice that despite the low order model implemented for MHE, the latter was able to estimate the true noiseless states from the noisy state and control measurements (see Fig. 7.5).

Table 7.2: Implementation parameters.

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
N_e	6	N_p	65
V	σ_y^{-1}	q	0.025
W	σ_u^{-1}	r	1.25
δ_{max}	$\frac{\pi}{6}$	N	16
δ_{min}	$-\frac{\pi}{6}$	T_s	20ms
D_{max}	1	D_{min}	-1

The \mathcal{GP} regressors for the faulty states are programmed using sci-kit learn with a combination of radial basis function and constant kernels. The training for the whole lap takes about 15 to 20 seconds and results in an R2 score of about 98% for the training data and between 65% and 78% for the test data, which contains 15% of the whole data set. Fig. 7.6 shows the \mathcal{GP} predictions and 95% confidence intervals for the four model mismatch states on the test data. As can be seen, the \mathcal{GP} regressors do well at predicting the model mismatch, the highest uncertainties in predictions generally correspond to the track's high-speed corners.

Figure 7.4: Control signals (measurement vs true value).

Figure 7.5: Vehicle states estimation with MHE.

Figure 7.6: \mathcal{GP} predictions, true values, and confidence intervals for errors of the states (X , Y , ψ and v).

7.4.2 Planning and control results

The designed controller is tested on two race tracks, the first one has an L-shape while the second one is of an oval form. Figs. 7.7 and 7.8 show the planned race line and the vehicle's tracking performance using regular MPC and MPC with the learning extension denoted L-MPC. It can be clearly seen that the designed controllers track well the planned race line (in red color) while exhibiting acceptable cornering capabilities. In fact, L-MPC has higher tracking precision, where the RMSE results in 0.091m for L-MPC compared to 0.121m for regular MPC. Moreover, L-MPC performs better cornering compared to regular MPC, which is mainly due to online model correction with the learning extension allowing for more aggressive driving. Furthermore, the star sign in the figures, shows that L-MPC travels a longer distance compared to MPC meaning that the learning extension allows the controller to reach higher speeds. It is worth noting that tracking precision is further improved in the second lap.

Figure 7.7: Race line tracking for lap 1.

Figs. 7.9a and 7.9b show the speed of the vehicle for both laps. Generally, L-MPC is able to reach higher speeds (up to 2.9 m/s), even though regular MPC is also fast

Figure 7.8: Race line tracking for lap 2.

enough (up to 2.78 m/s). This can further be observed in Figs. 7.10a and 7.10b where L-MPC exhibits relatively higher accelerations/decelerations and hence more aggressive racing. Fig. 7.11a and 7.11b show the corresponding steering controls of MPC and L-MPC for both laps.

Figure 7.9: Vehicle speed (a): lap 1,(b): lap 2.

Figure 7.10: Acceleration control (a): lap 1,(b): lap 2.

Figure 7.11: Steering control (a): lap 1,(b): lap 2.

The computation time for both MPC and MHE is relatively low, which allows for real-time application. This is very important since autonomous racing systems are known for fast dynamics. More importantly, MHE runs faster than MPC with an average computation time of 9.5ms compared to 20.9ms for MPC. This ensures that the new estimates are readily available to the controller and no lag is to be expected. This is clearly illustrated in Fig 7.12 which shows the required computation time during the consecutive race laps.

Figure 7.12: Computation time for MPC/MHE.

The proposed control strategy has been evaluated on an oval track as well (see Figs 7.14 and 7.15), where similar racing performance is observed. Particularly, L-MPC ensures more cornering capabilities with higher tracking precision. For laps 1 and 2, MPC/L-MPC tracking errors on the lateral and longitudinal positions are compared in Figs 7.13a and 7.13b. The corresponding RMSE lateral errors (Y position) for the whole track result in 0.044m for L-MPC against 0.082m for regular MPC. Similarly, for the longitudinal errors (X position), L-MPC scored an RMSE of 0.1m against 0.13m for regular MPC.

Figure 7.13: Tracking error for laps 1 and 2 (a): Longitudinal,(b): Lateral.

Figure 7.14: Race line tracking for lap 1.

Figure 7.15: Race line tracking for lap 2.

7.5 Conclusions

This chapter introduced a solution to the problem of autonomous racing, which is a sub-field of autonomous driving. The control part has been solved by developing an NMPC controller to handle the coupled lateral and longitudinal dynamics of the vehicle. The proposed controller is developed using a nonlinear extended kinematic bicycle model that allows for real-time application. For a more realistic approach, the controller has been coupled with an MHE that performs real-time state estimation from noisy state measurements. Moreover, a learning extension based on Gaussian processes has been proposed to correct the model mismatch of the NMPC prediction model and increase its accuracy, which further improves the racing capabilities. Finally, the optimal race line of the race track is planned offline using a nonlinear model predictive planner that takes into account the handling limits of the vehicle and the boundaries of the racing track. The proposed controller, estimator, and planner have been tested in `Matlab` simulations for two challenging race tracks, where the obtained results proved that the proposed control strategy has superior performance and ensures high-speed racing capabilities.

Chapter 8

Conclusions and Perspectives

8.1 Conclusions

The concept of autonomous driving has been around for decades and research regarding this field has considerably expanded. The self-driving technology evolved significantly and became a promising solution ever since the number of cars started increasing, which incurred high traffic and increased road accidents. These research advances allowed researchers to turn the concept of self-driving vehicles into a reality. Nowadays, commercial vehicles are readily equipped with very advanced driver assistance systems, capable of achieving certain levels of autonomy. Nevertheless, numerous problems remain unsolved and require further improvements in the existing research and technological knowledge, particularly in the fields of control, sensing, estimation, and planning. This PhD thesis further contributes to the state-of-the-art control strategies for autonomous driving with a focus on data-based reinforced control approaches.

In Chapter 2, background information on autonomous vehicles and state-of-the-art control strategies for autonomous driving have been reviewed with pertinent analysis on their strengths and limits. Vehicle modeling techniques for control design have been particularly addressed in Chapter 3 with detailed highlights on their suitability for different driving scenarios. The differences between geometric, kinematic, and dynamic modeling have been presented along with combined modeling approaches for improved control performance. Generally speaking, data-based control techniques are being used more often to solve the autonomous driving problem compared to classical control methods. However, the lack of interpretability and stability insurance

are major barriers to the deployment of such control strategies. The MPC approach is still the dominant method in classical control thanks to its predictive feature and ability to easily handle state and control constraints.

Chapter 4 has addressed the longitudinal control problem where a self-adaptive PID has been proposed to achieve speed control. Two distinct methods have been introduced, the first approach uses genetic algorithms to optimize the PID gains for different driving scenarios, which generates a data set of optimal PID gains. The latter is then used in a lookup table method to realize PID adaptation. In the second approach, an online learning neural network has been proposed to simultaneously optimize and adapt PID gains online. The shallow network makes use of the PID equations to perform gain optimization and only requires the control and tracking error information. Finally, both methods have been evaluated and compared against each other. It has been found that the GA-PID approach produces smoother control performance but requires long offline optimizations, while NN-PID presents a fast online and robust solution with learning capabilities, but its control performance is more aggressive.

Chapter 5 has dealt with the path tracking problem by introducing the adaptive MPC technique. In the first part of the chapter, the different MPC parameters have been tuned with a new improved PSO algorithm, and Laguerre functions have been proposed to approximate the MPC control signal. This approach has enabled the use of long prediction and control horizons without affecting the MPC computation time, which further improved the MPC predictions and control performance. Similar to the previous chapter, MPC parameter adaptation has been achieved using lookup tables. In the second part of the chapter, two methods have been proposed to realize MPC adaption. MLP Neural networks and ANFIS systems have been used to learn the data of optimal MPC parameters that was generated with the proposed PSO algorithm, and then perform online MPC adaption. These methods allow the controller to be more adaptive, as the neural network and ANFIS systems are able to generalize beyond the generated data set of optimal MPC parameters. The proposed strategies are assessed and compared with the standard MPC and the pure pursuit controllers in double and triple lane change maneuvers subject to wind disturbance and variable road adhesion. The results proved that the proposed strategies are able to handle

varying working conditions and to reject external disturbances with improved tracking capabilities. Overall, the NN-MPC and ANFIS-MPC are more adaptive and more accurate compared to the adaptive MPC with lookup table method.

The combined lateral and longitudinal control for autonomous driving has been addressed in Chapter 6. First, the coordinated control approach has been introduced using PSO-optimized PID for speed regulation and LPV-MPC for steering control. In this approach, the longitudinal and lateral dynamics of the vehicle have been decoupled, and the cost function of the LPV-MPC has been improved by adding exponential weights. The prediction model of the controller has been adapted with cornering stiffness coefficients that are estimated using an RLS algorithm. In the second approach, the coupled lateral and longitudinal control has been proposed using a more elaborate LPV model for the MPC controller. The latter handles both speed and steering controls, and it has been optimized with a new improved GA. Furthermore, the MPC has been built with an adaptive prediction model, where the cornering stiffness coefficients are predicted online using a feed-forward neural network. Finally, both control strategies have been tested and compared on a challenging trajectory under variable wind disturbances. The results have shown that both control strategies achieve good speed and trajectory tracking performance, but the coupled LPV-MPC approach provides much better performance whilst being real-time feasible.

In Chapter 7, a more challenging autonomous driving application has been addressed. The problem of autonomous racing has been solved using real-time NMPC coupled with a state estimator based on nonlinear MHE. The NMPC has been formulated with an extended kinematic bicycle model that takes into account engine dynamics, the same model has been used to develop the MHE, which provides the controller with accurate real-time state estimates. For optimal racing, an offline trajectory planner has been introduced, which uses the nonlinear bicycle dynamic model for more accurate planning while taking into account the handling limits of the vehicle and the boundaries of the circuit. The NMPC controller has been further enhanced by a learning extension, the latter uses Gaussian process regression to correct the mismatch between the true vehicle dynamics and the NMPC prediction model. This allows for better and more accurate predictions, which in turn results in more aggressive racing performance. The proposed strategy has been evaluated on two challenging

race tracks, where high control performance and speed racing capabilities have been achieved.

Autonomous driving, being a multidisciplinary field, is always open to improvements. Despite the huge advances achieved so far in self-driving, modern vehicles have barely made it to level 3, and fully autonomous vehicles of level 5 remain an unfulfilled challenge. This thesis explored the possibility of enhancing classical control techniques through data-based approaches. The objective is to provide powerful solutions for controlling autonomous vehicles to cope with dynamic and constantly changing environments. All the proposed methodologies have shown the capability of enhancing classical controllers and adapting to changing working conditions.

8.2 Perspectives

The approaches developed in this work can be considered as a starting landmark for further advancements in the control of autonomous vehicles. This section provides some suggestions that can further improve and extend the presented methodologies in order to address their main drawbacks.

- The adaptation of PID gains using lookup tables in Chapter 4 can be improved by using machine learning techniques to learn the generated data. This should provide a more generalized adaptation to cope with more scenarios compared to lookup tables. Furthermore, the optimization and adaptation with online neural network produce a very aggressive response that would likely induce jerk effects, hence this can be enhanced by smoothing the output of the PID controller. Finally, only the MSE cost function has been used to optimize the PID gains, other functions are susceptible to produce more optimal results and should be further investigated.
- The ANFIS approach used in Chapter 5 suffers from the curse of dimensionality, which makes it not real-time applicable. Instead of using 4 ANFIS subsystems where each one predicts one output, one can use a single system that predicts all outputs at once, to further reduce the computation time. This would require more data for better learning. Similar to the previous chapter, only the MSE

cost function has been used in the PSO algorithm, and investigating other optimization functions would improve the performance.

- In Chapter 6, the LPV formulation of MPC uses scheduling vectors with constant values at each iteration. The formulation can be enhanced by including vectors that span into the future for certain parameters like the longitudinal velocity for instance, which would significantly enhance the prediction performance of the MPC controller. In the second part of the chapter, feed-forward neural networks have been used to predict and adapt the cornering stiffness coefficients. However, temporal dependencies can be added using different types of neural networks, namely recurrent neural networks. This should vastly improve the learning process of the network to better predict the cornering stiffness coefficients
- The MHE estimator in Chapter 7 is developed using the same model of the MPC controller. Thus, it would be beneficial to use a more accurate vehicle model like the dynamic bicycle model to provide better estimates. However, this should not compromise the computation time, and it should still run relatively faster than the MPC to avoid any computation gaps. In addition, the race line planner is run offline due to its high computation burden. It would be interesting to investigate the possibility of using online planners that run in real-time and allow us to incorporate obstacle avoidance as well.
- Finally, it would be very interesting to test and evaluate the proposed controllers and the above-discussed ideas on real experimental vehicles, although this would require a fully instrumented car and an evacuated driving circuit with strict safety precautions.

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Titre : Stratégies de contrôle renforcé par apprentissage pour les véhicules autonomes.

Mots clés : Commande prédictive, Estimation d'état, Commande adaptative, Conduite autonome, Apprentissage automatique, Optimisation méta-heuristique

Résumé : Dans un monde où les gens sont constamment en mouvement et où la mobilité personnelle est préférée, le nombre de voitures personnelles sur la route ne cesse d'augmenter. Cela a induit plus de risque d'accidents de route, des conditions de circulation et de pollution de l'air plus dégradées. Par conséquent, les chercheurs travaillent depuis des décennies pour une transition vers la conduite autonome. Cette dernière a la capacité de remodeler la mobilité en diminuant les accidents de route, les embouteillages et la pollution de l'air, ce qui se traduirait par plus d'efficacité énergétique et de productivité, où le temps de conduite pourra plutôt être utilisé pour d'autres activités. Les véhicules autonomes sont des systèmes complexes constitués de plusieurs modules qui effectuent la perception, la prise de décision, la planification et le contrôle. Le module de commande, composé d'un contrôle longitudinal et d'un contrôle latéral, est essentiel pour obtenir une conduite automatique. En raison de la nature hautement dynamique et en constante évolution des environnements routiers, le module de commande des systèmes de conduite autonome doit apprendre et s'adapter à ces environnements dynamiques en exploitant les données disponibles et en utilisant différentes techniques d'apprentissage. Cette thèse apporte quelques contributions à l'état de l'art des stratégies de contrôle amélioré et appliquées à la conduite autonome. Les contributions abordent les tâches de contrôle longitudinal et latéral séparément, puis le contrôle latéral et longitudinal coordonné et couplé. Pour le contrôle longitudinal, nous proposons l'approche PID adaptatif en utilisant deux techniques différentes : l'optimisation et l'adaptation hors ligne à l'aide d'algorithmes génétiques (GA-PID) puis l'apprentissage et l'adaptation en ligne avec les réseaux de neurones (NN-PID). Pour le contrôle latéral, nous introduisons une technique de contrôle prédictif MPC adaptatif améliorée avec un nouvel algorithme PSO amé-

lioré. Ensuite, nous réalisons l'adaptation en ligne des paramètres du contrôleur en utilisant les réseaux de neurones (NN-MPC) et les systèmes d'inférence neuro-flou adaptatif (ANFIS-MPC), qui apprennent à adapter le contrôleur aux conditions de fonctionnement et aux perturbations externes. Pour le contrôle latéral et longitudinal coordonné, nous proposons un PSO-PID pour la régulation de la vitesse, et un contrôleur prédictif de type LPV-MPC pour contrôler la dynamique latérale. Le LPV-MPC est développé avec une fonction de coût améliorée pour obtenir de meilleures performances et stabilité, il est aussi formulé avec un modèle LPV adaptatif, dans lequel les coefficients de rigidité de glissement latéral des pneus sont estimés par un estimateur récursif. Ensuite, nous abordons le contrôle couplé de la vitesse et de la direction en développant un contrôleur LPV-MPC plus élaboré et capable de gérer simultanément les dynamiques latérales et longitudinales du véhicule. De plus, le modèle de prédiction du LPV-MPC est adapté en temps réel par un réseau de neurones, et sa fonction de coût est encore optimisée par un algorithme génétique amélioré. Enfin, nous abordons le problème de course autonome où le véhicule roule à ses limites de maniabilité. Nous introduisons un contrôleur prédictif de modèle non-linéaire en temps réel (NMPC) couplé avec un estimateur d'état de type (MHE). Nous résolvons le problème de course optimale par un planificateur de trajectoire hors ligne basé sur la méthode NMPC qui calcule la meilleure trajectoire tout en tenant compte des limites physiques du véhicule et des contraintes du circuit. Ensuite, nous améliorons encore la stratégie de contrôle en ajoutant une extension d'apprentissage basée sur la régression par processus de Gauss. Ce dernier améliore les prédictions NMPC en apprenant et en corrigeant le décalage entre la véritable dynamique du véhicule et le modèle de prédiction NMPC.

Title : Learning-based reinforced control strategies for autonomous vehicles.

Keywords : Model predictive control, State estimation, Adaptive control, Autonomous driving, Machine learning, Meta-heuristic optimization.

Abstract : In a world where everyone is constantly on the move and has more preferences for personal mobility, the number of cars on the road is constantly increasing. This has induced higher risks for road accidents, degraded traffic conditions, and further aggravated air pollution. Consequently, the research community has been working toward a shift to autonomous driving for decades. The latter can reshape mobility and transportation by reducing road accidents, traffic jams, and air pollution, yielding energy efficiency, convenience, and more productivity, as significant driving time will be used for other activities instead. Autonomous vehicles are complex systems consisting of several modules that perform perception, decision-making, planning, and control. The control module, consisting of longitudinal control for speed tracking and lateral control for path tracking, is essential for achieving automatic driving. Due to the highly dynamic and constantly changing nature of road environments, the control module in autonomous driving systems needs to learn and adapt to these dynamic environments by exploiting available data and using different learning techniques. This thesis contributes to the state-of-the-art enhanced control strategies applied to autonomous driving. The contributions address the longitudinal and the lateral control tasks separately and then the combined coordinated and coupled lateral and longitudinal control. For the longitudinal control, we propose the adaptive PID approach using two techniques : offline optimization and adaptation using genetic algorithms (GA-PID) and online learning and adaptation with neural networks (NN-PID). We introduce an adaptive MPC technique enhanced with a new, improved PSO algorithm for steering control. Then we achieve MPC online pa-

rameter adaption by using neural networks (NN-MPC) and adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference systems (ANFIS-MPC), which learn to adapt the controller to the changing working conditions and external disturbances. For the combined coordinated lateral and longitudinal control, we propose a PSO-PID to handle the task of speed tracking and an enhanced linear parameter varying model predictive controller (LPV-MPC) to control lateral dynamics. The LPV-MPC is enhanced with an improved cost function to provide better performance and stability and formulated with an adaptive LPV model, in which a recursive estimator estimates the tire cornering stiffness coefficients. Then, we address the coupled speed and steering control by developing a more elaborate LPV-MPC capable of simultaneously handling both lateral and longitudinal vehicle dynamics. Furthermore, a neural network adapts the controller's prediction model online, and an improved genetic algorithm further optimizes its cost function. Finally, we tackle a more challenging autonomous driving problem where the vehicle drives at its handling limits, namely autonomous racing. We introduce a real-time nonlinear model predictive controller (NMPC) coupled with a moving horizon estimator (MHE). We solve the optimal racing problem with an NMPC-based offline trajectory planner that computes the best trajectory while considering the physical limits of the vehicle and circuit constraints. Then, we further enhance the control strategy by adding a learning extension based on Gaussian process regression. The latter improves the NMPC predictions by learning and correcting the mismatch between the actual vehicle dynamics and the NMPC prediction model.